

Deliverable 1.2

Good Governance Practices

MTU

28/02/2023

**DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT
REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH**

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ABBREVIATIONS

EU	European Union
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MTU	Munster Technological University
QPL	Q-Plan International Advisors PC
CTA	Fundacion Corporacion Tecnologica de Andalucia
WR	White Research SPRL
PED	Pedal Consulting s.r.o.
S2i	Steinbeis 2i GmbH
ZSK	Rozvojova Agentura Zilinskeho Samospravneho Kraja n.o.
AUTH	Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis
RCM	Region of Central Macedonia
CAP	Consejería de Agricultura, Pesca, Agua y Desarrollo Rural
IFA	Instituto Andaluz de Investigación y Formación Agraria, Pesquera, Alimentaria y de la Producción Ecológica
BPRO	Biopro Baden-Wuerttemberg GmbH
SRA	Southern Regional Assembly
CO.	Coordinator
CR.	Contractor
AE.	Affiliated Entitites
MARCS	Multi-Actor Regional Constellation
ESIF	European Structural and Investment Fund
EAFRD	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development
SAT	Self Assessment Tool
BIC	Bio-Based Industry Consortium

UK	United Kingdom
JRC	Joint Research Centre
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
TP	Transformational Path
EG	Enabling Governance
R&D	Research And Development
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisations
GPP	Green Public Procurement
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
DAFM	Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine

Executive Summary

This document constitutes the collection of “Good Governance Practices” elaborated as a deliverable (D1.2) in the framework of the ROBIN project.

ROBIN sets out to empower Europe’s regional authorities to fulfil their role as agents of just, inclusive, and resilient economic development for their territories. The project provides support to co-shape their governance structures and models in ways that accelerate the deployment of their **circular bioeconomy targets**, while also promoting social innovation and accounting for different territorial contexts. Under this light, ROBIN entails several activities that involve collecting, producing, and processing data to generate meaningful insights that will feed into the project and fuel the co-creation and delivery of demand-driven and evidence-based results.

In this context, Deliverable 1.2 “Good Governance Practices” sets out to identify a range of good governance practices for supporting local operators and innovation developers in the circular bioeconomy. These practices are drawn from across six geographical regions covering the continent of Europe, supporting different stakeholder groupings, and covering a multitude of different support types, including policy innovation, education and awareness, social innovations, networking, financial supports and many more. In total **75 practices** have been documented in Section 4.2 and a further **10** of these have been further developed into case studies within Section 4.1.

This **inventory of good practices and case studies** will serve as input to later ROBIN Work Package 2 activities in supporting the 5 ROBIN regions towards the co-development of regional governance models and structures. To support these efforts, the report highlights key information from these practices, including whether the models have been or may be **replicated** to other regions, which **stakeholders** are supported, what is the **territorial context** and what are some of the **environmental, social, and economic benefits resulting from their deployment**. In addition, the good practices have been selected on the basis of their alignment with the definition of good practice, outlined in Section 2, and care has been taken to ensure that a broad diversity of good practices has been included to give the regions the widest scope possible. In addition to supporting the regions in co-creating their good governance practices, the best practices will be useful for other regions across Europe and beyond who are looking for successful mechanisms to support regional bioeconomy development.

The 75 good practices included within Section 4.2, include examples from the **Balkan Region (12), Central Europe (7), Eastern Europe (8), Mediterranean (12), Northern Europe (24) and Western Europe (12)**. The breakdown of countries within these regional clusters is described in Section 2. Considering the categorization of instruments covered, and the closest link between the practices and categories of instruments described by Elbersen et al., (2020) the practices break down across the following instruments: fiscal and financial instruments (24), regulatory instruments (7), information and advisory instruments (15), networking, collaboration, and joint planning instruments (20), voluntary instruments (3), other instruments (6). However, many of practices straddle across multiple instruments. Drawing from the good practices, several case studies have been selected to further elaborate the good examples, covering a wide geographical and territorial setting, and a broad array of initiatives from social innovations, public procurement programmes, funding programmes, social media awareness campaigns, business models and regulatory instruments. There are found in Section 4.1.

To complete the analysis, in Section 4.2. the inventory of good practices has been further **classified against a typology of circular bioeconomy governance models** developed in ROBIN Task 1.2,

creating a linkage between both studies, and providing practical inspiration towards the implementation of circular bioeconomy governance structures and models. This document will help to provide an interesting analysis of transformation paths, enabling and constraining governance factors, drivers, focus areas and collaborations, providing a better understanding of both the strengths and limitations of the good practices available within the regions studied.

Introduction

The current document represents the Deliverable 1.2 “Good Governance Practices” of the ROBIN project which has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation funding programme under Grant Agreement No 101060504.

ROBIN aims to **empower Europe’s Regions to adapt their governance models and structures to accelerate the achievement of their circular bioeconomy targets** while promoting social innovation and accounting for different territorial contexts. Europe’s regional authorities have a crucial role to play as agents of just, inclusive, and resilient economic development for their territories. To this end, we establish and demonstrate the potential of innovative circular bioeconomy governance structures and models in 5 European Regions within **Ireland, Germany, Spain, Slovakia, and Greece**. ROBIN will provide them with all the necessary support for networking and mutual learning, as well as a practical **digital toolbox** to drive the operation of successful governance models.

To support its endeavours, the consortium of ROBIN brings together a complementary and interdisciplinary group of 13 partners across 6 different countries within the European Union (EU), as presented in the **Σφάλμα! Το αρχείο προέλευσης της αναφοράς δεν βρέθηκε..**

Table 1. Robin Partners

Partner Role*	Partner No	Partner Name	Partner Short name	Country
CO	1	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	QPL	Greece
CR	2	FUNDACION CORPORACION TECNOLOGICA DE ANDALUCIA	CTA	Spain
CR	3	WHITE RESEARCH SPRL	WR	Belgium
CR	4	PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	PED	Slovakia
CR	5	STEINBEIS 2I GMBH	S2I	Germany
CR	6	ROZVOJOVA AGENTURA ZILINSKEHO SAMOSPRAVNEHO KRAJA NO	ZSK	Slovakia
CR	7	MUNSTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	MTU	Ireland
CR	8	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	Greece
CR	9	REGION OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA	RCM	Greece

Partner Role*	Partner No	Partner Name	Partner Short name	Country
CR	10	CONSEJERÍA DE AGRICULTURA, PESCA, AGUA Y DESARROLLO RURAL	CAP	Spain
AE	10.1	INSTITUTO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACIÓN Y FORMACIÓN AGRARIA, PESQUERA, ALIMENTARIA Y DE LA PRODUCCIÓN ECOLÓGICA	IFA	Spain
CR	11	BIOPRO BADEN-WUERTTEMBERG GMBH	BPRO	Germany
CR	12	SOUTHERN REGIONAL ASSEMBLY	SRA	Ireland

* CO = Coordinator, CR = Contractor, AE = Affiliated Entities

To ensure that ROBIN delivers on its aim to deploy circular bioeconomies at regional level within the territorial approach, 5 diverse EU regions are engaged as partners within the project. These regions are:

- Andalucía, Spain
- Baden-Württemberg, Germany
- Central Macedonia, Greece
- Southern Region, Ireland
- Zilina, Slovakia

Each ROBIN regional cluster contains a regional government partner and a supporting partner. In addition, Work Package 1 sets out to develop Multi-Actor Regional Constellations (MARC) in each participating region (Task 1.1), comprising quadruple-helix stakeholders from local government, business community, academic institutions, primary biomass producers, and civil society. Through the project, the MARC members will be active in co-creating and informing development of regional governance structures in their specific regions. Other tasks in Work Package 1, focus on assessing the current regional policy mix of these regions (Task 1.4), but also assessing the current EU landscape in terms of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models (Task 1.2), and Good Governance Practices for Supporting Local Operators and Innovation developers (Task 1.3). These activities will help to inform the co-creation of Regional Governance Models taking place within the regions during WP2. A typology of circular bioeconomy governance models will also be developed.

Task 1.3 ROBIN which is directly related to the current **D1.2** aims to perform a deep dive into good practices of regional governments supporting local operators and innovation developers via appropriate business models and social measures. A screening exercise, involving all regions has results in an inventory (long list) of 75 good practices within and outside the ROBIN regions. Partners MTU, AUTH and S2i have, in addition, created 10 case studies highlighting a diverse cross-section of these good practices. The long list of good practices has been classified under the typology of governance models developed in **T1.2**, providing practical inspiration for the regions to improve their governance models.

The work provides key insights into examples of actions or enablers which can support the development of the bioeconomy on a regional level and will allow the 5 regions to co-create their policies including best practices, selecting the examples which best suit their individual needs and objectives. In this respect, the information will be useful to further support activities undertaken during **ROBIN WP2** Co-creating the regional governance models and structures, **WP3** Setting up and operating the regional governance models and structures, and **WP4** Evaluation and sharing of best practices, peer-learning and knowledge transfer.

With the above in mind, this Deliverable 1.2 report is **structured in 5 distinct chapters**, as follows:

- **Chapter 1** provides introductory information about the project and Deliverable 1.2, its objectives and structure.
- **Chapter 2** presents a short literature review and context for the existing study considering the EU and regional bioeconomy context and existing and previous initiatives.
- **Chapter 3** describes the methodology that is applied to generate the Deliverable 1.2 results.
- **Chapter 4** provides an overview of the findings and includes 10 good practice case studies (Section 4.1), the classification of ROBIN good practices and the inventory of good practices (Section 4.2).
- **Chapter 5** summarizes the findings of the report and concludes on the next steps foreseen in the framework of the project which relate to D1.2.

Annexed in the document are (i) data collection template which has been developed for the collection of our inventory of good practices (ii) case study guidelines used by the MTU, AUTH and S2i.

1. Context for Study

The development of a strong circular bioeconomy to support implementation Europe's Green Deal and the target of climate neutrality by 2050 is promoted by the European Commission and many of its member states. In the addition to the benefits offered to Europe as a whole, as well as its member states at national level, the benefits for European regions, and the importance of regional participation is also a key consideration. Regions play an important role in the further development of the European bioeconomy as they can support the establishment of (regional) innovative value chains. Regions are also best situated to identify the locally available feedstocks (from agriculture, agrifood, forestry, residual and side streams, etc.) that can initiate and scale up bioeconomy development, and can play a key role in attracting investments in local demonstration or flagship projects by benefiting from the European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF) or the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD), creating jobs, economic growth and new opportunities for the primary sectors (Bio-based Industries Consortium, 2017). They also have a clear understanding of the territorial (urban, coastal, rural) needs and synergies of their regions.

A 2017 report highlighted the emergence of bioeconomy regions across Europe, highlighting the opportunities for bioeconomy development in these regions (Bio-based Industries Consortium, 2017). Several initiatives have been undertaken to support the development of regions in further developing their bioeconomies. Some of these include:

- Model Demonstrator Regions for Sustainable Chemical Production: Six model demonstrator regions for sustainable chemical production were established in 2016 to encourage investments in sustainable chemicals production in Europe that could contribute to the development of the circular economy, for example by taking advantage of locally available feedstock such as biomass and urban waste (SUSCHEM, 2017). The project included the development of a Self-Assessment Tool (SAT) to help regions determine their readiness level for investment in sustainable chemical production (European Chemical Regions Network, 2017).
- Vanguard Bioeconomy Pilot Initiative which aims at supporting the deployment of high TRL technologies, through the setting up of transregional value chains in an industry-driven process, where public support comes into play to help bridging the valley of death (Vanguard Bioeconomy Pilot Initiative, 2022).
- The Bio-based Industry Consortium's (BIC) regions bioeconomy platform is a digital, partnering platform where regions and industry can make contact based on mutual interest. The platform focuses on creating local value chains and supporting access to finance, namely helping regions and industry bridge the gap between bio-based investment opportunities and financial incentives at regional level. It is currently home to 51 regions (Bio-based Industries Consortium, 2020)

In addition, a growing number of EU-funded bioeconomy projects, such as POWER4BIO, ICT-BIOCHAIN, Enabling, and BIOEASTsUP, have taken a regional approach in deploying the main research and capacity building activities of their projects, often resulting in the development of supporting tools to enable regional bioeconomy growth.

The pace of regional bioeconomy development, and its supporting governance models and practices, varies from region to region. The EU Bioeconomy Strategy notes that a significant number of European regions have included bioeconomy-related priorities in their Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisation (European Commission, 2018). The importance of developing regional bioeconomy strategies and rural renaissance is also one of the points of the Bioeconomy Stakeholder Manifesto which notes the potential for the bioeconomy to reinvigorate rural regions (European Bioeconomy Stakeholders, 2017). Charles et al. (2016) has previously explored the development of regional bioeconomy strategies in the context of the BioStep project focusing on 4 regional case studies in Scotland (United Kingdom), South-West Netherlands (The Netherlands), SaxonyAnhalt (Germany) and Veneto (Italy). This study explored aspects including, how bioeconomy was defined within these strategies, which were the driving institutions behind these strategies, what types of governance structures were in place and what has been the involvement of stakeholders and the public within these strategies. Recent work by the EU Joint Research Centre (JRC) has focused on the mapping of regional strategies across Europe and has found that their deployment has accelerated since the launch of the updated EU Bioeconomy Strategy in 2018. Considering NUTS1, NUTS 2 and NUTS 3 region, the JRC study found that 194 regions in EU27 have a strategic framework for bioeconomy in place or are in the process of doing so. Overall, there are 359 bioeconomy-relevant strategies at regional level in the EU. Of those, 334 frameworks are published in the form of documents such as strategies, action plans, roadmaps, and the rest are under development (Haarich and Kirhmayr-Novak, 2022).

The ROBIN project advances previous work by taking an EU-wide approach to explore different typologies of regional bioeconomy governance structures and models, and identifying good practices for supporting local operators and innovation developers in the bioeconomy. It also supports the sharing of these practices within 5 regions across the EU comprising regional government partners and quadruple-helix stakeholders, for their further analysis and to support the regions to co-creation of their governance models. In this way the project supports in delivering inter-regional cooperation, sharing of best practices, and peer-learning, a key region recommendation of the European Bioeconomy Stakeholders Manifesto (European Bioeconomy Stakeholders, 2017).

2. Methodology

The methodology for Deliverable 1.2 is divided into 2 interlinked components:

1. A screening of good practices of regional governments supporting local operators and innovation developers via appropriate business models and social measures, to develop an inventory (long list) of at least 50 good practices within and outside the ROBIN regions. The long list of good practices will be classified under the typology of T1.2, providing practical inspiration for the ROBIN regions to improve their governance models.
2. Assessment of the inventory of good practices against specific criteria to select a list of 10 cases to be further studied. The further development of 10 case studies showcasing how regional government has encouraged social innovation and business models to promote circular bioeconomy.

2.1 Compilation of Inventory of Good Practices

2.1.1 Defining Good Practice

To assess which practices constitute good practice, for inclusion within the inventory, it was first necessary to define the term “good practice” based on literature and previous studies. This approach has previously been used by Hyland (2021) as a first step to cataloguing good practices. Various organisations have offered their interpretations as to what criteria lead to a practices being defined as ‘good’; most notably the FAO and ENRD.

(FAO, 2013) “A good practice is not only a practice that is good, but a practice that has been proven to **work well and produce good results**, and it is therefore recommended as a model. It is a successful experience, which has been **tested and validated**, in the broad sense, which **has been repeated and deserves to be shared so that a greater number of people can adopt it**”.

ENRD (2018) “Good practice” refers to strategies, programmes, projects, procedures, management, and implementation practices that should be at least:

- Implemented with **positive results**.
- Successful, (innovative), **tested and validated**: it contributes to the improved performance of an entrepreneurship/farm/organisation and this contribution is recognised.
- **Transferable: it can be adopted in and adapted to other contexts**.

Several commonalities exist within these definitions including:

- **Demonstrating positive results**.
- **Has been tested and validated**.
- **Has been or can be transferred and/or replicated**.

These common criteria have been included in our criteria for screening of best practices within this report.

2.1.2 *What is a bioeconomy governance practice?*

During Task 1.2 of ROBIN, research was undertaken to identify regional bioeconomy governance models and structures which are existing in regions across the EU. Task 1.3 and Deliverable 1.2, on the other hand investigates the types of bioeconomy governance practices which can be used to support local operators and innovation developers within regions. If the bioeconomy structures are the overarching structures, models, and strategies for overseeing bioeconomy implementation within regions, then the governance practices are the individual enablers or initiatives which can support development of different bioeconomy objectives. Examples of such enablers may include:

- Business Model Supports (e.g., support in developing sustainable business models, financing support, incubators for new start-ups)
- Regional Policy Supports (e.g., incentives for practitioners, or bio-based procurement programmes)
- Technical supports (e.g., accessing R&D, pilot facilities and scale up, product testing)
- Collaboration supports (e.g., support in networking/matchmaking)
- Education, Skills, and Knowledge Sharing
- Support for social innovations

Previously the POWER4BIO project undertook some research into suitable regional policies to support bio-based business models, and as part of the work sought to characterize the existing policies in place for bio-based economy (Elbersen *et al.*, 2020). The project developed a categorisation of instruments based on common policy instrument categorisations that are used in policy research. The following types of instruments were identified.

- Fiscal and financial instruments
- Regulatory instruments
- Information and advisory instruments
- Networking, collaboration, and joint planning instruments
- Voluntary instruments
- Other instruments (Elbersen *et al.*, 2020)

The purposes of the current task and report is to map governance practices from regions across Europe, which are enabling important aspects of regional bioeconomy development. These will later be used by partners when co-creating their own bioeconomy governance models.

2.1.3 *Collection of bioeconomy good governance practices*

To support the collection of at least 50 bioeconomy good governance practices from across Europe, ensuring a large number is achieved with good geographical coverage, ROBIN partners divided Europe into specific jurisdictions which were then allocated to specific regional clusters (one regional partner and one additional partner) to conduct a scoping of good practices within these regions. The breakdown was as follows:

- **AuTH, QPL & RCM** – Balkan Cluster (Main Country: Greece, Other Countries: Cyprus, Bulgaria, Albania, Serbia, Montenegro, Romania, North Macedonia, Croatia, Bosnia, Slovenia)
- **S2i & BPRO** – Central Europe Cluster (Main Country: Germany, Other Countries: Austria, Switzerland, Netherlands, Denmark, Poland)
- **PED & ZSK** – Eastern Europe Cluster (Main Country: Slovakia, Other Countries: Czech Republic, Hungary, Ukraine, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova)
- **CTA & CAG** – Mediterranean Cluster (Main Country: Spain, Other Countries: Portugal, Italy, Malta)
- **MTU & SRA** – North-West Europe Cluster (Main Country: Ireland, Other Countries: UK, Sweden, Norway, Finland, Iceland)
- **MTU & WHITE** – Western Europe Cluster (Main Country: Belgium, Other Countries: France, Luxembourg)

To ensure that consistent information was collected for each good governance practice, a data collection template was developed to support partners in completing this desk-based review. This template is described in section 3.1.4. The template was developed and circulated to partners for review and input with a final template agreed and circulated to partners on 26th of October 2022. Regional clusters then had a period until 2nd of December 2022, to collect a target at least 12-15 good practices per region, with an interim call held on 16th of November to ensure that collection was on track.

As a first step regional partners investigated from within the governance structures identified within their regions as part of T1.2. For example, where a regional strategy, governance structure or cluster was in place, perhaps it was delivering or offering certain good practices to support regional bioeconomy development. In addition, there are many initiatives and projects on which the project partners have participated or coordinated. So, project partners also searched within their networks, to consider relevant projects which may offer tools or models which could also be included for best practice. Some of these (e.g., BIOVOICES and ICT-BIOCHAIN) have been included in the final inventory.

2.1.4 Bioeconomy Good Governance Practice Collection Template

The template to collect bioeconomy good governance practices is described in simplified form in Table 2 below. The focus of the template is to collect a detailed description of the practice with useful information for the regional partners to understand and repeat the practices, and to also bring together important criteria to allow us to analyse, compare and select a final list of case studies. The template has several components, including identifier information, geographical location and context, and description, driver, territorial context and type of practice. The template also includes questions related to defined criteria for good practice as described above, including:

- **Working and demonstrating positive results – the template asks for contribution of practice to environmental, social, and economic impacts.**
- **Has been tested and validated – the template asks to the nature of beneficiaries, level of uptake, and the duration to which the practice has been operation.**
- **Has been or can be transferred and/or replication – the template seeks to understand whether the practice can be replicated in other settings/jurisdictions and to understand if there are barriers to regional deployment.**

Table 2. Information Requested in Data Collection Template.

Good practice name	Name of the good governance practice identified	Short text (5-10 words)
Country / Region	Country/ region/locality where the practice has been implemented	Short text
Year Implemented	Year that the good practice was implemented within the specific region	A number
Problem Statement	Context of the deployment of good practice (Example: does the good practice help to resolve a barrier, or initiate an action to support local operators?)	Short text (50 words max.)
Executive summary	Descriptive and short summary of the selected good practice	Short text (50 - 100 words max.)
Type of practice	Choose from the drop down list the term which best describes the model of practice e.g. social innovation, public procurement model, educational model, incentive model, non-financial business support, other	Drop Down List
If Other	Complete if other is chosen in Type of practice column	Short text
Good Governance Practice Description	Longer Description of the Good Practice: (What were the main drivers? What were the ambitions of the practice? What barriers were needed to be overcome?, What was the enabling potential of implementation?, Was it developed through a project (FP, Interreg, EIP Agri, BBI_CBE JU etc)?, Was it part of a governmental measure? Was it part of a governmental measure? Who was the promoter of the practice?)	Long text (200 - 250 words max.)

Good practice name	Name of the good governance practice identified	Short text (5-10 words)
Deployment Setting	Choose from the drop down list the geographical context of deployment (urban, Peri-urban, rural, coastal, mountainous / upland, multiple, other)	Drop Down List
If Other	Complete if other is chosen in Deployment Settings column	Short text
Replication potential	Has it been transferred or is it transferrable to other regions or sectors? If not, is there potential to transfer and replicate	Short text (1 - 20 words)
Regional deployment considerations	Important deployment barriers for other regions if any	Short text (1-20 words)
Stakeholders / Beneficiaries	Choose from the drop down list the type of stakeholder that is most supported by the good practice	Drop Down List
Level of Uptake	Number of stakeholders availing or subscribing to the good practices	Drop Down List
Is the practice currently in operation?	Is the practice currently in operation within the region?	Short text (1 - 5 words)
Number of years that the measure has been operational in the region	How long since its introduction has the practice been in operation within the region?	A Number
Environmental Impact	Environmental impact or benefits resulting from implementation of good practice, if relevant	Short text (20 - 40 words)
Social Impact	Social impact or benefits resulting from implementation of good practice, if relevant	Short text (20 - 40 words)
Economic Impact	Economic impact or benefits resulting from implementation of good practice, if relevant	Short text (20 - 40 words)
Organisation name	Name of the responsible organisation or authority that has implemented or oversees the good practice	Short text
Link	Link to the detailed info of about the good practice	A web link

2.1.5 *Classification of good practices based on typology of governance structures.*

In addition, good practices were classified based on the typology of governance structures previously developed in ROBIN T1.2 and outlined by AUTH in D1.1. In this task, 20 model case studies of governance structures, models and strategies were analysed to inform the development of a typology for circular bioeconomy governance structures based on Dietz et al. (2018) who had developed an earlier taxonomy of political support measures. Classification of the best practices

using the typology of governance structures developed through ROBIN can help to analyse and distinguish between different governance practices and approaches.

A more detailed description of the typology is provided along with the classification of good practices based on typology of governance structures in Section 4.2.

2.1.6 Selection of case studies

To shortlist a set of at least 10 case studies from the larger inventory of practices, an initial screening was undertaken to remove any practices which contained insufficient information to be considered for further analysis.

Following this, a review of all practices was undertaken to compare which practices demonstrated a clear overlap with the good practice criteria defined earlier.

In addition, consideration was given to ensuring good diversity of practice, such that a broad range of case studies could be provided for consideration by regions. This included the need to ensure that models associated with different types of practices, and covering different territorial contexts are represented within the case studies. The 10 case studies are elaborated in Section 4.1.

2.1.7 Development of case studies

To develop case studies, an approach was taken to supplement information from literature (e.g., news items, articles, regional policy/strategy documents, etc.) with, where feasible, interviews with some of the primary actors involved to understand the good practice in more detail. A guidance document to support development of case studies and any interviews was developed by MTU, with an agreed approach for developing and completing case studies during December and January 2022. A suggested format and questions for completing the case study are included in Table 3 although this could be tailored to the case study and interviewee where required.

Task leader MTU reviewed (one or more) draft versions of each of the case studies, after which case study leaders produced the final draft case study content. The final case studies can be found in Section 4.1.

Table 3. Suggested Format and Questions for Case Study Interviews.

Theme / Category	Question / Guidance
Background of region in which good practice waste demonstrated	Provide some information about the region in which the good practice was demonstrated - the country and local situation. In what type of deployment setting did this take place (urban, rural, coastal etc?). At what stage of development is the bioeconomy at within this region? Does the local government place an active role in the bioeconomy development - if so, how?
Context for deployment of good practice	What specific challenges were the good practices aiming to address? Was there baseline information available to assess the status of the situation? What was the inspiration/foundation for the implementation of the good practice? Who were involved in its development and how difficult was it to bring to fruition?
Implementation of the good practice	What steps were taken to launch the good practice? When was the good practice implemented and how long has it been implemented for? What has the uptake level being like and what type of stakeholders have benefited from the practice?
Involvement of regional government or public bodies in the development of the practice	Where relevant, describe the role of regional government or public bodies in developing or supporting the practice.
Results of Good Practice	What has been the result of implementation of the good practice? How have you measured/assessed this? Has it been successful in achieving the initial aims (if so, indicated how)? Has it delivered specific contributions on economic, environmental, and social sustainability in the context of the region's bioeconomy – if so, please describe how (be as quantitative as possible e.g., number of stakeholders, emissions reduction contribution etc).
Replication of Good Practice	Is there interest from other regions/bodies in relation to replication of this practice? Do you know if it has been replicated in other regions? If so, which regions? Do you see potential for its replication to other regions? If not, why not. If so, is it suitable for implementation in all regions, or specific regions (what are the dynamics required for replication). Are there barriers that regions should be prepared for if implementation this practice.
Case Study examples	Are there any specific case studies in your region you can mention which have benefited from the practice (e.g., a success case). This could be a company who has scaled, new products on the market, a specific target of regional government that has been achieved and so on.
Lessons Learned from Implementation	Lessons learned. What worked well? What did not work so well? What unexpected barriers had to be overcome? What would you do different (or in another order) next time? Further take-home messages.
Future plans	Are there any future plans for development of the good practice
Further Information	References (relevant literature for further reading)

Results

The target KPI for identification of good governance practices was set at 50 from within and outside the ROBIN regions of Europe. In total **84** practices were collected by ROBIN partners from across the regional clusters outlined in Section 3. Following on from a preliminary analysis, it was determined that 9 practices contained insufficient information to be considered as best practice and were therefore excluded. This left a list of **75** practices which could be included within the long list inventory of good practices. An analysis of the inventory of good practices, including their classification based on the typology of good governance models and a description of each practice is included in T4.2.

To select **10** good practices for further development as case studies, a review of all good practices was undertaken to identify which of those met the defined criteria associated with good practice, and demonstrated good impact, whilst also ensuring sufficient diversity of practice type and diverse territorial settings. The case studies are presented next in Section 4.1

2.2 Case Studies

Out of 75 good practices identified by the different ROBIN partners from regions across Europe, 10 of these have been further elaborated into larger case studies to provide ideas and inspiration for regions across Europe looking to develop and promote their bioeconomies. To select the case studies consideration was given to ensure that they met the definition of good practice outlined in Section 3, and to ensure coverage of different instrument categories and deployment settings. In this regard we selected examples which cover the different categories of instrument outlined by Elberson et al., (2020), including fiscal and financial, regulatory instruments, information and advisory instruments, networking, collaboration and joint planning instruments and voluntary instruments. Practical examples of what can be achieved and scaled, through municipalities and their public and private partners in different settings are evidenced by case studies such as **Greve Biogas “Magic Factory”** and **Grand Est Bioeconomy**. The impact and importance of government interventions to support and regulate for more sustainable innovations can be showcased through **Skåne's public procurement programme**. While the importance of communication, education and social innovation are also highlighted through the various case studies, including **BIOVOICES**. While not all are active at a regional but national level example, **Italy's plastic bag ban**, shows what can be achieved through smart government policies supporting the scale-up of sustainable new industries, something with regional potential as well as national impact.

The case studies are shortlisted in Table 4. and further outlined in detail in this section.

Table 4. Inventory of Good Governance Practices

Case Study #	Case Study Name	Country, Region
1	Region of Skåne's Innovation-oriented Public Procurement Programme	Skåne, Sweden
2	Greve Biogas "Magic Factory"	Oslofjord, Norway
3	Video shorts in social media (BIOVOICES)	Italy
4	BIOVALE Innovation Biocamp	Yorkshire and the Humber, UK
5	Italian Ban on Plastic Bags	Italy
6	Grand Est Bioeconomy	Grand Est, France
7	Baden-Württemberg Bioeconomy Congress	Baden-Württemberg, Germany
8	National Procurement Database for Biobased Products	Zeeland, North Brabant, Overijssel and North Holland, Netherlands
9	Edible Landscape Project CLG	Northwest, Ireland
10	Funding programs regarding bioeconomy topics in Baden-Württemberg	Baden-Württemberg, Germany

Case Study 1 - Region of Skåne's Innovation-oriented Public Procurement Program

Typology: Fiscal & Financial

Regional background

Figure 1. Map of Sweden showing Skåne region

The first good practice is situated in the region of Skåne, in Sweden. Skåne has close proximity to cross-border regions, especially near the Öresund Strait, and the region also occupies a strategic location as a hub between Scandinavia and continental Europe. The Öresund strait area is named after the body of water separating Sweden and Denmark and is bounded by Skåne and the Danish capital region, Zealand. The Öresund strait area is the most densely populated area in Scandinavia, with good transport links such as road and rail tunnels, and strong economic and geographic links across the strait.

The region of Skåne's has moved away from traditional manufacturing dependence in recent decades, towards greater reliance on services related to human capital such as business services and financial intermediation. This shift has increased employment and productivity in these sectors. Skåne's economy contributed significantly to the economic growth of Sweden, until the financial crisis associated with the Great Recession. Until 2007, Skåne's economic growth was close to Sweden's average and generated around 12% of the country's economic growth. Skåne's economy was hit particularly hard in the first two years of the Great Recession but has recovered well in comparison to the Swedish average. Unemployment rates have also recovered well, even though they were relatively high due to population growth and immigration from other Swedish regions (OECD, 2012).

The regional governance context plays a strong role in the emergence of this good practice, which concerns a public procurement initiative. The public governance system of Sweden comprises the municipalities, the county/regions, and the central government. The county/regions are relatively weak in terms of power, as most power and functions are held by the municipalities and central government. The central government has the most important say in terms of strategic planning and allocation of public investment, with most of it devoted to welfare services (OECD, 2012). Sweden has an income equalization system for regional and local governance whose goal is *"to put all municipalities and county councils in Sweden on an equal financial footing to deliver equal levels of services to their residents, irrespective of the income of local authority residents and other structural factors. The intention is for differences in local taxes to largely reflect differences in efficiency and in*

levels of services and charges, and not to be due to differences in structural conditions” (Ministry of Finance and the Swedish Association of Local Authorities and Regions, 2008). This equalization system is based on costs, income, and adjustment grants.

Regional governments mainly develop investment plans that are implemented and financed by the central government. For example, in Skåne, most of the regional investment in 2011 was financed by operating revenue (OECD, 2012). The region of Skåne’s actual powers is thus somewhat limited and their ability to undertake independent initiatives depends mostly on the availability of funds coming from EU programs. The region has a say in the decision-making process, but most implementation and financing are still bound by a central mandate. One of the regional fund programmes of the central government of Sweden is Skåne-Blekinge with a budget of €880 million. Each region has a partnership fund between country councils, municipalities and county administrative boards and other associations and stakeholders. Through them, the maximization of the impact for the region is planned through project applications for EU funds. There is a program stipulating goals, rules, and investment projects, as well as actors and implicated areas. The programs are monitored by committees which are consisted of NGOs, representatives of the authorities, and other stakeholders. Evaluations are carried out to ensure and improve the overall quality of projects and programs.

Context for deployment of good practice

The type of deployment setting of the good practice was in the urban context, and the type of good practice was in the field of public procurement. The good practice was initiated between 2014 to 2016. Since its formal establishment as a region, Skåne has used its regional government resources to maximize its influence on investment decisions, even though other levels of government in Sweden keep most of the formal power. Furthermore, it has established close links with municipalities as well as key regional actors. It has thus been able to engage its regional government to lobby for its own agenda at central government level, as well as on the international level.

Implementation of the good practice

Following an analysis carried out in 2011 concerning the regions of Skåne's impacts on climate change emissions, the regional council discovered that 40% of Skåne's CO₂ emissions were generated through its healthcare sector with a large contribution from disposable products. The region of Skåne introduced an innovation-oriented procurement program focused on the sustainable

procurement of bio-based aprons as a mechanism to reduce healthcare emissions. Disposable

Figure 2. Bio-Based aprons of Skåne region

aprons were considered an interesting product for innovation procurement, due to their environmental impact and relatively straightforward production, as the supplier could concentrate primarily on developing a climate-neutral material with the required product properties. In 2014, Skåne's healthcare sector was responsible for using and disposing of 5.2 million single-use aprons, generating the equivalent of 300 tons of CO₂ emissions. The region of Skåne understood that the climate impact caused by these kinds of products can be reduced by limiting unnecessary consumption, but also finding new materials offering better performance and lower weight, as well as replacing fossil-based materials with fossil-free alternatives through, for example, innovation procurement.

As the products were not yet available on the market, the region of Skåne undertook, with the financial support of the Swedish Energy Agency, an innovation procurement process for the supply of 5.2 million bio-based disposable aprons (ICLEI, 2017). The aim of the pilot project was to procure a climate-neutral product and test an approach and develop the knowledge and ability of the region to use

this type of public procurement innovation process in the future. The winner of this procurement process was also able to secure some financial support for their use of bio-based materials (ICLEI, 2017). The winning company was an innovative regional company and some of the raw materials used were sourced locally and sustainably: starch from Kristianstad and chalk from Örebro.

Involvement of regional government or public bodies in the development of the practice

In the case of the good practice, since no climate-neutral disposable protective aprons were available on the market at that time, the Region of Skåne embarked on an innovation-oriented public procurement process to purchase aprons, made primarily from renewable (bio-based) material.

This good practice was one of the main projects of the Skåne region funded by the EU and aimed to support the clean growth objectives of the region. One of the goals, was also helping small and medium enterprises increase their competitiveness as well as establishing new clean tech companies. Prior to the project, an evaluation was carried out which concluded that Skåne has an established strength in clean technology companies, with the main fields being waste disposal technology, energy efficiency or recycling, and wastewater treatment. One of the key goals of the project was to develop collaboration between public sector, companies, and academia, to develop new products and new technologies to be sold on international markets.

Evaluating and monitoring public investment projects is still a centralized task. In this case, the Swedish Government, through Vinnova (Sweden's government agency administering state funding for research and development) commissioned an Environmental Management Board for the procurement to be carried out. The innovation procurement process was applied as a pilot project with support from the Swedish Energy Agency to support the target of the region to be fossil-free in 2020. Given the financing role and policy setting of the central level authorities, they remained

responsible for evaluation and monitoring. On the regional level and for bioeconomy strategies, user feedback mechanisms were established at a satisfactory level.

Results of good practice

The tender comprised the supply of 5.2 million bio-based disposable aprons. The process began in 2014 and concluded in May 2016 with the contract awarded to a company for the supply of disposable aprons consisting of 91% renewable material, which was 60% bio polyethylene and 40% calcium carbonate. There was also an improvement in the quality and the design of the aprons, in comparison to the aprons which were formerly purchased. The product also informs users on how to use the aprons via QR-codes available on the aprons. The codes give the opportunity for users to find instructions for recycling, as well as information regarding the manufacturer's code of conduct.

The procurement process helped many companies to increase their competitiveness in the field of climate-neutral disposable products. For both the company that won the negotiating process and other bidders, the process resulted in a technology boost that increased their competitiveness and fostered their capacity building in meeting the increased demand for disposable products that are environmentally friendly. For the Region of Skåne, the pilot project meant, not only, that it was possible to stimulate innovation which led to the development of more climate-neutral products, but also that it was possible to create a model for how a successful PPI could be implemented in future processes.

Finally, Skåne Region developed a Carbon Footprint Calculation tool to monitor CO₂ emissions from products with a high climate impact. The calculations take emissions, costs, and the product's weight and consumption per month into account. According to the Carbon Footprint Calculator and with reference to conventional plastic aprons, the purchase and use of bio-based aprons resulted in savings of 250 tons per year of CO₂ emissions.

Figure 3. Bio-based aprons of Skåne region

Replication of good practice

For the Region of Skåne, the procurement exercise meant not only that it was possible to stimulate innovation, which led to the development of a more climate-neutral product, but that it was also possible to create a model for how a public procurement innovation process can be implemented, with lessons - and newly developed materials - that can be implemented in future processes. For the regional deployment considerations, this model could be suitable for adoption in regions facing similar challenges, or the model could be adapted to consider other materials which provide such challenges.

Future plans

The knowledge and experience acquired in this case study can be used for similar procurements in the future, particularly those that involve single-use products, for which the aim is to reduce their impacts on climate.

Lessons Learned

- The incentive of supplying large quantities of a product is not enough to result in offers that are attractive from the market, especially in the case of protective aprons. Activities that have to do with pre-procurement market dialogue and engagement, and tender remodelling can be very helpful to attract qualified actors for the participation in the procurement.
- Many skills from a plethora of different fields are required to create and apply good tender documents and specifications. A continuous dialogue with industry representatives is crucial for success.
- When considering innovation, the development of a product is not necessarily completed once the tender is out. When a 'negotiated procedure' in public procurement is employed, it can significantly improve the quality of the tender that is published by the contracting authority, its cost and the final product delivered.
- A public procurement innovation procedure that is well implemented, not only can lead to the development of a functional new product but can also result in developing new skills among suppliers and procurers.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.skane.se/en/politics-and-organisation/doing-business-with-us/procurement/innovation-procurement/>

Previous case study:

<https://www.biobasedconsultancy.com/en/procurementtools111/good-practice-examples/biobased-aprons>

Detailed report:

Climate Friendly Health Care (CLIRE) Final Report (2015), Region Skåne

http://ec.europa.eu/environment/life/project/Projects/index.cfm?fuseaction=home.showFile&rep=file&fil=LIFE09_ENV_SE_000_347_FTR.pdf

Case Study 2 – Greve Biogas “Magic Factory”

Typology: Networking, Collaboration, Joint Planning

Regional background

Figure 4. The "Magic Factory" in Greve, Norway

Greve Biogas “Magic Factory” is situated in the region of Oslofjord, in Norway. Greve Biogas is owned by the municipalities of Bamble, Færder, Holmestrand, Horten, Larvik, Porsgrunn, Sandefjord, Siljan, Skien and Tønsberg. Greve Biogas' overall purpose is to contribute to green value creation, with the focus of the good practice being on Vestfold, the Drammen and Greenland regions.

This was done through the development of a value chain which is based on biogas produced from livestock manure, organic waste, and sludge, and through production of

food which was climate-friendly, green CO₂ and biofertilizer (Greve Biogas AS, 2022). The type of deployment setting is coastal, and the type of good practice is in the field of Networking, Collaboration and Joint Planning.

Grenland Vestfold Biogas AS (Greve Biogas) was founded in 2013. It was decided in 2018 to reorganize the company by splitting it into two new companies. One company for handling the shareholders' sludge and food waste (Grenland Vestfold Bestiller AS), and a company that was linked to the operation of the biogas plant, now known as Greve Biogas AS from 2019 (Greve Biogas AS, 2022).

The Magic Factory was established near the E18, the main road transportation in the Vestfold area. Through this location, waste trucks from the region can deliver food waste to be used to produce biogas. The factory was set up as an industrial symbiosis model between the biogas facility and nearby greenhouses. The facility has also farmlands all around, which makes easier to transport bio-fertilizer and livestock manure.

In Norway, municipalities are obliged to the transition to green energy, as well as the contribution of the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, due to legislation, voted in 2009, from the government of the country, which also promotes the production of biogas in Norway. Biogas production based on sewage sludge, manure, and other types of waste hold a vast potential to decrease greenhouse gas emissions.

A large part of the reduction would be achieved through biogas substituting fossil energy, and that could come from the reduction of emissions from sectors such as heating of buildings or transportation (Hegg, 2015).

Context for deployment of good practice

The Magic Factory is a biogas plant cooperatively owned and managed by two multi-municipality partnerships, Greve Biogas and Vesar refuse collection. It produces biogas from household food waste and agricultural manure, and biofertilizers from digestate which is sold to local farmers. The food waste comes from households in Eastern Norway and the manure comes from farms in the region. Approximately 110,000 tons of food waste and manure are recycled per annum, producing biogas equivalent to 6.8 million litres of diesel fuel. There is an on-site Educational Centre for Sustainability for sharing knowledge with school students.

The Magic Factory's goal was to become an international pioneer for green carbon capture. Carbon capture takes place through renewable and green CO₂ from the factory being used inside industrially adapted greenhouses for food production, together with bio-fertilizer from the factory.

Emissions from transportation is a huge contributor to the overall greenhouse gas emissions of Norway. The low-level treatment of livestock manure was also an issue that needed to be tackled. The Norwegian government has thus developed strategies for curbing this emission, which includes a goal of utilizing 30% of livestock manure to produce biogas and also to find alternative sources other than fossil fuel in transportation (Meld. St. 21 2011–2012).

The entities that were involved in the development of the good practice were aiming to achieve key environmental impacts from the initiative including fossil fuel displacement with biogas in public transport, municipal and greenhouse waste collection, displacement of synthetic fertilizers with biofertilizers and efficient municipal waste management. At a societal level, benefits included an efficient municipal waste management system, public transport being fuelled by locally produced biogas, extra income for farmers and a local biofertilizer supply, and a sustainable education venue and programme focused on children and teenagers. At an economic level, with local production of biogas for public vehicles reduces the require for fossil-based energy while generating income for farmers for their manure. The initiative ensures the continued collaboration with agricultural stakeholders for developing storage facilities and spreader technology for biofertilizers, and the greenhouse sector for the establishment of industrial Bio-CCP (Carbon Capture Products) greenhouses.

Implementation of the good practice

The municipal governments had a vision of achieving a more sustainable biogas-fuelled infrastructure, e.g., public transport. They established a partnership to produce biogas from manure and household food waste to fuel public buses and waste collection vehicles, and bio-digestate to replace chemical fertilizers.

The Magic Factory is a biogas plant cooperatively owned and managed by two multi-municipality partnerships, Greve Biogas and Vesar refuse collection. It produces biogas from household food waste and agricultural manure, biofertilizers from digestate, and has an on-site Educational Centre for Sustainability and its goal was to become an international pioneer for green carbon capture. The biogas is used as environmentally friendly fuel for vehicles such as public buses and trucks.

The Magic Factory uses livestock manure and food waste as a resource to produce bio-fertilizers, biogas, and climate neutral vegetables. The process of industrial symbiosis allowed the sharing of side streams and resources to be distributed. The local farmers, who started to give manure got bio-fertilizer in return, thus enabling a circular economy scheme. Close to the biogas factory, growth houses were built, that utilize the "waste" to grow climate neutral tomatoes, making further steps to reduce waste. The stakeholders who benefitted from the good practice include 1.2 million households and 12 municipalities.

Figure 5. Circular systems at the Magic Factory, Greve

Involvement of regional government or public bodies in the development of the practice

The biogas project in Vestfold started as a collaboration between 12 municipalities in the area (Lind, 2013). In June 2011, an agreement was signed between the municipalities of Grenland and Vesar for the delivery of sludge and food waste to the biogas plant. Greve Biogas AS with support from the Tønsberg municipality built the "Magic Factory" plant. Tønsberg municipality owns and finances the project while Greve Biogas AS rents the plant on a long-term contract. Public tender 46 offered the plant's operation to the company (Hegg, 2015).

The treatment of the local food waste ensured that counties, municipalities, and businesses in the region could reach their climate targets. "The Magic Factory" is the facility in the Nordic countries, with the highest net reduction in greenhouse gas emissions per ton food waste. For this reason, the plant received financial support from Enova, which is owned by the Ministry of Climate and Environment (Hegg, 2015). The project is supported by local governments who purchase the biogas to fuel their waste collection trucks and public transport services.

Results of good practice

The factory contributes to green growth, by significantly reducing climate emissions, improving waste management and also creating additional value in the region. The Magic Factory wants to increase and expand its production capacity in line with the increasing need for green growth in the region and the rest of the country.

Vesar's goal was for 70% recovery of material before the year 2020. The Magic Factory has played a major role in the work made towards achieving this goal, both in relation to working with young people and children, but also in terms of highlighting that waste sorted at source can be transformed into something worthwhile. A knowledge and visitor centre that is associated with The Magic Factory provides young people and children with a valuable understanding and knowledge of the subject areas linked to source sorting of waste, recycling, and renewable energy.

The Magic Factory managed to have a significant influence on business development in the region of Oslofjord. First, in the field of agriculture in connection with investments in spreader technology for bio-fertilizer and storage facilities, and has also collaborated with the greenhouse sector, where the capture and use of biofertilizers and green CO₂ in greenhouses boosts local food production.

Figure 6. The Magic Factory, Greve

Replication of good practice

The site has become a national pilot plant and can be replicated in other contexts where biogas-powered vehicles are planned or prevalent. For the regional deployment considerations, where biogas-fuelled vehicles are rare and manure availability is low, this practice may have less relevance.

Future plans

In addition to the existing facilities, a Magic Pilot Greenhouse is under construction for testing, with further plans for rolling out industrial greenhouses for local food production.

Lessons Learned

- The Magic Factory was able to supply both local waste collection trucks and public transport, greatly reducing the overall emissions. Moreover, they were able to reach the regional goal of 30% biogas resources formation from all livestock manure.
- The industry and farmland symbiosis allowed for biogas to become a biofertilizer.
- The excess CO₂ was used in green houses to produce tomatoes and create more green and sustainable growth methods.
- Biogas and biofertilizers can be used as a replacement for traditional fuel and agricultural artificial fertilizers.
- Treatments of the desired substrate can be included regardless of whether it was handled or processed (e.g., manure directly spread directly as a fertilizer or waste that was sent to other plants).

Further Information

Websites:

<https://www.greenvisits.no/product/the-magic-factory/>

<https://denmagiskefabrikken.no/>

Case Study 3 – BIOVOICES

Typology: Information & Advisory

Regional background

The next good practice was deployed in Italy, using short educational videos about bioeconomy, involving famous people, on social media to promote bioeconomy development and sustainable consumption and lifestyles. For the regional deployment considerations, there were no major barriers, just identifying the proper public profiles and testimonials to disseminate the specific initiative.

Context for deployment of good practice

Bioeconomy, despite its many applications, has not yet entered the public consciousness as an exciting solution to address societal challenges. Raising overall awareness and understanding of the societal, economic, and environmental impacts of bio-based products and processes and the bioeconomy at large is of utmost importance for the future development of a smart, sustainable and inclusive bioeconomy and to educate society on more sustainable consumption and lifestyle patterns.

BIOVOICES (<https://www.biovoices.eu/>) project experimented successfully with the engagement of famous people to multiply the educational effect, by leveraging existing trusted relations they have with their followers. These people were the centre of a communication campaign launched through social media (Albertini, *et al.* 2022). The deployment settings were at multiple level (as the video shorts were about different topics on the bioeconomy).

Implementation of the good practice

Figure 7. Still frame from "Lo Sai che?" video short

The usage of video shorts in social media through the project BIOVOICES was an educational initiative and was first implemented in 2021. The project involved two famous Italian TV presenters, already known as sensitive to environmental issues: Syusy Blady and her daughter Zoe. Their social media channels reach 750,000 followers, and they are well-known as unconventional travellers in primary television formats. The idea was to show and explain, in a very simple and inspirational way,

the circular bioeconomy in everyday life. In 10 video shorts called “*Lo sai che?*” (Do you know that?), Syusy and Zoe, engage in a funny competition to show to each other, in a playful banter, who knows more about bioeconomy in an inter-generational mother and daughter rapid word exchange.

Before getting in contact with the projects, they had never heard about bioeconomy. Therefore, the first step was to inspire them in presenting several stories on how waste can become a resource (e.g., apple skin can become leather, leftovers from winemaking can become cosmetics, etc.), to raise their enthusiasm and interest. Once inspired, the next step was to empower them with solid knowledge as well as bio-based products and curiosities, and create a series of stories, each one addressing an application field of the bioeconomy.

Finally, after the video shooting and editing, a contents check was performed, to prevent misleading communication. In this phase, insights like prices of bio-based products, communication messages and data were provided in a nice graphical format. The videos were distributed through social media channels as a weekly appointment with the bioeconomy, targeting the Italian public (including mature audiences, as planned) (Albertini, *et al.* 2022).

This target audience was not easy to involve as they were very resistant to behavioural and attitudinal change. Their main social media is YouTube or Facebook, but they also used newspaper and television as a source of information.

Results of good practice

From April 2021, BIOVOICES experimented this format in Italy using their channels on social media and the broadcasting on Rete 4 TV station to see the impact of the activity. With this activity, Syusy Blady and Patrizio Roversi managed to attract on their various social media channels, 519,755 followers (Facebook), 123,731 (Instagram), 75,307 (Twitter), 21,070 (YouTube) with a total of 739,683 followers in all social media (Cohen, *et al.* 2021).

The use of different channels on social media represented a good means of outreach to the engaged public and allowed BIOVOICES to reach out and to disseminate the projects’ results more efficiently. The social media activities also helped the project in promoting the project’s results and effort thanks to their efficacy in reaching the younger audiences. Instagram, turned out to be a very important tool in order to reach and inform existing communities, reach influencers, bio-based industries and brands, and monitor megatrends. The BIOVOICES Instagram page had a very positive impact on increasing the knowledge and acceptance of Bio-Based Products and raising awareness in particular among young generations. From the social media insights, it appears also that women rather than men are at a greater amount, committed and sensitized to the issues of sustainability and bioeconomy.

Figure 8. Still frames from “*Lo Sai che?*” video short

BIOVOICES tried to explore what format could be more effective in order to reach the specific target group and in order to identify possible formats that were suitable. From these internal reflections and discussions, the following points emerged:

- The best way to reach the target audience was through the involvement of testimonials (famous people) that they already follow and trust, e.g., from important people that were already promoting values that were linked to the bioeconomy (such as social innovation, environment protection, circularity, shared economy, frugal economy, etc.). The important people should already have a large community of followers in social media, television, and media (press), to ensure significant impact of the activity.
- The target group should be convinced of the value of the bio-based products, to be credible and the testimonial should share and tell their “real experiences” about bio-based products which would also mean that they had to use them in order to convey contents about the bioeconomy and its impacts on the economy, environment and society.
- The contents should be conveyed as part of the testimonials’ daily life, to ensure wide coverage in most of the application fields (e.g., personal care, cleaning, cosmetics, food, building and insulation, accessories, toys, clothing, textiles, etc.) and use simple and transparent language. The contents should be based on reliable knowledge.
- The testimonial should communicate the risks and make aware to the public unsustainable behaviours. The testimonials should provide additional information, like the impacts on the environment, the price, the impacts, the society (e.g., jobs creations, health) and the economy. They should also stimulate the curiosity of the target audience (Cohen, et.al. 2021).

Replication of good practice

As previously mentioned, the format concept was mainly based on the testimonials selected. The communication style, characters, and their audience are very rooted in the targeted country and, therefore a simple translation of the video shorts would not be the most effective solution for the

Slow Tour Padano

After the great success, the production company decided to use the knowledge acquired to create new contents for a new TV show “Slow Tour Padano”, where a curious tourist, riding an electric motorcycle, explores the north of Italy, meeting examples of sustainable living, producing, and consuming (Albertini, *et al.* 2022).

Figure 9. Slow Tour Padano

replication to other countries. Nevertheless, the format could be replicated, if the best candidate who will deliver the testimonial could be identified for the local situation of a specific country.

Lessons Learned

- Take a strategy on social media and plan right from the beginning.
- Define your target audience, messages, goals, and channels.
- Monitor your social media channels very often, to measure the impact, you're having.
- Choose the social media accounts and platforms which are the most relevant to your project and be very consistent across all your channels of communication.
- Design content dedicated and tailored to the language and the interests of the stakeholders in the different channels.
- Use storytelling to raise the attention and interest of the public for bio-based and bioeconomy products.
- Make the activities on social media more responsive to the news and trends of society.
- Bio-based and bioeconomy products are not known yet at a big scale and so, it is useful to connect them to words and concepts like sustainability, health benefits, circular economy waste reduction, etc.

Further Information

BIOVOICES video playlist:

https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLAOYbpieiFAfIOH1RCHpTZXL-oC-y_oLR

Case Study 4 – Biovale Innovation Biocamp

Typology: Information & Advisory

Regional background

BioVale Innovation Biocamp, is an initiative of the BioVale Circular Bioeconomy cluster situated within the Yorkshire and Humber region in the northeast of the England, United Kingdom. The region boasts a population of 5,284,000 with the major urban centres of Leeds (516,200), Sheffield (556,000) and York (156,000) where the BioVale cluster is located. Large parts of the region, Yorkshire have been synonymous with the now largely redundant coal mining industry. The BioVale cluster's mission is to stimulate economic growth with a focus on renewable raw materials and low-carbon agriculture.

Context for deployment of good practice

Within the remit of the cluster are several focus areas that lead to the overall development of the circular bioeconomy. Value from agri-food waste is focused on innovative food and drink researchers and businesses across the region who are finding new ways to extract value from food and farming waste. The region is the largest food producer in the United Kingdom and the further valorisation of this waste is seen as a key economic driver. Another area of focus is high-value chemicals from plants and microbes and there is a growing sector within the region that aims to exploit manufacturers from the personal care, food, drink, and pharmaceutical industries using more of these natural inputs. Developing innovations from anaerobic digestion and delivering a low carbon future for agriculture is another focus area along with driving agri-tech innovation to transform food production .

Due to experience in working with and fostering activity in those areas, BioVale were aware of several issues startups and SMEs faced when developing circular bioeconomy-based enterprises or practices within their businesses.

The cluster were aware of a great deal of research being carried out within the region (and further afield) particularly around the area of plants and microbes and high-value applications. It was identified that there was a significant drop off from the research being done in the lab to developing those concepts and ideas to practical commercial entities. It has been dubbed 'the valley of death'.

A training program was developed to support entrepreneurs "whose drive is to use locally produced bio-based feedstocks, rather than imported fossil resources, to produce materials, chemicals, energy". The Innovation Biocamp funded through the Interreg project Biobase4SME, focused on

start-ups and SME's overcoming technological and non-technological barriers to bring innovation to the market with 3 ½ years.

Implementation of the good practice

Figure 10. Participants of the Innovation Biocamp Pitching Contest 2018

Project co-ordinators initially met and designed the first BioVale Biocamp in 2017, holding what would become the first of 3 unique training programmes in the UK. The week-long peer-to-peer learning and networking residential program was specifically aimed at and developed for bio-based entrepreneurs with innovations for the circular biobased economy.

The camp was centred around peer-to-peer activities which included a series of lectures from experienced actors focusing on thematic area of business development such as value proposition and financing growth and risk management. These activities were then followed by group exercises led by

experienced facilitators to allow entrepreneurs to analyse their value proposition, develop a business model, identify, secure, and communicate with customers and key partner agencies, manage business operations, and develop their company's pitch. Key to the long-term goal setting of the programme was the opportunity for the participants to participate in one-to-one mentoring from business leaders with the week culminating in attendees pitching to a panel of specialist investors. These mentors provided post programme coaching to participants to help them carry on from the learning within the camp and set new actions and targets over the upcoming year to further develop their business. This ensured that participants would experience medium- and long-term benefits from their participation in Innovation BioCamp.

Results of good practice

Figure 11. Participants gathering for the week-long Innovation Biocamp

Within the intensive atmosphere of the residential setting many peer-to-peer networks naturally formed as a result and have provided long lasting and commercially useful working partnerships.

2017, the first year of the camp held in the UK, 17 participants took part from a variety of circular bioeconomy sectors, Biofuels (2), Bioplastics (1), Food and drink (1), Personal care (1), Biorefineries (2), Agritech (3), Materials (1), Biochemicals (6).

Participants were not just from the UK but also from Ireland, Belgium, and the Netherlands.

The 2018 BioCamp was also held in the UK, hosting 17 participants from an equally diverse set of circular bioeconomy sectors, Food and drink (1), Water treatment (2), Agritech (1), Materials (3), Biomedical (1), Construction (1), Energy (2), Biochemicals (6). This included participants from the UK, Ireland, France, Germany, and the Netherlands.

In 2019 the BioCamp was held in the Netherlands with a strong representation from Biochemicals (8) as well as Food and drink (1), Personal care (1), Biofuels (1), Construction (1), Materials (4). Participants were once again from across Europe including the UK, Netherlands, France, Belgium, Germany, and Switzerland.

Success highlights for entrepreneurs have included Holiform who were awarded £400K to build a pilot plant for a separation fermentation process, Oceanium securing £2 Million investment to scale up its proprietary seaweed biorefinery and Bio Bean securing £5 Million investment to industrialise the process for recycling waste coffee grounds into advanced biofuels and biochemicals.

INNOVATION BIOCAMP

“Really enjoyable event! Definitely learnt a lot. I think what was also really valuable was meeting other entrepreneurs and sharing our experiences and strategies, especially since we spent so much time together. This is a big plus of the event.” (Farrugia, 2022).

Figure 12. Participants of the Innovation Biocamp

Replication of good practice

The idea of an intensive residential training camp is completely replicable and the model has had further one- and two-day training and online events for the THYME project, N8 AgriFood and the High-Value Biorenewables network. There have also been requests to hold a shorter academically focused one for the education sector which is currently being designed. The model has served as inspiration for another incubator model demonstrated in Ireland, Hungary, and Spain through the AgriForValor project called Bio-Enterprise Academy

However, barriers do remain, and project coordinators have identified the amount of promotion of the camp and its benefits, and the time commitment that participants must give as key to its success.

Future plans

BioVale would like to do more innovation camps and have done shorter programmes.

Lessons Learned

There were many lessons learned over the three-year initial run of the camp. What worked well was being locked away for the week focused participants on the future over day-to-day concerns of their business. The program developed good long-lasting bonds and networking opportunities and participants actively engaged and sought feedback daily.

As they initially thought there would be IP concerns among companies, training was therefore initially centred around fantasy companies. However, during the course of the week people wanted to talk about their own companies and a sense of comradery grew even amongst potential competitors.

Further Information

<https://www.biovale.org/about/our-impact/biovale-biocamps-case-study/>

<https://holiform.com/>

<https://oceanium.world/>

<https://www.bio-bean.com/>

Case Study 5 – Italian Ban on Plastic Bags

Typology: Regulatory

Regional background

The good practice is situated in the nation of Italy and was implemented nationwide by the government of Italy. Its aim was to trigger investment in the bioeconomy and protect the environment, also in line with the guidelines of European Union. The goal was also to achieve multiple social benefits that had to do with consumption patterns and waste prevention with regards to the public.

The Italian law on plastic shopping bags came into force on 1st January 2011. The aim was to reduce the contamination of the environment which was caused by traditional plastic bags. The goal was to introduce a regulation with which, thick and long-life reusable carrier bags and single use biodegradable bags would be the environmentally friendly alternative that would be available for retailers and consumers.

The initiative was built on legislative measures that were introduced in Italy since late '90s, so as to address waste management in compliance also with the Landfill Directive and the Waste Framework Directive.

The land use required for 100 billion plastic bags consumed in a year in Europe is just 0,05% of the total arable land, if produced from bioplastic. The development of integrated local biorefineries in Italy showed that local crops can grow on contaminated and marginal land in combination with local by-products. This led to synergies established in the agricultural sector in the country as well as restarting production and revitalizing certain areas, while respecting local biodiversity and local ecosystems (Bastioli, 2013).

Italy has a strong bioplastic sector, with a market of significant size, and numerous private investments have been made in demonstrator and new plants, and the sector has provided economic growth to areas previously affected by the economic crisis of the previous decade.

For the regional deployment considerations, the deployment was taken in multiple settings as the initiative was nationwide and there were no major barriers, to transfer the good practice to other regions. However, consideration should be given to availability and types of biomass feedstocks which vary between regions and countries.

Context for deployment of good practice

Italy has a special position in Europe for the use of compostable bioplastics. The use of compostable bags, combined with its organic waste treatment sector and a law banning the use of conventional plastic shopping bags, are some of the factors that has enabled Italy to take a leading position in the recycling of food waste compared with the European average (47% compared with a European average of 16%).

The environmental goal was the reduction of carrier bags by 50% in retail in the following 5 years. There was also an aim for 50% of bags to be for separate collection of organic waste giving higher quality compost. Moreover, the goal was to increase in the use of biodegradable plastics (including marine biodegradable plastics), as well as an increase in the use of bio-based content in plastics with reduced emissions.

At a societal level, the goal was the creation of local supply chains, through the development of bioplastics based on an Italy Agri-supply chain, with an estimated creation of 3,000 direct jobs in 5 years. At an economic level, the goal was to invest approximatively 1 billion in the Italian bio-based biorefinery sector within the 5 years following implementation.

Implementation of the good practice

Figure 13. Promotion of biodegradable bags, in conjunction with Italian ban on plastic bags

Thin single use plastic bags are considered a case of over-packaging in the whole world. Most of them are just used once, which can lead to litter problems and this is also a waste of resources. Plastic bags are thin and airy and have the tendency to fly away into the environment. In the top 10 marine litter items, plastic bags are the top ranked in terms of pollution (also reported by UNEP report, “A Marine Litter: A Global Challenge”). They are very difficult biodegrade and have the tendency to accumulate in the marine environment if they are not disposed of properly.

Over time, carrier bags are fragmented by the waves and marine current erosion and this leads to the formation of fragments that are microscopic (e.g., microplastics). The toxic chemicals present in the sea, have the tendency to be assimilated by the microplastics that are found in the marine environments. Owing to this fact, the microscopic plastic fragments are swallowed by marine mammals and fish, due also to their similarity to plankton organisms. For these reasons, there is a paramount risk that toxic chemicals could enter in the food chain, carried by these plastic fragments in the marine environments.

The first step to prevent this enormous environmental problem, was to identify the source of littering. A vast number of studies had indicated that marine waste originates either from navigation or from land, carried by rivers. Thus, measures of prevention had to be applied not only to coastal areas but also to rivers and lakes.

Due to the huge amount of coastline (more than 8000km), Italy, which is in the centre of the Mediterranean Sea, was strongly affected by marine waste which was caused largely by carrier bags (Ganapini, 2013). Plastic bags contributed to the destruction of the marine environment, in a country which relies economically, at a profound level, on sea tourism.

Plastic bags were also a problem in the organic recycling of kitchen and garden waste (biowaste). Italy has a well-established organic recycling, thanks to clear policies on separate waste collection and compost quality, as Italy produces almost 4.2 million tons of high-quality compost per year, converted from municipal organic waste. Nevertheless, as plastic bags are not biodegradable, organic recycling of biowaste required plastic-free streams and thus could not be properly recycled, and contaminated biowaste resources.

Involvement of regional government or public bodies in the development of the practice

Globally, all the previously mentioned factors have produced a series of policies intended for the reduction of the consumption of single-use plastic bags. A plethora of retailers, committed to curb the environmental impact of their businesses, tried to move forward to more sustainable solutions. In Italy, specific legislations were introduced to move towards a shift in consumption habits and a profound number of new legislations were announced.

The strategy introduced in 2011 which was aiming at the elimination of thin, non-biodegradable single-use plastic carrier bags, attempted to conform to a harmonized European standard law on compostable packaging (EN 13432) (Ganapini, 2013).

Furthermore, with a view to maximize the interaction of coherent policies with a state-of-the-art approach, in September 2012, the Italian government started sponsoring the creation of a Public Private Green Chemistry Cluster.

Results of good practice

Figure 14. Information notice about biodegradable bags in an Italian supermarket

The Italian law on plastic shopping bags came into force in the beginning of 2011. No one-to-one replacement of conventional plastic shopping bags with bioplastic bags occurred after law came into force, but on the contrary, plastic shopping bag consumption fell from almost 180 tons in 2010 to 74,5 tons in 2020. The effect of the law was therefore very positive, because the consumption of plastic shopping bags fell by 60% over 10 years.

The good practice limited the number of single use plastic bags that were circulating and reduced the littering risk and its environmental consequences. It also improved the quality of organic recycling and the growth conditions for the market of bio-based products, acting also as a boost for new bioeconomy investments. This was also recognized recently by the European Commission, adopting a dedicated strategy that outlined Europe's need to move forward to a post-petroleum society, to respond to fundamental societal challenges

that the globe is set to face in the following years (Ganapini, 2013).

There were improvements in recycling and biowaste collection. After first use, biodegradable compostable plastic bags could be reused as waste bags and were suitable for the collection of residual waste (non-separated collected waste), and for kitchen waste (biowaste). This was well communicated to consumers and became an education vehicle. This led to an improvement in the quantity and quality of recycling and collection of biowaste.

Less non-biodegradable plastic bags were contaminating compost. With the elimination of non-biodegradable plastic bags, the risk of using them to improperly collect biowaste was reduced and thus improved the quality of organic recycling.

High quality, plastic-free compost maintains the soil fertility and thus forms a circular life cycle of bioplastics (from LCA (Life Cycle Assessment) viewpoint, this meant reductions of up to 30% in greenhouse gas emissions, which were linked mainly to saving the required energy to dispose and recover the plastic scraps) (Bastioli, 2013).

The Italian law on plastic bags turned out to be an example of positive actions supporting bioeconomies. The market pull that was created for compostable and biodegradable plastic bags resulted in an opportunity for fostering innovation and development of the bioeconomy. Replacement rates of traditional plastic bags with biodegradable ones was 8% in 2010 and 28% in 2011 (Ganapini, 2013). The European Union capacity for polymers that were biodegradable reached more than 200,000 tons. Three privately financed plants for biodegradable monomers, were under construction, while the ENI petrochemical site, located in Sardinia (Porto Torres) was redeveloped into a biorefinery for bioplastics production, as well as bio lubricants and bio fillers with the development of local crops grown on contaminated and marginal land (Bastioli, 2013).

The Italian public was encouraged by the new law to adopt behaviours and views that are more attentive to waste management and the environment. Most Italians (94%) believed that this law is an important milestone for the environment, and 88% recognized that compostable biodegradable plastics were an important innovation with the capability of triggering multiple positive effects, such as green jobs and new green attitudes (Bastioli, 2013).

Compostable bags can be biodegradable in the natural environment. The good practice reduced the risk of littering, as consumers prefer durable bags. Even if the compostable bags reach the sea anyway, they can be effectively susceptible to biodegradation. Non-biodegradable plastic bags can still be in circulation in Italy, provided that they are thick enough to make them reusable. This law has not only helped change the polymer that is normally used to produce these bags (polyethylene PE) to biodegradable polymers but has also led to a decrease in the overall consumption of these bags.

Replication of good practice

This approach demonstrates good potential for replication in other regions, e.g., as pursued by France.

French Ban on Plastic Bags

In 2013, the country of France outlined the willingness and intention of following the Italian model and to boost compostable and biodegradable bags, foreseeing the potential that this measure could have in creating local value chains that would be dedicated to the production of bioplastics (Ganapini, 2013).

Lessons Learned

- Consumers were ready to change their habits rapidly, to achieve behaviours which were more sustainable, and thus promoting packaging prevention. Studies showed that use of single-use plastic bags dropped as far as 50%, after the good practice was enforced, providing a positive impact to waste management.
- There were less single use plastic bags in circulation, there was a lower amount of littering, helping litter prevention. Less pollution is thus produced, less waste needs to be recovered and less resources are consumed.

- Only compostable, biodegradable plastic bags could still be sold in Italian retail shops as single use bags, together with bags that were reusable.

Further Information

Previous case study:

https://issuu.com/edizioniambiente/docs/bioplastics_case_study_of_bioeconomy_in_italy

Case Study 6 – Grand Est Bioeconomy

Typology: Networking, Collaboration, Joint Planning

Regional background

Grand Est, located in northeast of France is an amalgamation of the Alsace, Champagne-Ardenne, and Lorraine regions resulting from territorial reform initiated by the French Government in 2014. The diverse region holds a population of 5,562,651 with the major population centre at Strasbourg (290,500) and Reims (180,318) with 80% of the region being directed towards agriculture and forestry, while also being the second largest industrial region in France.

Context for deployment of good practice

The region has an been ambitious in developing the regional bioeconomy with many initiatives and actions carried out due strong collaboration between research and academia, bio-based industries, agro-industries, cooperatives, and businesses. A comprehensive regional bioeconomy strategy has been in place since 2019 with the overarching goal of reconciling the objectives of the region's economic development with its ecological and agricultural ambitions. The five priorities for the strategy include local energy strategies, regional biorefineries, sustainable agriculture, bio-based materials in construction and renovation, and sustainable food production.

Central to this strategy and Grand Est Bioeconomy ecosystem is the Pomacle-Bazancourt biorefinery complex. Located outside of Reims, it has evolved from a bankrupt distillery purchased by a farmers cooperative in 1948 to be used as a sugar refinery. The site began to expand to develop into an ago-industrial complex in the early 1990s developing research facilities with the local grain cooperative. The initial was to strengthen competitiveness and open up new markets for the cooperatives, such as those offered by the biofuels sector, and related strategies, targets and markets. This has led to expansion towards the development of a research centre serving not only those industries but the larger bioeconomy.

Implementation of the good practice

The Pomacle-Bazancourt biorefinery ecosystem brings together farmers, academic researchers, industry, and experts with the common aim of capitalising on the abundance of feedstocks within the region. The 10,000 cooperative farmers are crucial to the facility and ecosystem and supply the facility with predominantly sugar beet and wheat. The site ethos is based on the sharing of resources. All the companies on site are independent of each other but do become more efficient through the shared use of energy, materials and by-products, steam, water, resources, and logistics.

Sharing the site are an amalgamation of ago-food and bio-based industries as well as research organisations. The innovation hub incorporates the research centre ARD, and two engineering schools Ecole Centrale Paris, Agro Paris Tech, and NEOMA Business School. The research facilities support new value chain development from pilot to demonstration level.

Figure 15. Biorefinery ecosystem

Some of the innovations on site include, Cristanol producing bioethanol from wheat and sugar beet co-products, the Air Liquide workshop for the recovery and processing of fermentation-issued CO₂, the pilot of the Futurol Project a world class initiative for developing bioethanol 2G (now owned by ARD), Soliance (molecules for cosmetic products), the BioDemonstration plant (also owned by ARD), for the scale up of bioprocesses up to TRL 9, and Wheatoleo (a subsidiary of ARD) producing surfactants. ADM Chamtor process wheat into starch-based products. Other companies on the site manufacture bio-based inputs for the detergent industry, cosmetics and other products. In 2018 Givaudan, the world’s largest flavours and fragrances company, joined the ecosystem. The site operates 24/7 converting 4 million tons of different types of biomass (mainly sugar beet and wheat, but also alfalfa and more recently woody materials) on a site of more than 260 hectares.

Additionally, there are several joint ventures (JVs) of high interest in the bio-based production world:

- Dupont Tate and Lyle for the production of 1-3 propanediol in the United States, further processed in polymer by Dupont on the same site
- Corbion-Total in Thailand to produce polylactic acid (PLA) based on lactic acid produced by Corbion’s plant on site
- BASF-Avantium for the production of Polyethylene furanoate (PEF) at a demonstration scale and further at industrial
- Global Bioenergies and Cristal Union for elaboration of business plan and a process optimisation stage prior to the construction of an isobutene production plant.

Results of good practice

The cooperation of the actors involved within the Pomacle-Bazancourt ecosystem have made the site a leading innovation hub within the European bioeconomy. Crucial also is the positive interactions with the local population. The complex has resulted in the creation of 1,200 direct jobs and 1,000 indirect jobs in the region. Hiring for graduate level roles has always been easy due to their high value, however process driven jobs have been difficult to fill. The close relationship with the two academic institutions located on site continues to drive

Figure 16. Overview of the Biorefinery and Industrial Symbiosis

bioeconomy research. The sites revenue reached approximately €800 million in 2018 from direct activities on site in a market that covers the agricultural, cosmetic, chemical and bioenergy sectors. The practice is a model of what can be achieved when primary sectors and cooperatives collaborate with industries, and research organisations, with support from regional government in a model of partnership. The primary producer organisation have strengthened their competitiveness and can now supply into a diversity of markets.

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Replication of good practice

Within the Grand Est region there is already replication although at smaller scale at other sites, however under the new joint bioeconomy and agricultural strategy currently being developed within the region, this is expected to be expanded upon. The model adopted has the potential to be adopted by other regions, and where required, adopted to local contexts and feedstocks. However, buy-in of local stakeholders is a crucial success factor, particularly from the agricultural community, in addition to local government and private industry.

Future plans

The Grand Est region strives to be a European leader within bioeconomy, and the complex is continuing its own plans to collaborate with relevant stakeholders to innovate in the management and use of bio-based resources using circular economy principles. This development of synergies is on-going in the sense that processes are constantly being improved, the use of by-products is being developed and increasing savings in resources are always on the agenda. The desire to consider the plant as a whole, to minimize its harmful aspects and environmental footprint, to return to farmers the organic elements they need, is a daily concern of all the biorefinery actors.

Lessons Learned

The importance of local government in support the vision of the biorefinery complex leaders have been a major asset in its development. The site has been supported over the years by the local authorities through their various iterations, more recently in the bioeconomy strategy for the region.

The collective interest shared by all companies on site and the willingness to build towards a collective 'bioeconomy' vision has been a key to success.

ARD selected the following as the main contributions that the public sector can make to improve building their industrial ecosystem. The overarching role should be to facilitate the development of the bioeconomy, through various actions:

- Generate real positive communication to the population about what the bioeconomy is, including the recognition of the biomass producer roles and their positive impact on environment and job creation.
- Consider that this is a transition period, and that financial risk sharing tools through public-private partnerships have to be emphasised.
- Encourage the formation of specialised staff to these new businesses, including technical, and commercial entities.

Further Information

Website:

<https://rubizmo.eu/attachment/render/c4ee5fa9-7dcc-4ea3-b880-6061d44fd7ef>

Philp, J. and Winickoff, D., 2019. Innovation ecosystems in the bioeconomy.

Case Study 7 – Baden-Württemberg Bioeconomy Congress

Typology: Information & Advisory

Regional background

Figure 17. Bioeconomy Research Logo

Baden-Württemberg is the third largest state in Germany, both in terms of area (35,000 km²) and population (around 11 million). It is in southwestern Germany and adjacent to three German states. In Europe, it is centrally located and shares its borders with three countries.

Stuttgart is the state capital and the largest city, with a population of around 630,000 in 2020. In addition to the urban centres,

Baden-Württemberg has a strong rural area with diverse agriculture, forestry, and tourism. The landscape and nature are diverse with large contiguous forest areas such as the Black and the Swabian Forests, or the Odenwald. Around 40% of Baden-Württemberg's surface area is covered with forest. Regarding water bodies, the lake Constance (total area: 572 km²) plays an important role as a drinking water source and recreational use in the region. The main rivers that flow through Baden-Württemberg are the Rhine (437 km), Neckar (367 km) and Danube (251 km).

The most developed value chains related to the bioeconomy are those related to forestry and agricultural sectors. For both sectors the use of biomass and valorisation of fibre-rich by-products for multiple purposes plays a major role e.g., biopolymers (e.g., packaging, automotive, textile and paper industry), bio-based building blocks for phyto pharma (e.g., natural cosmetics) and biomass for energy or biofuels as final stage of the cascade use. The most relevant biomass feedstocks of Baden Württemberg are wood, lignin, lignocellulose, bio-waste and agricultural by-products (e.g., from harvest or slurries) and insects. Biogas plants using agricultural residue streams, as well as wastewater treatment for nutrient recovery are also relevant in the region.

Baden-Württemberg was quoted in a European Commission study in 2017 as one of the six top ranking European regions on the bioeconomy maturity index. In 2019 a “Sustainable Bioeconomy Strategy” was launched by the Government of Baden-Württemberg, which was a milestone for the relevance of bioeconomy in the policy agenda. The basic objectives of the bioeconomy strategy are the development of biological concepts for the exploitation of renewable or recyclable raw materials, and the development of Baden-Württemberg as a model region for sustainable and circular economy, as well as, strengthening the role of the rural areas. Other relevant aspects considered are e.g., impacts on climate change, protection of biodiversity and the promotion of bio-based innovations. The scope of the strategy is wide, covering rural, urban, and industrial areas.

Context for deployment of good practice

The International Bioeconomy Congress is being implemented as a measure within the Baden-Württemberg bioeconomy strategy under the action area “Networking among areas, actors and clusters” (Measure 29 in the Strategy).

The objective of the action area is to support the development and dissemination of a sustainable circular bioeconomy by bringing together material flows and stakeholders in rural, industrial, and urban areas. Its organisation is embedded within the action area “Networking among areas, actors and clusters”. Additionally, an objective of the congress is to promote international exchange and networking.

Implementation of the good practice

Figure 18. Participants of the Second Bioeconomy Congress

The international “Bioeconomy Congress Baden-Württemberg” was first established as part of the Baden-Württemberg Bioeconomy research programme initiated by the Ministry of Science, Research, and the Arts. It was first organised in 2014. It currently continues with the aim to promote networking and cooperation among several actors, and knowledge exchange between research, business, policymakers, regarding local and regional activities. The societal engagement is a key aspect of the initiative.

During the congress important topics regarding bioeconomy are addressed by information sessions, discussion panels, workshops, excursions, and seminars including real-life practices. The topics includes among others primary production, industry, sustainability, environmental and climate protection, and waste management.

The congress takes place every two-years. In 2022 the fourth edition took place focusing on the contributions of the bioeconomy to the European Green Deal.

Involvement of regional government or public bodies in the development of the practice

The Baden-Württemberg Bioeconomy Strategy including their measures such as the Bioeconomy Congress are implemented under the leadership of two ministries in Baden-Württemberg: The Ministry of the Environment, Climate Protection and the Energy Sector and the Ministry of Food, Rural Affairs and Consumer Protection. In former years, the Congress was initiated and led by the Ministry of Science, Research, and the Arts.

Results of good practice

The first congress addressed the science community. Nowadays the congress is focused on examples of implementation of the strategy: from rural and urban areas, best practices, pilot plants, start-ups, etc. The last congress in 2022 was attended by more than 300 participants.

Replication of good practice

The practice can be replicated by other regions to bring together different types of stakeholders. It could also be implemented at several levels such as districts, municipalities, etc. For example, a similar case is the International Bioeconomy Conference organised annually in the federal State of Saxony-Anhalt, that will celebrate its 11th edition in 2023. If the regions that wish to replicate the practices, has already a regional bioeconomy strategy in place, that can increase the impact of the event. No barriers are foreseen if adequate funding for the organisation and promotion of the event is available.

Awareness Raising and Networking

“I was very impressed by the Bioeconomy Congress in September 2022. It was very good in terms of content and well attended. The combination of awareness-raising about the environmental challenges and where and why there is a shortage of raw materials, together with a big platform of best practices and network meetings has been very successful”. Mr. Thomas Karle, Member of the Sustainable Bioeconomy Council Baden-Württemberg from 4th Bioeconomy Congress

Future plans

The next congress will take place in 2024, since it is a biannual event.

Lessons Learned

The Bioeconomy Congress Baden-Württemberg has been successful in increasing the awareness of bioeconomy best-practices in the region, raising trust of several stakeholders, and engaging them through the biannual congress as well as social engagement.

Some barriers to overcome are financial constraints for the implementation especially if there is no bioeconomy strategy or regulation in the region to prioritize these activities. Additionally, the early engagement of all actors in the value chain for a wider deployment of the bioeconomy at the regional level can be difficult. The organisation of the congress, including plenary sessions, tailored workshops, and networking possibilities, can help to lighten this situation.

Further Information

- Information of the 4th congress in 2022: [Bioeconomycongress - Bioökonomie Baden-Württemberg \(baden-wuerttemberg.de\)](https://www.baden-wuerttemberg.de/en/service/bioeconomycongress-2022)
- Website Bioeconomy Baden-Württemberg: [Home - Bioökonomie Baden-Württemberg \(baden-wuerttemberg.de\)](https://www.baden-wuerttemberg.de/en/service/bioeconomy)

Case Study 8 - National Procurement Database for Biobased Products

Typology: Voluntary Instruments

Regional background

The provinces of Zeeland, Overijssel, North Brabant and North Holland took on the initiative to set up a national Procurement Database for Biobased Products in the Netherlands.

Zeeland located in the southwest of the country is predominantly coastal and boasts scenic islands and peninsulas and borders Belgium to the south. Bordering it is North Brabant and industry is predominantly agricultural and manufacturing. Overijssel is in the eastern part of the Netherlands and borders Germany to the west and is a highly industrialised province, whilst North Holland located northwest of the Dutch capital Amsterdam.

Context for deployment of good practice

As in many European regions, government in these regions is a major purchaser of different products. A top-down initiative from central government has identified sustainable procurement as a key driver for increasing sustainability in national, provincial, and municipal government departments. However, companies and governments in the region have often faced significant issues identifying and sourcing which biobased products are on the market and understanding the benefit of using these products.

Figure 20. Database logo

As a result, the provinces of Zeeland, Overijssel, North Brabant and North Holland have developed the National Procurement Database for Biobased Products to address this issue. Implementation of this initiative on behalf of the four provinces is managed by the Circular Biobased Delta Foundation. A triple helix network within the region that organises and facilitates cooperation between

the business community, provinces, water boards, municipalities and knowledge and educational institutions. The Centre of Expertise Biobased Economy is the responsible knowledge partner. Key to producers' interactions with the database is Performis BV and is media partner for the construction, design, and continuity of the database.

Approximately 500 companies have been contacted to add their bio-based products. The database is accessible to everyone after going live, including purchasers from governments but also companies and organizations, and also for the general public. The database and products are broken

down by sector including packaging, food and catering and healthcare. The new database answers many questions from buyers. When is a product biobased? What is it made of then? What offer is there in the specific purchasing categories? How much more sustainable are these products than their fossil alternatives? How can I compare different products and materials on sustainability characteristics?

Implementation of the good practice

Central to future success of the procurement database is that it remains populated by interested biobased product providers along with interested clients. An editorial board is accountable for

determining the product information that must be entered by each supplier wishing to use the database, and monitoring the product information. The editorial board drafts important criteria to help describe the biobased products and make them comparable across a range of characteristics, such as materials used and production method, end of life stage and whole life cycle as outlined in tables 5,6 and 7 below.

Figure 21. Category Screenshot

Table 5. Editorial Board Criteria - Materials used and Production Method

Product Features	Definition	Choice form	Obligated
<u>Bio-based content</u>	The biobased content of the product, expressed as a mass percentage of the entire product according to the standard <u>NEN EN 16785-1:2016</u> .	percentage	Yes
<u>Biobased carbon content</u>	The biobased carbon content of the product, expressed as a mass percentage of the carbon in the product according to the <u>NEN EN 16640-2017 standard</u> .	percentage	No
<u>Biobased raw material/material</u>	Biobased raw materials/materials used. So, from biomass.	The most important raw materials and/or materials (maximum 10)	Yes
<u>Origin of biobased raw material/material</u>	Country(s) where the biobased raw materials/materials come from.	Country(s) of origin (maximum 10)	Yes
<u>Share of recycled material</u>	The mass percentage of recycled material in the product. Recycled material comes from a discarded product.	percentage	Yes

Product Features	Definition	Choice form	Obligated
<u>Origin recycled material</u>	Which process or product originates from the recycled materials used in the production of the product.	The main process(es)/product(s). (maximum 10)	No
<u>Production location</u>	Country(ies) where the products or materials were produced.	Country(ies) of production (maximum 10)	Yes

Table 6. Editorial Board Criteria - End of Life Stage

Product Features	Definition	Choice form	Obligated
<u>Biodegradable parts</u>	Indicate whether a removable part of the product is biodegradable. If so, which part of the product is biodegradable.	Yes or no	No
<u>Biodegradable</u>	Conditions under which the entire product is biodegradable.	Choose one or more options: 1: Industrial compostable 2: Home compostable 3: Cold soil 4: Fresh water 5: Seawater	No

Table 7. Editorial Board Criteria - Whole Life Cycle

Product Features	Definition	Choice form	Obligated
<u>Additional environmental properties</u>	Additional properties of this product during the production, use and/or end-of-life phase, with regard to environmental effects (e.g. saving CO2 equivalents).	Statement required in case of statement	N

The editorial board is independent of the purchasing database and consists of experts from Dutch academic institutions and independent content experts per product category. Initially 500+ biobased suppliers were requested to add their products, new companies can also apply to be included and upload to the database. All information provided by manufacturers is regularly reviewed by the editorial board. The main purpose is to ensure accurate information is communicated to the

customers, but also that the information can be transparent and understood to help inform the customers choices between different products.

Results of good practice

Figure 22. Product Database screenshot

2022 saw the 500+ companies populate the database with a wide variety of biobased products across the following categories: Food & Catering, Cleaning & Hygiene, Healthcare, Nature & Public Space, Clothing & Textiles, Packaging, Office furnishings & Office Supplies, Construction & Infrastructure, and Vehicles & Mobility. Interest is strong and products are uploaded regularly. The tool is used by public bodies, industry, and the public to understand what bio-based alternative options are available in different product categories. These can

then be procured by the customer. It also allows them to understand the biobased content of these materials, and the sustainability benefit associated with the biobased materials. Public and corporate procurement officers can use the new database as a tool to meet sustainability targets in their tenders. Suppliers can enter their bio-based products into the new database free of charge.

Public and corporate procurement officers can use the new database as a tool to meet sustainability targets in their tenders. Suppliers can enter their bio-based products into the new database free of charge. In addition to the actual database, a digital environment will be set up where buyers can find background information about, for example, developments in biobased applications and the process of sustainable purchasing.

Replication of good practice

The good practice highlights the important need to stimulate the market for bio-based products, and a database such as this allows public bodies, as well as private actors and consumers the opportunity to easily access and compare bio-based alternatives, and for bio-based companies to exhibit their products. Since the practice has been implemented at regional level with support from national government, and with the participation of local industries, it seems that this can be replicated to other regions. Internationally, other similar schemes such as the USDA BioPreferred Programs has also delivered significant results for boosting the bioeconomy within the USA. Such a programme can be replicated, but requires the support of national and regional government, along with the buy-in of experts, industries and other actors to ensure its success.

Future plans

Future plans involve the continued expansion of the scope of the products and suppliers of the database and to monitor its uptake amongst national, provincial, and municipal governments, along with private sector actors and consumers.

Lessons Learned

The monitoring of the suppliers is crucial to the success of the project. Suppliers must align with the criteria as laid out by the editorial board and monitoring must be consistent and transparent to overcome any possibilities of greenwashing.

Further Information

Website: <https://biobasedinkopen.nl/>

Case Study 9 – Edible Landscapes Project

Typology: Voluntary Instruments

Regional background

Edible Landscapes, is a social enterprise based across the West of Ireland, predominantly in County Mayo an area situated on the Atlantic Ocean, known for its natural beauty and stark landscape. With a population of the approximately 137,000 people, largely rurally based, with the largest urban centre being the towns of Castlebar (12,000 people), Ballina (10,000) and Westport (6,000) where the Edible Landscapes project is based. Outside of these towns many rural primary are interested in teaching about issues surrounding sustainability and climate action, as well as addressing issues related to climate anxiety among children.

Context for deployment of good practice

“The Food Choices we all make every day affect climate change either positively or negatively”. Caithriona McCarthy, Program Director, Edible Landscape Project had founded the project in 2014 and previously had noticed that historically the urgency around climate action didn't exist. The Climate Action Bill was being implemented in the summer of 2021 and Caithriona had been getting reports of climate anxiety amongst primary aged children. The program was developed within a systems thinking framework to greater involve the participation of children in an enjoyable fashion. Coming from an educational background, the program developers knew how important to teach children the importance of climate change at an early age, including what they can do to help address it.

Edible Landscapes has devised a novel Education Program for Irish primary schools to encourage more school children to grow and consume food in an environmentally sustainable, climate smart way. This solution focused, Food Forest- Climate Education Program was developed by teachers, for teachers, and in November 2021 was launched in local primary schools in Co. Mayo.

The project was formalized in 2018, with a voluntary board in place. Edible Landscapes gathered pace in 2021 as Caithriona was completing a post graduate diploma and used that to further develop and test the program outside of the local region, introducing it to an urban 'audience'. This led to the development of a Food Forest working group of school teachers, climate activists, sustainability experts and community activists to further develop their research to a initially to a program directed towards primary school children, which further plans to develop this into second-level education once more funding is achieved.

Implementation of the good practice

Figure 23. School Programme Launch

The program is aimed at primary school children but designed to 'teach the teacher' who will then teach the children. A school co-ordinator is assigned the role of advising the teachers on the curriculum, A teacher or parent who has an understanding or keen interest in gardening or sustainability is assigned to take part and is the primary link with the co-ordinator.

Starting at a small scale, and largely based on word-of-mouth, uptake was developed through local contacts and to teachers and schools that the coordinators knew would have a strong interest in

incorporating. The initial response was very strong and the children 'loved it'. As a result, once a school ran the program, they kept it within their curriculum, and it became an integral part of the school's culture. With that success the problem of managing the program on a small budget became an issue. To overcome this, clusters of schools within the Sligo area are running the program. They have had interest from schools outside this area, however as it is a largely voluntary program it was not practical at the present. Plans are in place once future funding is obtained to spread the geographical reach.

Results of good practice

The program has received significant interest from other schools, both at a primary and secondary level as well as community groups due to word of mouth, so there is a strong interest in replicating the model. For school children it works well because they're learning with their friends - it's a joint effort. It can be difficult to encourage children to help in the garden, but when you add that sense of community and a bringing together of hearts and minds, the difference is incredible. It becomes fun for them rather than a chore, and when something's fun, they engage and learn better.

Murrisk National School

Murrisk National School is a three-teacher rural primary school at the foot of Croagh Patrick, Westport, Co. Mayo. They have been running the program since the autumn of 2021 and planted their food forest in November of that year.

Children's Quotes:

Figure 24. Participants Quotes

"It was so uplifting to see the children get so involved with the planting today - from digging to hammering, measuring, and even getting to know all the little creatures we came across, every child wanted to have a go at everything! Absolutely fantastic to see the joy on their faces at being outdoors and getting mucky. From a personal perspective I believe it's so important to pass these skills on - not just from a practical sense of being able to grow your own food, but because it's fun and rewarding. That, to me, is the key to developing our children's sense of connection to nature and a desire to look after it." Terri Metcalfe - Parent

Replication of good practice

This project is unique in its approach to climate action and anxiety in the educational environment. Co-ordinators have not found any other project comparable within the European Union and they have not found any other with similar methodology or approach in terms of a systems thinking approach and using the food forest as a learning toolbox.

The project has applied for further funding to Ireland's Dept of Environment. Core to the application is the five aspects of their systems thinking approach which is soil, water, biodiversity, food miles and the food forest. The intention is to extend these aspects to also include food waste and food composting and use that funding to trial their approaches in an urban environment concentrating on these two areas as these issues can be considered within the confined spaces of the urban environment.

The further adaptation of the program to involve the urban environment would make the unique systems thinking approach fully replicable to any school or community group.

Lessons Learned

- There is a latent demand for this kind of education program at a primary, secondary schools' level and within community groups.
- Managing expectations of schools and community groups wanting to get involved was another issue, and although welcomed, at the current level of the project is infeasible due to available resources.
- As the project expands there will be a strong need to take on further regional coordinators and this will be key to any further expansion or replication as they are the direct link to each school and each teacher and further expertise, and funding are core to this.
- Perhaps the biggest lesson learned by the coordinators is that climate anxiety exists, and it is an issue with children.
- Educating children early on climate issue can instil a greater appreciation of the need to care for our environment
- The systems thinking approach that Edible Landscapes has adopted has worked well where in operation.

Further Information

Website:

<https://ediblelandscape.ie/index.php/food-forest-climate-education-program/>

Case Study 10 - Funding programmes regarding bioeconomy topics in Baden-Württemberg

Typology: Fiscal & Financial

Regional background

Figure 25. Map of Germany showing Baden-Württemberg region

Baden-Württemberg is the third largest state in Germany, both in terms of area (35,750 km²) and population (around 11 million). It is in southwestern Germany and adjacent to three German states. In Europe, it is centrally located and shares its borders with three countries.

Stuttgart is the state capital and the largest city, with a population of around 630,000 by 2020. In addition to the urban centres, Baden-Württemberg has a strong rural area with diverse agriculture, forestry, and tourism. 586 of the 786 municipalities in Baden-Württemberg have fewer than 5,000 inhabitants. The landscape and nature are diverse with large contiguous forest areas such as the Black and the Swabian Forests, or the Odenwald. Around 40% of Baden-Württemberg's surface area is covered with forest. Regarding water bodies, the lake Constance (total area: 572 km²) plays an important role as drinking water source and recreational use in the region. The main rivers that flow through Baden-Württemberg are the Rhine (437 km), Neckar (367 km) and Danube (251 km).

The most developed value chains related to the bioeconomy are those related to the forestry and agricultural sectors. For both sectors the use of biomass and valorisation of fibre-rich by-products for multiple purposes plays a major role e.g., biopolymers (e.g., packaging, automotive, textile and paper industry), bio-based building blocks for phyto pharma (e.g., natural cosmetics) and biomass for energy and biofuels as final stage of the cascade use. The most relevant biomass feedstocks of Baden Württemberg are wood, lignin, lignocellulose, bio-waste, agricultural by-products (e.g., from harvest or manures) and insects.

In 2019 a "Sustainable Bioeconomy Strategy" was launched by the Government of Baden-Württemberg, which was a milestone for the relevance of bioeconomy in the policy agenda. The basic objectives of the bioeconomy strategy are the development of biological concepts for the exploitation of renewable or recyclable raw materials, and the development of Baden-Württemberg as a model region for sustainable and circular economy, as well as, strengthening the role of the rural areas. Other relevant aspects considered are e.g., impact to climate change, protection of the biodiversity and the promotion of bio-based innovations. The scope of the strategy is wide, covering rural, urban, and industrial areas.

Context for deployment of good practice

The Funding Program “Sustainable Bioeconomy as a Driver of Innovation for Rural Development” is being implemented as a measure (number 17) within the Baden-Württemberg Bioeconomy Strategy. The aim is to support the transfer of technology and knowledge in the field of sustainable production and use of resources from regional agriculture and forestry to enable a sustainable development of the region.

The program is launched within the Action Area “Sustainable bioeconomy in rural areas” (7.1.6. Regulatory and funding policies for rural areas) of the regional bioeconomy strategy. The program is supported by the Ministry of Food, Rural Affairs and Consumer Protection, one of the two ministries leading the implementation of the strategy. The program is currently managed by VDI/VDE Innovation + Technik GmbH.

Implementation of the good practice

Figure 26. programme funds rurally focused projects such as decentralized biogas grid injection

The topics and priorities for the funding are applied research and development in the following areas:

- Efficient and sustainable production and supply of regional biomass
- Consumer-oriented product and process innovations along the food value chain
- Intelligent raw material and material flow management
- New materials from wood, lignocellulosic growths, and agricultural by-products
- Innovative concepts for the further development of biogas plants.

The funding consists of a two-stage program. First, feasibility studies are funded to determine

the economic and environmental potential of the proposed solutions. The maximum funding amount in this first phase is €60,000 per project with a duration of 9 months.

Secondly, the selected feasibility studies can apply for a funding for innovation projects with a maximum funding €600,000 and a duration of up to 3 years.

Involvement of regional government or public bodies in the development of the practice

The funding program is implemented under the leadership of the Ministry of Food, Rural Affairs and Consumer Protection of Baden-Württemberg and as a measure of the regional bioeconomy strategy, as detailed above. The strategy was published in 2019 and there was a consultation process in 2017/2018 involving around 500 stakeholders. The financial support of the regional Government was up to € 5.1 Million, as of June 2022.

Results of good practice

For the last announcement of March 2022 regarding the results of 2020-2021, twenty-six feasibility studies were selected for funding:

- 5 projects in the area “Efficient and sustainable production and supply of regional biomass”

- 5 projects in the area “Consumer-oriented product and process innovations along the food value chain”
- 2 projects in the area “Intelligent raw material and material flow management”
- 8 projects in the area “New materials from wood, lignocellulosic growths, and agricultural by-products”
- 6 projects in the area “Innovative concepts for the further development of biogas plants”

Projects aimed at supporting bioeconomy adoption in rural regions.

Examples of feasibility studies funded under the programme include:

- Exploiting synergies between environment and economy for efficient biomass production for the bioeconomy in Baden-Württemberg
- Potential analysis of commercial hemp in the context of a sustainable bioeconomy
- Evaluation of innovative processes to produce plant fibres in regional added value for the optimization of the biogas process chain.
- Microalgae preparations for the reduction of fungicide use in viticulture.
- Sustainable culture media for the industrial production of clean meat
- A digital platform for mobilization and marketing of forestry and agricultural (residual) materials
- Regional biobased materials for packaging and films in agriculture and for ecological plant protection
- A new generation of bioenergy villages, integrative as biorefinery and in a renewable energy network
- Decentralized biogas upgrading: Numerical simulation of a novel biogas upgrading process for small volume flows for its technical and economic evaluation.
- Combined recovery of nitrogen and phosphorus from agricultural digestate considering the carbon cycle

Figure 27. Field Research

Replication of good practice

The practice can be replicated by other regions to support the development of the bioeconomy in rural areas.

Future plans

The funding program is still operating.

Lessons Learned

The funding process and payments are easier and more straightforward for companies than other regional programmes.

Further Information

- Information funding program (in German): [FE-Förderprogramm: Ministerium für Ernährung, Ländlichen Raum und Verbraucherschutz Baden-Württemberg \(baden-wuerttemberg.de\)](#)
- Website Bioeconomy Baden-Württemberg: [Home - Bioökonomie Baden-Württemberg \(baden-wuerttemberg.de\)](#)

2.3 Inventory of Good Practices

From **86** practices identified in the screening of good practices, **75** have been selected for inclusion within the best practices inventory, aligning closely with the definition of good practice outline in Section 3. These practices were distributed widely across Europe and the different regional jurisdictions allocated to partners in Section 3. The practices primarily focus on regional level initiatives, however, in certain cases e.g., where a practice has a major impact and could be transferred regionally (e.g., Italian Ban on Plastic Bags, or Netherland’s Green Deal examples), or where a programme is operating nationally but benefits regional stakeholders (e.g., the LEADER programme), these have been included within the inventory. The breakdown of practices across regions includes Balkan Region (12 practices); Central European Region (7 practices); Eastern European Region (8 practices); Mediterranean Region (12 practices); Northern European Region (24 practices) and Western European Region (12 practices). This is depicted in Figure 28 below.

Figure 28. Breakdown of Good Practices by Region

Due to the presence of regional partners within the clusters, there is inevitably a bias towards the 5 ROBIN regions. However, a broad distribution of practices from across Europe is still evident from the fact that examples are drawn from 24 different countries. The distribution of good practices by country is shown in Figure 29 below.

Figure 29. Distribution of Good Practices by Country

Considering the categorization of instruments covered, and the closest link between the practices and categories of instruments described by Elbersen et al., (2020) the practices breakdown across the following instruments: fiscal and financial instruments (24), regulatory instruments (7), information and advisory instruments (15), networking, collaboration, and joint planning instruments (20), voluntary instruments (3), other instruments (6). However, many of practices straddle across multiple instruments. For example, some of the accelerator programmes, such as BioVale’s Innovation BioCamp provide advisory services, while at the same time providing network opportunities and, potentially, access to finance and investment. The potential for overlapping categories of instruments is also noted by Elbersen et al., (2020). The main types of instruments covered by the good practices are highlighted in Figure 30 below.

Figure 30. Category Of Instruments

There was a wide distribution of territorial deployment locations among good practices identified. Many of the practices could be deployed in multiple territorial contexts, while some are more geared towards a rural (24%), urban (16%) or coastal (11%) setting, with a smaller (1%) number described as peri-urban or mountainous/uplands. This is useful for governments to understand the types of practices which may be used to stimulate different bioeconomy territories within a particular region.

Figure 31. Deployment Location of Good Practices

The inventory of good practices is described further in 4.2.1 and 4.2.2.

2.3.1 Classification of Good Practice Inventory under Typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models

The inventory of good practices is further presented and described in Section 4.2.1 where practices are classified under the typology of circular bioeconomy governance models, developed through the ROBIN project. The practices are later present in full in Section 4.2.2. The typology of circular bioeconomy governance models was developed previously in ROBIN D1.1 “Typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models” by AUTH with input from ROBIN partners.

In D1.1., AUTH and partners collected 20 case studies of regional bioeconomy governance models from across Europe and analysing these and drawing on sources from literature, AUTH developed a typology of circular bioeconomy governance models, with defining characteristics which can help to distinguish between different governance approaches.

The typology of circular bioeconomy governance models which was developed, is partly based on the theoretical framework of Dietz *et al.* (2018) who have developed a taxonomy of political support measures (enabling governance) that represent the first challenge of governance, and regulatory tools (constraining governance) that represent the second challenge of governance, to distinguish between the two fundamental political challenges in setting up an effective governance framework for a sustainable bioeconomy. Within D1.1. AUTH applied this typology to the collected governance

models. Within T1.2 this typology is applied by MTU to the inventory of good practices, classifying these to better define the practices and provide providing practical inspiration for ROBIN regions to improve their governance models through the integration of best practice supporting mechanisms. The typology matrix is shown in Table 8 below.

Table 8. Typology

Transformation Path	TP1: Fossil fuel substitution
	TP2: Boosting primary sector productivity
	TP3: New and more efficient biomass uses
	TP4: Low-bulk and high-value applications
Enabling Governance Mechanisms	EG1: Bio-based R&D strategy
	EG2: Enhancing the competitiveness of bio-based products through subsidies
	EG3: Implementing awareness-raising campaigns to increase societal participation
Constraining Governance	CG0: No goal conflicts explicitly considered
	CG1: Global equity/ Regional equity concerns
	CG2: Water scarcity
	CG3: Land degradation
Helix Model	CG4: Land use change
	H1: Penta Helix: Business, Knowledge, Administration, Society, Capital
	H2: Quadruple Helix: Business, Knowledge, Administration, Society
Driver Measures	H3: Triple Helix: Business, Knowledge, Administration
	DM1: Economic measures (price, taxation or subsidies)
	DM2: Regulatory measures
Territorial aspects	DM3: Information and support
	TA1: Rural
	TA2: Urban
	TA3: Coastal
Focus	TA4: Multiple
	F1: Energy
	F2: Material use
	F3: Waste prevention

	F4: Recycling
	F5: Food & Feed
Type of model	M1: Public
	M2: Private
	M3: Mixed
Transition Process	TS1: Top-Down
	TS2: Bottom-Up
Decision Making	DS1: Ad hoc / Voluntary agreements
	DS2: Legally binding / legislated decision making
Voting Mechanisms	V1: One member - one vote OR votes proportional to population
	V2: Minority members have more than one vote
Dispute Resolution Processes	DR1: Transparent and accountable process
	DR2: No formal process

Looking at the typology matrix, there are certain categories within the matrix which apply more closely to the governance structures outlined in T1.1. and which are less applicable to practices outlined in the inventory of T1.2. This is particularly the case for categories including decision making, voting mechanisms and dispute resolution, which were excluded from the analysis based on available information. For the purpose of aligning the inventory based on the typology, each practice was examined to see which categories were applicable, and which option within those categories best fit the practice, based on the information available.

Considering the first category of Transformation Path (TP), described by Dietz et al. (2018) the root cause of hurdles in the successful implementation of the circular bioeconomy, it was found that the majority of practices which aligned to one of the transformation paths aligned most closely with TP1 Substitution of fossil fuels with bio-based raw materials (40%), followed by TP3 New and more efficient biomass uses (30%), followed by TP2 Boosting primary sector productivity and TP4 Value creation and addition through the application of biological principles and processes separate from large-scale biomass production (15% each).

Considering the category of enabling function of governance models, i.e., how government can support the rise of the bioeconomy through appropriate political means, the analysis found that there was a slightly higher representation of practices which aligned most closely with enabling government (EG) option 3. 38% of practices were most aligned with EG3 Implementing awareness-raising campaigns to increase societal participation in bio-based transformation, including more responsible and sustainable consumption, while 35% were aligned with EG1 Bio-based research and development (R&D) strategy, with the remaining aligned with EG2 Enhancing the competitiveness of bio-based products through subsidies. This indicates a good balance between the various government enabling functions.

When evaluating the next category of constraining government, or using the safeguarding function of government to guard against the risks of an implementing bioeconomy, a small number of practices were found to be aligned constraining government 4 (CG3) relating to land degradation. These identified good practices were associated with bioeconomy activities which help to restore contaminated land, while others relate to activities around regenerative agriculture. There is, however, a noticeable lack of practices which contain information about potential negative impacts from their activities (e.g., how initiatives will meet their bio-based product objectives without having an impact on food, land, biodiversity etc.). Considering the recent emphasis on the requirement for the bioeconomy to operate within the ecological boundaries of the planet, this is a very important consideration.

Looking at the next matrix category, from the analysis of the stakeholders involved in our good practices, we find that there is enough information to indicate that the majority (around two thirds) of initiatives contained in the inventory are a least triple-helix collaborations (H3), combining business and knowledge with administration, with the remaining also bringing on board society (quadruple helix-H2) in initiatives such as education, knowledge and awareness, community activities, and social enterprises. We find less obvious examples of Penta helix models (H1), which also include the collaborations above plus capital (excluding that capital provided by businesses and government who are supporting many of the initiatives). Clearly, this is an important factor, as the bioeconomy requires significant investment and scaling the bioeconomy will require the participation of private investors, investment banks etc. The European Circular Bioeconomy Fund, and initiatives of the Nordic Investment Bank supporting investment in bioeconomy scale-up, among others show that there is a growing interest from the capital stakeholders, and significant further potential for development of penta-helix models.

Considering the driver measure of the best practices we find that the majority of these are either related to DM3 (45%) Information and support or DM1 (42%) Economic measures (price, taxation, or subsidies) and only a relatively small number related most closely relate to DM2 Regulation (12%).

Looking at the territorial setting of these practices, based on the typology options, around half of the practices could fit across multiple territorial contexts, with the other remaining practices dedicated specifically to rural (24%), urban (16%) or coastal (10%) settings.

When analysing the focus of the practice, it seems that the largest number of practices link most closely with material use (52%), with a smaller number aligned with energy (22%), waste prevention (13%), food and feed (8%) and recycling (3%).

Considering the type of model used to implement the practice, the vast majority are either public initiatives (39%), or public-private collaborations (52%), with a small amount (8%) that can be identified as private. This emphasizes that government is playing a significant role in development of initiatives to support bioeconomy development, but also that the private sector is engaging and seeing the commercial benefit of many of these developments.

Finally considering the transition process, the typology matrix distinguishes between two main approaches, a bottom-up approach that facilitates regional clusters and promotes radical innovation through cooperation between vested players and frontrunners that are co-creating a longer-term vision that informs the short-term actions and a more traditional top-down governance strategy, focusing on the shorter-term economic opportunities and incremental innovation that keep the overall structure of existing industries intact (Bosman and Rotmans, 2016). There is a slightly higher level of top-down approach from the analysis.

The complete inventory and its classification under the typology are presented by geographical cluster in Table 9. The full list of best practice description follows in Section 4.2.2.

Table 9. Inventory of Good Practices by Regional Cluster

Classified based on typology developed in Deliverable 4.1 of ROBIN project Transf. Path = Transformation Path ; Enabl. Gov. Mech. = Enabling Government Mechanisms; Const. Gov. Mech. = Constraining Government Mechanisms; Driver Meas. = Driver measures; Trns. Prcs. = Transition Process; Dsc. Mkg. = Decision Making; Vote Mch. = Voting Mechanism; Dispute Res. Proc. = Dispute Resolution Process).

Balkan Cluster																																								
Typology	Transf. Path				Enabl. Gov. Mech			Const. Gov Mech.				Helix Model			Driver Meas.			Territorial Aspects				Focus					Type of Model			Trns Prcs		Dsc Mkg		Vote Mch		Dispute Res. Proc.				
	TP1	TP2	TP3	TP4	EG1	EG2	EG3	CG0	CG1	CG2	CG3	CG4	H1	H2	H3	DM1	DM2	DM3	TA1	TA2	TA3	TA4	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	M1	M2	M3	TS1	TS2	DS1	DS2	V1	V2	DR1	DR2	DR3	
Practices																																								
1. Organic, Sustainable, Regenerative Agriculture Practices In Danube Delta																																								
2. SPIRE (Smart Post-Industrial Regenerative Ecosystem)																																								
3. GODANUBIO – Participative Ecosystems for fostering the revitalization of rural-																																								

Balkan Cluster																																										
Typology	Transf. Path				Enabl. Gov. Mech			Const. Gov Mech.					Helix Model			Driver Meas.			Territorial Aspects				Focus					Type of Model			Trns Prcs		Dsc Mkg		Vot e Mch		Disput e Res. Proc.					
	TP1	TP2	TP3	TP4	EG1	EG2	EG3	CG0	CG1	CG2	CG3	CG4	H1	H2	H3	DM1	DM2	DM3	TA1	TA2	TA3	TA4	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	M1	M2	M3	TS1	TS2	DS1	DS2	V1	V2	DR1	DR2	DR3			
Practices																																										
urban cooperation through governing Danube Circular Bioeconomy																																										
4. LIFE climate value chains																																										
5. Measures for widening participation																																										
6. Increasing the urban bio-waste recycling rate																																										
7. Synergies and consulting services for urban bioeconomy																																										
8. Funding programmes for green																																										

Balkan Cluster																																									
Typology	Transf. Path				Enabl. Gov. Mech			Const. Gov Mech.				Helix Model			Driver Meas.			Territorial Aspects				Focus					Type of Model			Trns Prcs		Dsc Mkg		Vot e Mch		Disput e Res. Proc.					
	TP1	TP2	TP3	TP4	EG1	EG2	EG3	CG0	CG1	CG2	CG3	CG4	H1	H2	H3	DM1	DM2	DM3	TA1	TA2	TA3	TA4	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	M1	M2	M3	TS1	TS2	DS1	DS2	V1	V2	DR1	DR2	DR3		
Practices																																									
transition, including bioeconomy																																									
9. SOCIAL PLATE - Supporting Social Enterprises in combating poverty and social exclusion																																									
10. Bioenergy and fertilizers from livestock and agriculture farms																																									
11. Use of by-products of the wine and spirits industry as disinfectants for Covid-19 pandemic																																									
12. Restoration of non-compliant landfill sites																																									

Balkan Cluster																																								
Typology	Transf. Path				Enabl. Gov. Mech			Const. Gov Mech.				Helix Model			Driver Meas.			Territorial Aspects				Focus					Type of Model			Trns Prcs		Dsc Mkg		Vot e Mc h		Disput e Res. Proc.				
	TP1	TP2	TP3	TP4	EG1	EG2	EG3	CG0	CG1	CG2	CG3	CG4	H1	H2	H3	DM1	DM2	DM3	TA1	TA2	TA3	TA4	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	M1	M2	M3	TS1	TS2	DS1	DS2	V1	V2	DR1	DR2	DR3	
Practices																																								
in Larnaka District- Tersefanou																																								

Central European Cluster																																										
Typology	Transf. Path				Enabl. Gov. Mech			Const. Gov Mech.				Helix Model			Driver Meas.			Territorial Aspects				Focus					Type of Model			Trns Prcs		Dsc Mkg		Vot e Mch		Disput e Res. Proc.						
	TP1	TP2	TP3	TP4	EG1	EG2	EG3	CG0	CG1	CG2	CG3	CG4	H1	H2	H3	DM1	DM2	DM3	TA1	TA2	TA3	TA4	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	M1	M2	M3	TS1	TS2	DS1	DS2	V1	V2	DR1	DR2	DR3			
Practices																																										
1. Bioeconomy Innovation and Investment Program for Rural Areas (BIPL BW)																																										
2. Green Start-up Ecosystem																																										
3. BayBioökonomie-Scale-Up																																										
4. National Procurement Database for Biobased Products																																										
5. Circular Biobased Delta																																										

Central European Cluster																																							
Typology	Transf. Path				Enabl. Gov. Mech			Const. Gov Mech.				Helix Model			Driver Meas.			Territorial Aspects				Focus					Type of Model			Trns Prcs		Dsc Mkg		Vot e Mc h		Disput e Res. Proc.			
	TP1	TP2	TP3	TP4	EG1	EG2	EG3	CG0	CG1	CG2	CG3	CG4	H1	H2	H3	DM1	DM2	DM3	TA1	TA2	TA3	TA4	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	M1	M2	M3	TS1	TS2	DS1	DS2	V1	V2	DR1	DR2	DR3
Practices																																							
6. Netherlands Green Deal																																							
7. Bioeconomy Congres Baden Wuerttemberg																																							

Eastern European Cluster																																									
Typology	Transf. Path				Enabl. Gov. Mech			Const. Gov Mech.				Helix Model			Driver Meas.			Territorial Aspects				Focus					Type of Model			Trns Prc s		Dsc Mkg		Vot e Mc h		Disput e Res. Proc.					
	TP1	TP2	TP3	TP4	EG1	EG2	EG3	CG0	CG1	CG2	CG3	CG4	H1	H2	H3	DM1	DM2	DM3	TA1	TA2	TA3	TA4	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	M1	M2	M3	TS1	TS2	DS1	DS2	V1	V2	DR1	DR2	DR3		
Practices																																									
1. The Greening Self-Assessment Tool for SME																																									
2. Landscape Recovery Program of the Košice region																																									
3. Environmental approaches in Haňovice																																									
4. Local suppliers providing food to regional schools and other types of facilities																																									
5. Regional municipal biomass project on Poľana																																									

Eastern European Cluster																																								
Typology	Transf. Path				Enabl. Gov. Mech			Const. Gov Mech.				Helix Model			Driver Meas.			Territorial Aspects				Focus					Type of Model			Trns Prcs		Dsc Mkg		Vot e Mch		Disput e Res. Proc.				
	TP1	TP2	TP3	TP4	EG1	EG2	EG3	CG0	CG1	CG2	CG3	CG4	H1	H2	H3	DM1	DM2	DM3	TA1	TA2	TA3	TA4	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	M1	M2	M3	TS1	TS2	DS1	DS2	V1	V2	DR1	DR2	DR3	
Practices																																								
6. Lithuanian Bioeconomy Development Feasibility Study																																								
7. NATIONAL REFORM PROGRAMME OF HUNGARY 2022 - green business development																																								

Mediterranean Cluster																																								
Typology	Transf. Path				Enabl. Gov. Mech			Const. Gov Mech.				Helix Model			Driver Meas.			Territorial Aspects				Focus					Type of Model			Trns Prcs		Dsc Mkg		Vot e Mc h		Disput e Res. Proc.				
	TP1	TP2	TP3	TP4	EG1	EG2	EG3	CG0	CG1	CG2	CG3	CG4	H1	H2	H3	DM1	DM2	DM3	TA1	TA2	TA3	TA4	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	M1	M2	M3	TS1	TS2	DS1	DS2	V1	V2	DR1	DR2	DR3	
Practices																																								
1. "Bioeconomy Technical Platform" Call																																								
2. Biovoices: Video shorts in social media																																								
3. Interactive map Atresbio																																								
4. Novamont@school																																								
5. Blue Bio Value																																								
6. Greenhouse soil biosolarisation in horticulture																																								
7. Green manures and cover crops in field and horticultural crops																																								

Mediterranean Cluster																																										
Typology	Transf. Path				Enabl. Gov. Mech			Const. Gov Mech.				Helix Model			Driver Meas.			Territorial Aspects				Focus					Type of Model			Trns Prcs		Dsc Mkg		Vot e Mch		Disput e Res. Proc.						
	TP1	TP2	TP3	TP4	EG1	EG2	EG3	CG0	CG1	CG2	CG3	CG4	H1	H2	H3	DM1	DM2	DM3	TA1	TA2	TA3	TA4	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	M1	M2	M3	TS1	TS2	DS1	DS2	V1	V2	DR1	DR2	DR3			
Practices																																										
8. Use of waste to promote biological control and biodiversity																																										
9. Use of alternative materials for plastic staking elements																																										
10. Use of alternative materials for plastic mulching films																																										
11. Use of treated sewage sludge in the agricultural sector																																										
12. Ban on single use carrier bags																																										

Northern Europe																																												
Typology	Transf. Path				Enabl. Gov. Mech			Const. Gov Mech.				Helix Model			Driver Meas.			Territorial Aspects				Focus					Type of Model			Trns Prcs		Dsc Mkg		Vot e Mch		Disput e Res. Proc.								
	TP1	TP2	TP3	TP4	EG1	EG2	EG3	CG0	CG1	CG2	CG3	CG4	H1	H2	H3	DM1	DM2	DM3	TA1	TA2	TA3	TA4	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	M1	M2	M3	TS1	TS2	DS1	DS2	V1	V2	DR1	DR2	DR3					
Practices																																												
1. BioVale Innovation Biocamp																																												
2. Region of Skåne's Innovation-oriented Public Procurement Programme																																												
3. Kalundborg Eco-Industrial park																																												
4. EIP-Agri																																												
5. Bioeconomy Ireland Week																																												
6. ABC Economy																																												
7. ICT-BIOCHAIN																																												

Northern Europe																																								
Typology	Transf. Path				Enabl. Gov. Mech			Const. Gov Mech.				Helix Model			Driver Meas.			Territorial Aspects				Focus					Type of Model			Trns Prcs		Dsc Mkg		Vot e Mch		Disput e Res. Proc.				
	TP1	TP2	TP3	TP4	EG1	EG2	EG3	CG0	CG1	CG2	CG3	CG4	H1	H2	H3	DM1	DM2	DM3	TA1	TA2	TA3	TA4	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	M1	M2	M3	TS1	TS2	DS1	DS2	V1	V2	DR1	DR2	DR3	
Practices																																								
8. The Sustainable Tipperary Energy Roadshow 2022																																								
9. LEADER Programme for Rural Development 2014-2020																																								
10. EPA Green Public Procurement																																								
11. Enterprise Ireland Climate Action Voucher																																								
12. Green Enterprise: Innovation for a Circular Economy Fund																																								

Northern Europe																																									
Typology	Transf. Path				Enabl. Gov. Mech			Const. Gov Mech.				Helix Model			Driver Meas.			Territorial Aspects				Focus				Type of Model			Trns Prcs		Dsc Mkg		Vote Mch		Dispute Res. Proc.						
	TD1	TD2	TD3	TD4	EC1	EC2	EC3	CC1	CC2	CC3	CC4	LI1	LI2	LI3	DM1	DM2	DM3	TA1	TA2	TA3	TA4	E1	E2	E3	E4	EF	M1	M2	M3	TC1	TC2	DC1	DC2	V1	V2	DR1	DR2	DR3			
Practices																																									
13. Woodland Support Projects Fund 2021-2022																																									
14. Local Enterprise Office Green for Micro Programme																																									
15. Skillnet Ireland-Climate Ready Academy																																									
16. Kerry Sustainable Energy Co-Op																																									

Northern Europe																																									
Typology	Transf. Path				Enabl. Gov. Mech			Const. Gov Mech.				Helix Model			Driver Meas.			Territorial Aspects				Focus				Type of Model			Trn s Prc s		Dsc Mkg		Vot e Mch		Disput e Res. Proc.						
	TD1	TD2	TD3	TD4	EC1	EC2	EC3	CC1	CC2	CC3	CC4	L11	L12	L13	DM1	DM2	DM3	TA1	TA2	TA3	TA4	F1	F2	F3	F4	FF	M1	M2	M3	TC1	TC2	DC1	DC2	V1	V2	DR1	DR2	DR3			
Practices																																									
17. Pairc NaMara (Nua Na Mara)																																									
18. Paper Province																																									
19. Greve Biogas "Magic Factory"																																									
20. Biorefinery Innovation Platform: Accelerate to commercialisation																																									
21. Växjö Energi																																									

Northern Europe																																								
Typology	Transf. Path				Enabl. Gov. Mech			Const. Gov Mech.				Helix Model			Driver Meas.			Territorial Aspects				Focus				Type of Model			Trn s Prc s		Dsc Mkg		Vot e Mch		Disput e Res. Proc.					
	TD1	TD2	TD3	TD4	EC1	EC2	EC3	CC1	CC2	CC3	CC4	LI1	LI2	LI3	DM1	DM2	DM3	TA1	TA2	TA3	TA4	E1	E2	E3	E4	EF	M1	M2	M3	TC1	TC2	DC1	DC2	V1	V2	DR1	DR2	DR3		
Practices																																								
22. Green Business Models Programme																																								
23. Ireland's Knowledge Centre For Carbon, Climate And Community Action (IKC3)																																								
24. Edible Landscape Project CLG																																								

Western Europe																																								
Typology	Transf. Path				Enabl. Gov. Mech			Const. Gov Mech.				Helix Model			Driver Meas.			Territorial Aspects				Focus					Type of Model			Trns Prcs		Dsc Mkg		Vot e Mch		Disput e Res. Proc.				
	TP1	TP2	TP3	TP4	EG1	EG2	EG3	CG0	CG1	CG2	CG3	CG4	H1	H2	H3	DM1	DM2	DM3	TA1	TA2	TA3	TA4	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	M1	M2	M3	TS1	TS2	DS1	DS2	V1	V2	DR1	DR2	DR3	
Practices																																								
1. Paris Region Sufficiency Factory																																								
2. Bio-based circular economy																																								
3. West Grid Synergy project																																								
4. Reducing bio-waste from domestic waste																																								
5. DERVAL AGRI' METHANE site																																								
6. "Terres Fert'île" (fertile island) project																																								
7. Regional Biomass Scheme																																								

Western Europe																																								
Typology	Transf. Path				Enabl. Gov. Mech			Const. Gov Mech.				Helix Model			Driver Meas.			Territorial Aspects				Focus					Type of Model			Trns Prcs		Dsc Mkg		Vote Mch		Dispute Res. Proc.				
	TP1	TP2	TP3	TP4	EG1	EG2	EG3	CG0	CG1	CG2	CG3	CG4	H1	H2	H3	DM1	DM2	DM3	TA1	TA2	TA3	TA4	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	M1	M2	M3	TS1	TS2	DS1	DS2	V1	V2	DR1	DR2	DR3	
Practices																																								
8. Catalisti																																								
9. Blue Cluster																																								
10. Moonshot																																								
11. Ecological Investment Support in Flanders																																								
12. Grand Est Bioeconomy Eco-System																																								

2.3.2 *Good Practice Inventory*

An inventory of 75 practices has been collected by the ROBIN partners and these are presented here in Section 4.2. These practices are distributed widely across Europe and the different jurisdiction outlined in Section. Within this section we include summaries of good practices found for each region as follows.

- Section 4.2.1 Balkan Region (12 practices).
- Section 4.2.2 Central European Region (7 practices).
- Section 4.2.3 Eastern European Region (8 practices).
- Section 4.2.4 Mediterranean Region (12 practices).
- Section 4.2.5 Northern European Region (24 practices).
- Section 4.2.6 Western European Region (12 practices).

The good practices are presented by region in Section 4.2.1.- 4.2.6 below.

2.3.3 Good Practices from Balkan Region

Within ROBIN, partners based within the Balkan Regions, namely AUTH, QPL & RCM, from Greece led in collection of good practices. This was focused on the territory of the Region of Central Macedonia but expanded more widely to include the following countries: Greece, Cyprus, Bulgaria, Albania, Serbia, Montenegro, Romania, North Macedonia, Croatia, Bosnia and Slovenia. 12 good practices have been collected from the region. The majority of these were either Networking, Collaboration and Joint Planning instruments or Fiscal and Financial instruments, with a small number of Information and Advisory instruments, and Voluntary instruments (see Figure 32 below). The full list of good practices from the Balkan Region is outlined in Table 10, and the best practices are included below.

Figure 32. Types of Good Practice in Balkan Region

Table 10. Balkan Region Good Practices

Good Practice Number	Good Practice Name	Jurisdiction, Country
1	Organic, Sustainable, Regenerative Agriculture Practices in Danube Delta	Danube Delta Region, Romania
2	SPIRE (Smart Post-Industrial Regenerative Ecosystem)	Maramures Region, Romania
3	GODANUBIO – Participative Ecosystems for fostering the revitalization of rural-urban cooperation through governing Danube Circular Bioeconomy	Slavonia Region, Croatia
4	LIFE climate value chains	Central Slovenia Region, Slovenia
5	Measures for widening participation	Region of Western Macedonia, Greece
6	Increasing the urban bio-waste recycling rate	Duboko, Pirot, Srem-Mačva and Pančevo, Serbia
7	Synergies and consulting services for urban bioeconomy	Belgrade, Serbia
8	Funding programmes for green transition, including bioeconomy	North Macedonia
9	SOCIAL PLATE - Supporting Social Enterprises in combating poverty and social exclusion	Region of Central Macedonia, Greece
10	Bioenergy and fertilizers from livestock and agriculture farms	Region of Central Macedonia, Greece
11	Use of by-products of the wine and spirits industry as disinfectants for Covid-19 pandemic	Region of Central Macedonia, Greece
12	Restoration of non-compliant landfill sites in Larnaka District-Tersefanou	Larnaka District-Tersefanou, Cyprus

1: Organic, Sustainable, Regenerative Agriculture Practices in the Danube Delta.

Problem Statement

Future agricultural practices and how they will be funded and implemented by the operators on the agri-food chains from the wetlands such as the Danube Delta but also other areas from the Danube area.

Executive Summary

This good practice seeks to maintain sustainable systems without degrading them. Regenerative practices recognize how natural systems are currently impacted and apply techniques to restore systems to improved productivity. Regenerative and sustainable actions overlap and essentially incorporate the same practices.

Description

Regenerative agriculture uses a holistic framework that aims to continuously renew the land and improve the overall environment. This system of farming principles and practices increases biodiversity, enriches soils, improves watersheds, and enhances ecosystem services. Regenerative agriculture processes capture carbon in the soil, reversing current global trends of atmospheric accumulation. The goal here is not just to cut down on the depletion of resources, but to restore lands, increase productivity, and improve the environment through better farming processes.

In addition, the objectives of the good practice are to identify opportunities for collaboration in support of clusters, through various programs, partnerships, tools; attracting resources for the development of the organic farming sector but also taking into consideration how to deal with agro-ecology issues like carbon sequestration.

Type of Practice: Non-Financial Business Support

Type of Instrument: Info & Advisory, Networking

Region: Romania / Danube Delta

Year Implemented: 2022

Implementation

Deployment setting: Coastal

Stakeholder beneficiaries: SMEs

Level of uptake: 4 operators on the agri-food chains.

Years of operation: 1

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Lasting impacts on water management, crop management, soil fertility, energy and waste management, and disease or pest management.

Social Impacts

The resulting improvements in biodiversity, soil quality, watersheds, and overall ecosystem and with the move towards regenerative agriculture will provide society with improved living standards and towards an eco- friendly culture.

Economic Impacts

Regenerative practices and applying these techniques to restore systems to improved productivity will naturally have a knock-on effect economically. With a sustainable agricultural system, a sustainable economic model will evolve.

Replication Potential and Regional Deployment Considerations

The knowledge can be transferred on future agricultural practices and how they will be funded and implemented by the operators on the agri-food chains from the wetlands such as the Danube Delta but also other areas from the Danube area.

Further Information

Website:

<https://biodanubius.ro/en/evenimente/organic-sustainable-regenerative-agriculture-practices-in-danube-delta-june-3-1000-tulcea-county-council-dobrogea-room/>

2: SPIRE (Smart Post-Industrial Regenerative Ecosystem)

Problem Statement

Baia Mare is among the first European cities that is trying to start the decontamination procedures for the heavy metal polluted soils using nature-based solutions through the SPIRE project. In the past, the city has faced problems related to soil pollution, and this project aims to solve these problems and aims to involve citizens actively in the development of the city.

Executive Summary

This good practice has the ambition of starting a long-term environmental, social and economic redevelopment in Baia Mare, facilitating its transition from Romania’s ex-mining capital to a leader of environmental design and production. It will achieve this through the co-development of new adaptive and productive landscapes, integrated into a circular ecosystem of cascading material and energy value chains.

Description

Over the next three years, a total area of about eight hectares of land will become Living Labs. The entire project will involve citizens, entrepreneurs and students who will be able to come up with innovation ideas and will have a specially created space in the city centre, an Innovation Hub.

The project partners will help to implement a virtual rewards and payments system, called iLEU, to encourage sustainable development behaviours in the city and to support citizens’ involvement in the project, but also to obtain benefits and reductions locally, in the future. The iGIS platform will be used for data collection, a platform that will be able to provide forecasts on the duration of a land decontamination.

Type of Practice: Social Innovation

Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning, Info & Advisory

Region: Romania / Maramures

Year Implemented: 2017-2019

The UIA SPIRE project will use non-invasive and plant methods for remediation of heavy metal pollution. At the same time, the project aims to support new economies based on nature at local level, new initiatives in the community and ideas from young people.

Finally, after the concrete results of the project the partners will develop a Masterplan for the Baia Mare Metropolitan Area, which will aim at the recovery and regeneration of the approximately 650 hectares of polluted land.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Peri-Urban

Stakeholder beneficiaries:

Level of uptake: 250 youth beneficiaries and 3000 citizens involved.

Years of operation: 4

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

SPIRE will overall reclaim ca. 7 ha of polluted and/or unused public land through an adaptive agenda able to deliver both short and long-term results. Combining landscaping design with the adoption of phytoremediation techniques will not only renature and reconnect such areas with the urban system but also trigger a long-term brownfields' remediation process and foster a "land-hold" strategy for future development ambitions/goals.

Social Impacts

SPIRE will stimulate awareness, knowledge and capacities related to environmental sustainability to actively engage and involve the citizenry and local stakeholders in the co-creation and embedding of a shared system of values aiming at a shift in the overall behaviour, attitude, and relationships between actors, towards an eco-friendly culture and a widespread collective ownership of SPIRE's goals and activities.

Economic Impacts

SPIRE will capitalise on underused local resources in order to stimulate the development of new green-economy activities. This will result in the generation of a bio-based energy supply and the start-up and incubation of new businesses dedicated to the prototyping and production of innovative construction materials, with the ultimate effect of reducing the overall GHG emissions in Baia Mare.

Replication Potential and Regional Deployment Considerations

Baia Mare joins the club of European Innovative Cities proposing a revolutionary approach to the reuse of heavy metal-contaminated land in the city, through adaptive phytoremediation and the creation of new urban ecosystems, as a long-term strategy for sustainable local economic development.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.greencluster.ro/english/spire.html>

Baia- Mare:

<https://www.uia-initiative.eu/en/uia-cities/baia-mare>

3: GODANUBIO - Participative Ecosystems

Problem Statement

Cities and regions around the Danube face major social changes because of demographic change. Better job opportunities and the prospect of a better life are attracting young people to the cities from the countryside. As a result, the exodus of workers leads to depopulated areas, leaving behind an ageing and increasingly unskilled population. The EU project GoDanuBio aims to counteract this process: the project is taking various approaches that aim to increase the attractiveness of rural areas and provide young people with new incentives to revive rural areas.

Executive Summary

The goal is to promote regional development in the Danube region through the bioeconomy. The ‘GoDanuBio’ project is designed to increase the attractiveness of rural areas in the Danube region, create new jobs, and thereby prevent the migration of young people to the cities. Demographic change is to be managed at the regional and local level through participatory governance and citizen involvement.

Description

Danube regions and cities face major societal transitions regarding demographic change. The rural exodus is caused by better employment opportunities for the youth and the prospect of a better life in cities. The movement of labour leads to depopulated areas leaving an aging and increasingly unskilled population behind. Circular bioeconomy is used as a tool, that promises to foster regional development: It is a concept focusing on the transition of a fossil-resource based economy towards an economy making use of sustainable production of biological resources and processes to develop new products, thus setting rural areas and their development into focus.

Type of Practice: Public Procurement

Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning, Fiscal & Financial, Info & Advisory

Region: Croatia / Slavonia

Year Implemented: 2020

Long term goal of the project is to enhance the socio-economic status of the regions, contribute to environmental, climate and resource protection as well as foster development of rural areas. An ecosystem for systematic multi-level governance with actors from the interested public, academia, industry, and political decision making will be developed. That ecosystem gives space for co-creation and new forms of integrated urban-rural cooperation leading to increased institutional capacity to tackle demographic change. Thus, overcoming the persistent lack of engagement of societal actors in the political system by giving them ownership to address demographic change.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Rural

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Public Bodies

Level of uptake: 5 partners, high level of participation in events

Years of operation: 3

Status: Recently ended (2022)

Environmental Impacts

The transition from a fossil-resource based economy towards an economy that makes use of the sustainable production of biological resources and processes to develop new products and services.

The use of renewable raw materials and their sustainable and regional production make an important contribution to the implementation of the bioeconomy.

Social Impacts

Increase the attractiveness of rural areas and provide young people with new incentives to revive rural areas. Establish new participatory policy systems and approaches to address demographic change at regional and local levels and encourage people to relocate from the city to rural areas.

Economic Impacts

Promote transregional cooperation and strategic development of the bioeconomy in the Danube macro region.

Replication Potential

A multi-level participative governance approach and new institutional capacities are needed to pool existent excellent competencies and development potentials. Co-creating future strategies to increase the attractiveness of rural areas is the key to give the youth new incentives to revive rural areas.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.interreg-danube.eu/approved-projects/godanubio>

Problem Statement

Establishing Climate Friendly Processing Chains to Reduce Carbon Emissions and Support the New Green Deal.

Executive Summary

The overall objective of the good practice is to contribute to a sustainable and long-lasting reduction of carbon emissions from supply chains of timber products in building and furniture sectors, fostering the principles of cascade use of biomass and substitution of fossil-based materials with biobased materials.

Description

The increasingly global transport of goods and raw materials contributes significantly to the environmental footprint of products.

Today, transport is the 3rd largest cause of climate change, along with energy consumption and the depletion of tropical and boreal primeval forests. The global movement of goods has been growing rapidly for years and will continue to grow for decades to now. Transport is also the only sector in the EU with steadily increasing rather than decreasing CO₂ emissions. All efforts to reduce climate-damaging CO₂ emissions, such as technical efficiency improvements, biofuel, and others, have not been able to stop the increase. This not only has a significant impact on the environment and climate, but also entails high economic costs. Finite raw materials such as crude oil, which are already scarce today, are senselessly burned on the road. The current project aims to initiate short supply chains in the wood industry within the European Union and thus make a practical contribution to climate protection.

Type of Practice: Financial Business Support

Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial, Info & Advisory, Networking

Region: Slovenia / Central Slovenia Region

Year Implemented: 2021

The project can be implemented as a good practice example for climate and environmentally friendly supply chains. The partners provide tools that can be of support in sustainable procurement also in terms of EU and UN goals, because sustainability in construction, office equipment, bioenergy and paper is much more than sustainable forestry.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: SMEs

Level of uptake: Targeting 400 architects, 300 public authorities and 300 businesses

Years of operation: 2

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Shifting supply chains in the timber sector towards a reduction of material flows to reduce carbon emissions. Integration of the issues of reduced grey energy and reduced carbon emissions into green public procurement.

Social Impacts

Raising awareness among designers and architects as important influencers on the choice of construction materials based on environmental impact. Sensitization of consumers and public on the influence of material flows on climate change, the need of changing behaviour and existing opportunities for acting.

Economic Impacts

Involves a range of different companies and focus on the development of economic incentives for climate friendly supply chains.

Replication Potential

Architects implementing in their projects the instruments and guidelines developed, as well as public authorities interested in using the tools in their construction and procurement projects. Companies involved shifting towards more sustainable supply chains.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.climate-value-chains.com/>

Problem Statement

There are already related policies and available facilities and mechanisms in the region for collecting some biowaste materials, such as bins and a collection company. But people are not aware of it and don't make use of them.

Executive Summary

Representatives of local stakeholders make targeted interventions to widen people's participation in collecting biowastes. For example, they took the following actions: (i) visited an open market to share with sellers' bags for biowastes and leaflets; and (ii) they approached the Association of Cafeteria Owners to inform them of alternative uses of coffee residues.

Description

In the HOOP project, the city of Kozani in the region of Western Macedonia established a "Biowaste Club" as an engagement tool to bring together different local actors and discuss new ways to transform urban food waste and sewage into high-value-added products. Recently local stakeholders designed and implemented the following local engagement activities:

(1) 18 people, representatives from the Municipality of Kozani, DIADYMA and representatives of the associations of the sellers/producers, visited the Kozani Open Market. They provided the sellers with bags to collect their biowastes. Also, they distributed a leaflet with instructions on what to put in the bags. When the open market closed, the sellers left the bags in a pre-defined place. Finally, the Waste Management Company collected the bags.

(2) CluBE with DIADYMA approached the Association of Cafeteria Owners regarding the coffee residues and food biowastes. Together, they prepared a document with topics and concerns to be discussed in their next board of directors meeting. The two key topics were the collection of the appropriate data (such as the list of all the cafeterias, indicative quantities, availability of storage in store, storage bins, ways of collection, frequency of collection, and the time of collection) and practical steps to widen participation (such as the frequent and effective collection of biowastes to avoid disturbing the operation of the cafeteria, distribution of brown bins in each cafeteria depending the quantities, and information campaigns to raise awareness to end users and clients).

Type of Practice: Social Innovation

Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning, info & advisory, Voluntary

Region: Greece / Region of Western Macedonia

Year Implemented: 2020

Implementation

Deployment setting: Urban

Stakeholder beneficiaries: SMEs & 50+ producers in the open market and cafeterias

Level of uptake: No (the activities were part of projects)

Years of operation: 3

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

The Biowaste Club is comprised of key local stakeholders along the value chain, and it is shaped according to a participatory approach. The group of participants is not fixed but flexible, set-up based on local needs and current topics. This approach empowers local stakeholders to have a say on local matters, improving inclusivity.

Social Impacts

People who have hens, pigs and other animals in their backyard collect biowastes from the Open Market every Saturday. Initiatives like the one in the Kozani Open Market should not break this circular economy loop.

Economic Impacts

Involves the participation of the business community via the Cluster of Bioeconomy and Environment of Western Macedonia (CLuBE)

Replication Potential

Other regions can organise targeted interventions by getting inspiration from the activities of the Region of Western Macedonia.

Further Information

Websites:

<https://hoopproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/SCALIBUR-HOOP-cross-project-webinar-CluBE-FV.pdf>

<https://www.cscp.org/hoop-biowaste-clubs/>

6: Increasing the urban bio-waste recycling rate

Problem Statement

215,000 tons of waste is collected per year. Up to 70,000 tons could be recycled and diverted from landfill. The bio-waste recycling rate could increase from 20% by 2025 to 40% by 2029.

Executive Summary

The EU and Sweden are helping the Serbian Ministry of Environment to launch a massive action to improve the separation of recyclable materials in municipal solid waste. They help it to buy waste collection vehicles, containers, and bins and to organise public information campaigns.

Description

In 2020, Serbia generated 2.95 million tons of municipal waste. According to the data of the Serbian Environmental Protection Agency, 79.45% of municipal waste was disposed of in landfills. There is no systematic waste treatment before landfilling. The average coverage of the municipal waste collection is 86.4%. The Serbia Waste Management Program 2022-2031 aims at an improved municipal waste management system through (1) an increased recycling rate; (2) reduced disposal of biodegradable waste in landfills; and (3) reduced disposal of waste in unsanitary landfills. To support Serbia in the implementation of its waste strategy for the benefit of citizens across the country, the EU and Sweden are helping the Ministry of Environment to launch a massive action to improve the separation of recyclable materials in municipal solid waste in four regions: Duboko, Pirot, Srem-Mačva and Pančevo. The EU investment of 6 million euros provides: (i) 26 waste collection vehicles; (ii) more than 90,000 containers and bins; and (iii) organise public information campaigns, based on studies and public opinion surveys. Serbian national institutions and local self-governments are co-financing the project. They and the citizens will be the owners and operators of the future systems. Sweden has provided technical assistance to central and local authorities to enable the successful preparation, introduction and operations of the new waste source separation services. Specific communication expertise is already in place to build awareness and inform the citizens about how the new recycling services will operate and what is expected from citizens.

Type of Practice: Public Procurement

Type of Instrument: Info & Advisory, Regulatory

Region: Serbia / Duboko, Pirot, Srem-Mačva and Pančevo.

Year Implemented: 2021

Implementation

Deployment setting: Urban

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Public Bodies

Level of uptake: Has been taken up but no precise numbers.

Years of operation: 2021 - 2023

Status: Not Active

Environmental Impacts

The resulting improvements in biodiversity, soil quality, watersheds, and overall ecosystem and with the move towards regenerative agriculture will provide society with improved living standards and towards an eco- friendly culture.

Social Impacts

Raising household recycling in the 4 regions involved in this project to 15% would mean an additional 30,000 tons of material per year directed to the Serbian recycling market. Then, the market is expected to create new opportunities and jobs in Serbia to process that material.

Economic Impacts

Regenerative practices and applying these techniques to restore systems to improved productivity will naturally have a knock-on effect economically. With a sustainable agricultural system, a sustainable economic model will evolve.

Replication Potential

Similar approaches can be applied to other regions. The project has a website where all key milestones are reported in the News section. Thus, interested regions could find there a lot of material (such as educational articles) and lessons learnt.

Further Information

Websites:

<https://odvajanjeotpada.euzatebe.rs/en/about-project>

<https://odvajanjeotpada.euzatebe.rs/en/news/waste-separation-also-creates-jobs>

<https://odvajanjeotpada.euzatebe.rs/en/news/eu-for-environment-promoting-waste-source-separation-in-4-regions>

7: Synergies and consulting services for urban bioeconomy

Problem Statement

The government of Serbia and cities such as Belgrade have ambitious plans. By 2025, at least a quarter of urban spaces should be green.

Executive Summary

Green infrastructure techniques are one of the components of urban bioeconomy. "Green Cities Serbia" offers sustainable and innovative solutions for greener cities. It is a Dutch public-private partnership that was founded to help Serbia reach these goals.

Description

The government of Serbia and cities such as Belgrade have ambitious plans. By 2025, at least a quarter of urban spaces should be green. To this end, they made synergies and engaged in knowledge-exchange activities.

(i) The Embassy of the Kingdom of the Netherlands in the Republic of Serbia run the "Green Cities Serbia" project. It was funded through a partnership between the Government of the Kingdom of the Netherlands and companies providing sustainable urban solutions to help their Serbian colleagues achieve the final goal of the green transition and improve the quality of life in Serbian cities. The project offers sustainable and innovative solutions for greener cities, such as the design of public or commercial greenery, renovation projects, parks, or other green spaces, which will enhance the social and economic well-being of Serbia's urban population.

(ii) Experts in urbanism and politicians from Serbia visited the Netherlands to exchange knowledge and ideas with their Dutch colleagues. The members of the Serbian delegation visited the green city model locations and exhibitions and attended presentations. They also participated in interactive workshops to recognise solutions that can inspire the next wave of sustainable urban development with a special focus on green infrastructure. At the end of the study visit, a session was organised at the Embassy of the Republic of Serbia in The Hague where Ksenija Milenković, the Ambassador of the Republic of Serbia to the Netherlands, talked with the participants about the continuation of the Green Cities of Serbia Project.

Type of Practice: Non-Financial Business Support

Type of instrument: Fiscal & Financial, Networking, Info & Advisory

Region: Serbia / Belgrade

Year Implemented: 2020

Implementation

Deployment setting: Urban

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Large Companies

Level of uptake: 7 partners involved, with more to be involved later.

Years of operation: 2020-2023

Status: Ongoing

Environmental Impacts

Green infrastructure improves biodiversity, air quality and water management, reduces heat and noise pollution.

Social Impacts

As more and more people move from rural to urban areas, municipalities face the challenge of keeping urban environments sustainable. Green spaces, such as parks and forests, play an important role in improving the quality of life in cities, enhancing social cohesion and contributing to healthy living and working environments.

Economic Impacts

Serbia could increase its GDP by 1% with more investments into green infrastructure, according to Siniša Mitrović, Adviser to the President in the Serbian Chamber of Commerce and Industry (PKS).

Replication Potential

Green Cities Serbia aims at sharing knowledge and expertise, and training and developing local private and public stakeholders. Their plans include incoming and outgoing trade missions, vocational training, knowledge exchange, and demonstration centres and projects. Other regions could benefit from these.

Further Information

Websites:

<https://www.greencitiesserbia.com/>

<https://www.kragujevac.rs/en/vizija-zelenih-gradova-srbije-razmenjena-sa-holandskim-kolegama/>

<https://balkanenergynews.com/green-infrastructure-may-increase-serbias-gdp-by-1/>

8: Funding programmes for green transition, including bioeconomy

Problem Statement

There is a need to make financing easier in the private sector for the transition to a modern, efficient, and competitive economy with zero greenhouse gas emissions in 2050 at the latest.

Executive Summary

The national government, the Free Zones Authority and the World Bank designed a strategic green investment fund for green structures, technologies, and infrastructure. The idea is to secure EUR 70 million from public funds, international financial institutions and private investors like banks, investment funds, and individuals. The fund's share in privately-owned projects won't exceed 40 percent.

Description

The Prime Minister of North Macedonia recently presented the Plan for Accelerated Economic Development ("Plan"), focusing on the green economy, digitalisation, innovation, and technological development. One of the financing mechanisms envisioned for fulfilling the purposes of the Plan is the Strategic Green Investment Fund for Investment Support ("SGIF"), intended for the support of investments in Technological Industrial Development Zones ("TDIZ").

The SGIF targets foreign and domestic investors, mainly focusing on medium and large companies, encouraging investments of up to EUR 750 million in the following four years. The decisions for what would be considered investment projects would be adopted by a panel of experts. The government would participate only 10% in the SGIF. In contrast, the rest would be financed through private capital, mainly invested by domestic and foreign banks, intended for projects and investments in green infrastructure and technologies, including bioeconomy. Currently, two large projects financed through the SGIF are in the pipeline.

Type of Practice: Financial Business Support

Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial, Information & advisory, Networking

Region: North Macedonia / National level

Year Implemented: 2022

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Large Companies

Level of uptake: 2 projects funded to date.

Years of operation: 1

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

The purpose is to create an efficient and competitive economy with zero greenhouse gas emissions in 2050 at the latest and to improve North Macedonia's compliance with the Sofia Declaration on the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans and EU rules.

Social Impacts

Based on analysis of the impact on the economy of current investments into TIDZ, with the current structure, quality and numbers achieved in the past decade, 15,000 new jobs are expected to be created by 2025.

Economic Impacts

The mechanism is expected to spark investments worth €750 million, boost economic growth by one percentage point, and increase exports by €2 billion over the next four years.

Replication Potential

Other countries or regions can develop similar financing mechanisms. TIDZ provides information on the structure of the mechanism and the terms and conditions of its operation on its website. Such information can serve as guidance for other initiatives.

Further Information

Websites:

<https://balkangreenenergynews.com/north-macedonia-to-establish-strategic-green-investment-fund-to-boost-green-economy/>

<https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?q=9c3d2389-334b-4e46-89ef-be2b29208b56>

<https://fez.gov.mk/en/green-investment-opportunities/>

9: SOCIAL PLATE - Supporting Social Enterprises in combating poverty and social exclusion

Problem Statement

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), about one third of global food production (around 30 to 40%), is lost or wasted annually. As such, every action that limits food waste is of great importance.

CMT is a public owned company and is the “Social Plate” is the first organized practice of “saving the food” in Greece with promising results.

Executive Summary

The “Social Plate” is a project coordinated by CMT. CMT is a public company founded in 1975 with facilities include the Fruit and Vegetable market (280 stores, distributed in 4 cores of 70 stores each) and the Meat market (24 stores). Daily, from CMT 600-800 tonnes of fruit and vegetables and 80-100 tonnes of meat are being shipped to local food markets and the Balkans.

Description

The goal of the project “Social Plate” is to provide food for weaker social groups, work to the long-term unemployed and to limit food waste. Within fifteen months of operation, the “Social Plate” team handled more than 345,000 kg fruits and vegetables, derived from the CMT facilities. The products are separated into those that are fit for consumption and those that are not. Specifically, 230,000 kg were recovered and offered to our fellow people and the rest was used for organic waste. The packaging of the received products is being reused instead of being discarded. The delivery is being handled by the organic waste management office of CMT with the help of volunteers from the agencies that benefit from the project. More than 75 agencies participate in the distribution (Social Grocery Stores, NGOs, Foundations, Church Kitchens). They receive the recovered products and distribute them, cooked or raw, to vulnerable social groups. Thus, the homeless, the unemployed, refugees, and anyone in need of a plate of food, can get just that, thanks to the all the volunteers working with “Social Plate”.

Type of Practice: Social Innovation

Type of Instrument: Voluntary, Info & Advisory, Networking

Region: Greece / Region of Central Macedonia

Year Implemented: 2018

Implementation

Deployment setting: Urban

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Communities/public

Level of uptake: More than 70 participant organisations

Years of operation: 5

Status: Initiative ended

Environmental Impacts

The original packaging of the products is being reused instead of being discarded. The products are separated into those that are fit for consumption and those that are not. Specifically, 230,000 kg were recovered and offered to our fellow people and the rest was used for organic waste.

Social Impacts

More than 230,000 kg were recovered and offered to for use and consumption and returned to the food chain, while the rest was used as organic waste.

Economic Impacts

The “Social Plate” is funded by INTERREG V-A Greece – Bulgaria 2014-2020 programme with a budget of €218,750. But the amount covers partially human resources and technical equipment. CMT tried to cover the financial gap by providing 3 employees on permanent basis even though more people were needed.

Replication Potential

This good practice could be applied by other such authorities’ handling/ retailing/ supervising food distribution/ retailing. CMT is directly supervised by Ministries of Development and Agriculture so other high level policy bodies could adopt such a good practice on regional/national level. In private sector, in the context of corporate social responsibility, can provide funds and labour until the practice becomes profitable through recycling, exploitation of organic waste or even through selling processed fruit.

Further Information

Website: <https://www.socialplate.eu/en/>

10: Bioenergy and fertilizers from livestock and agriculture farms

Problem Statement

Currently the management practices of livestock manure involve the collection and storage in livestock units or the spreading in the fields. The waste includes manure generation from pig or poultry livestock farms, cheese whey and olive facilities. The aforementioned practices constitute significant hazards due to the increased smelling and fire causing. Additionally, most of the nutrients are lost and the CO₂ footprint is high in the areas where such farms are located.

Executive Summary

The initiative involves the collection of farm manure for use in biogas systems to produce energy and fertiliser, along with sustainable management of the farm wastes.

Description

The facility is private and collects locally available farm manure for free. The manure is transported by trucks in the facility and is digested on-site. The produced biogas is utilized in a generator unit, while the digestate is composted and returned to the nearby fields as soil amendment.

The main stakeholders and beneficiaries are owners of the facility (who also own livestock farms and cultivations) and use most of the generated fertilizer in their cultivations. In addition, neighbouring farming facilities are collaborating and offering their facilities' waste to the biogas facility without the obligation of payment. This constitutes a "win-win" situation in the area since farmers are disposing of their waste in a sustainable manner and facility operation minimise the local CO₂ impact. All as well as local population are the beneficiaries. Finally,

Type of Practice: Other

Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning, Fiscal & Financial, Info & Advisory

Region: Greece / Region of Central Macedonia

Year Implemented: 2017

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Communities/public

Level of uptake: Both farmers and companies participating

Years of operation: 5 years

Status: Ongoing

yet importantly, the energy generated by the facility is provided to the national grid (under an agreed cost per kWh).

Environmental Impacts

The plant has operated since 2016 (trial) but officially started its operation and the electricity generation on early 2017. Biogas production helps to decrease the greenhouse gas emissions and through digestate composting nutrients return to the fields. The carbon footprint of the electricity production alone is 494,7 tons CO₂ eq/a negative. In 2017 the facility produced 8,5 MWh renewable electricity, while CO₂ savings were estimated at around 494.700 kg. During that year the facility processed:

- 70,000 t liquid cow manure
- 5,000 t poultry manure
- 1,000 t pork manure
- 6,000 t cheese whey
- 2,000 t olive mill by-products

Social Impacts

Awareness will rise amongst the local agricultural community. The practices developed will educate farmers and demonstrate the benefits to run their facilities in a more sustainable manner.

Economic Impacts

Directly revenue generated through low cost of feedstock for production and sale of renewable energy will constitute a strong sustainable business model for the facility. The availability of a biobased fertilisers.

Replication Potential

Biogas production helps to decrease the greenhouse gas emissions and through digestate composting nutrients return to the fields. The carbon footprint of the electricity production alone is 494,7 tons CO₂ eq/a negative. The practice may be transferred to other agricultural areas with both livestock farms and cultivations exist to solve the problems related to disposal of biological waste, raise awareness, and inspire farmers to run their facilities in a more sustainable manner.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.interregeurope.eu/good-practices/bioenergy-and-fertilizers-from-livestock-and-agriculture-farms>

11:Agrovision- Use of by-products of the wine and spirits industry as disinfectants for Covid-19 pandemic

Problem Statement

An important challenge that an industry must face the last years is the high cost of the cleaning and the disinfection of their equipment and surfaces to protect the employees against Covid-19 and therefore to continue their operation. Agrovision is trying to reduce this high cost applying the principles of circular economy, therefore, to re-use its by-products.

Executive Summary

The primary focus is on utilizing waste products from the wine and spirits industry to produce disinfectants to help fight the Covid-19 pandemic.

Description

The objectives of this practice are being reached as two potential disinfectants are produced by the wastes and by-products of the wine industry. The wine industry generates various wastes and by-products such as wine lees, grape pomace, and grape seeds. The above may be further used to produce a spirit called tsipouro. During the distillation process, the first litter (termed as ""head"") generated by the traditional copper vessels used for tsipouro production is rejected due to its composition in ethyl acetate and acetaldehyde as well as due to its high content in alcohol (80%, v/v). This rejected quantity is being utilized by Agrovision as a disinfectant on industrial surfaces. Similarly, a second by-product generated during the production of tsipouro, i.e., the filter papers, is also being used for cleaning and disinfecting industrial surfaces. These filter papers contain alcohol since they come from the filtration of the spirit before the bottling process for the removal of various residues. Now, Agrovision is the sole beneficiary of the practice due to the produced quantity.

Type of Practice: Social Innovation

Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning, Fiscal & Financial, Info & Advisory

Region: Greece / Region of Central Macedonia

Year Implemented: 2021

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: Agrovision is currently the sole operator due to the quantity of feedstock produced.

Years of operation: 2

Status: Ongoing

Environmental Impacts

Reduction in the high cost applying the principles of circular economy, therefore, to re-use its by-products will not only result in the avoidance of waste materials, and production of new materials from secondary sources. This will not only save resources but develop new economically sustainable value chains within the market.

Social Impacts

The initial social impact resulted in producing indigenous supplies of sustainably source disinfectant to protect employees during pandemic. The development of the practice would have further social impacts if replicated in further sites.

Economic Impacts

The possibility to produce means for cleaning and disinfecting by the wastes and by-products of an industry will have as a result the reduction cost of their management by 3% and of the disinfectants purchase by 8%. Agrovision focuses on this logic. To be more specific, Agrovision uses by-products to produce the traditional Greek spirit. The wastes and by-products generated through its production ("head", filter papers) are being utilized to clean and disinfect the surfaces against Covid-19.

Replication Potential

Since the spirits' production is particularly widespread in Europe, it would be of high interest if this practice were disseminated as one profitable technique of wastes and by-products management against other valueless ones. Moreover, the cost of antiseptics and disinfectants has increased generally in Europe and not only in Greece. Therefore, the case of Agrovision may be an example

to be followed by other companies and in conclusion has a triple benefit: (a) reduction of the wastes and by-products management cost, (b) reduction of the cost of antiseptics and disinfectants purchase, (c) production of a new product which is possible to bring new incomes to the company. Moreover, Agrovision intends to participate in calls for proposals (e.g., innovation vouchers) for the further development and promotion of products against Covid-19 through innovative production processes. This method could also be adopted as a good strategy in public policies at the municipal or regional level.

Further Information

Website:

<https://agrovision-dk.gr/>

12: Restoration of non-compliant landfill sites in Larnaka District-Tersefanou

Problem Statement

The problem is to restore a non-compliant landfill site based in Cyprus.

Executive Summary

The practical objective of this practice is the restoration of the non-compliant landfill site in Tersefanou (Larnaka District), one of the 10 high risk (Category C non-compliant landfill) landfill sites in Cyprus. The Tersefanou landfill (LF) Tersefanou (LR08) has an area of 183 000 m² and a volume of 1.661.650 m³. From 1980 to 2010 municipal waste was disposed there.

Description

The practical objective of this practice is the restoration of the non-compliant landfill site in Tersefanou (Larnaka District), one of the 10 high risk (Category C non-compliant landfill) landfill sites in Cyprus. The Tersefanou landfill (LF) Tersefanou (LR08) has an area of 183 000 m²) and a volume of 1.661.650 m³. From 1980 to 2010 municipal waste was disposed there. The restoration works included the following:

Type of Practice: Other

Type of Instrument: Info & Advisory, Regulatory

Region: Cyprus

Year Implemented: 2019

The Collection of scattered lightweight waste and redeposit them on the landfill waste mass. The Rearrangement of the landfill surface so that the slope of the final upper surface of the restored landfill permits drainage of rainwater with the installation of a capping system. Measures were undertaken to prevent surface erosion (e.g., green growth) and construction works to prevent inflow of rainwater from the sides of the landfill. This has allowed for the collection and safe removal of biogas, the control and monitoring of the landfill during the aftercare period (controls for groundwater, biogas, subsidence, etc), for leachate emitted from sides or other points, measures for fires (e.g., fire zones), setting of the boundaries/ fencing and security as well as effective environmental control and monitoring programme during after care.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Communities / Public

Level of uptake: Residents benefited from the practice.

Years of operation: no information

Status: Project finished

Environmental Impacts

The restoration is considered a good practice due to the resulting positive environmental impacts which include:

- Reduction of the negative effects on air quality from the collection of the produced biogas and its disposal after appropriate treatment.
- Reduction in greenhouse gas emissions .
- Reduction of ground and surface water pollution.
- Reduced risks from the uncontrolled waste disposal, particularly hazardous waste.
- Reduction of land pollution.
- Reduction of fire incidents.

Social Impacts

Reducing hazards of emissions and fire for the local population. It has also enhanced the social acceptance of the facility locally , with the reduction of emissions and other pollutants directly from the facility.

Economic Impacts

The restoration of the non-sanitary landfill has preserved and has improved the quality of the urban environment and has increased the land value of the area.

Replication Potential

Where similar facilities and situations exist, this practice can demonstrate the how an existing poorly run facility can become an example of how to transform others.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.interregeurope.eu/good-practices/restoration-of-non-compliant-landfill-sites-in-larnaka-district-tersefanou>

2.3.4 Central Europe Cluster

Within ROBIN, partners based within the Central Europe Cluster, namely S2i and BPRO from Germany led the collection of good practices in that jurisdiction. This was focused on the territory of the Region of Baden-Württemberg, but in addition to Germany expanded more widely to include the following countries: Austria, Switzerland, Netherlands, Denmark and Poland. 7 good practices have been collected from the region. The majority of these were Fiscal and Financial instruments, along with some interesting regulatory instruments and a small number of Information and Advisory instruments and Voluntary instruments. The types of instruments are highlighted in Figure 33. The full list of good practices from the Central Europe Region is outlined in Table 11, and the best practices are included below.

Figure 33. Types of Good Practice in Central European Region

Table 11. Central Europe Good Practices

Good Practice Number	Good Practice Name	Jurisdiction, Country
1	Bioeconomy Innovation and Investment Program for Rural Areas (BIPL BW)	Baden-Württemberg, Germany
2	Green Start-up Ecosystem	Baden-Württemberg, Germany
3	"BayBioökonomie-Scale-Up"	Bavaria, Germany
4	National Procurement Database for Biobased Products	Regions of Zeeland, North Brabant, Overijssel and North Holland, Netherlands
5	Circular Biobased Delta	Delta Region, Netherlands
6	Netherlands Green Deal	Netherlands
7	Bioeconomy Congress Baden Wuerttemberg	Germany/Baden-Wuerttemberg

1: Bioeconomy Innovation and Investment Program for Rural Areas

Problem Statement

To maintain the competitiveness of Baden-Württemberg as a business location, innovations and investments in future technologies are to be promoted within the framework of the BIPL BW program.

Executive Summary

The Funding Program “Sustainable Bioeconomy as a Driver of Innovation for Rural Development” is being implemented as a measure (number 17) within the Baden-Württemberg Bioeconomy Strategy. The aim is to support the transfer of technology and knowledge in the field of sustainable production and use of resources from regional agriculture and forestry to enable a sustainable development of the region.

Description

Further development of the "post-EEG" (Erneubare-Energie Gesetz) biogas plant stock, sustainable, bio-based, and functionalized materials, fibers and textiles including composites. Establishment of lignin-based value chains, Innovations to close regional material cycles and sustainably supply nutrients and proteins from the regions.

The funding program is implemented under the leadership of the Ministry of Food, Rural Affairs and Consumer Protection of Baden-Württemberg and as a measure of the regional bioeconomy strategy, as detailed above. The strategy was published in 2019 and there was a consultation process in 2017/2018 involving around 500 stakeholders. The financial support of the regional Government was up to € 5.1 Million, as of June 2022.

Type of Practice: Financial Business Support

Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial, Info & Advisory, Networking

Region: Baden-Württemberg, Germany

Year Implemented: 2021

Implementation

Deployment setting: Rural

Stakeholder beneficiaries: SMEs

Level of uptake: 5 large projects funded.

Years of operation: 2

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Feasibility studies such as exploiting synergies between environment and economy for efficient biomass production for the bioeconomy and the potential analysis of commercial hemp in the context of a sustainable bioeconomy show the potential positive impacts from sustainable biomass supply chains.

Social Impacts

A new generation of bioenergy villages developed through the project's feasibility studies aims to develop long lasting sustainable communities.

Economic Impacts

Some of the projects being funded through the programme are focused on increasing the awareness of the bio-based products and improving market potential.

Replication Potential

No barriers to replication exist.

Further Information

Website:

<https://mlr.baden-wuerttemberg.de/de/unsere-themen/biooekonomie-und-innovation/foerderung-bipl-bw/>

Problem Statement

Regional start-up companies sometimes struggle to get their new bio-based innovation off the ground.

Executive Summary

Initiation of support to young companies (start-ups) in the orientation, planning and start-up phase.

Description

Baden-Württemberg supports start-ups in the life sciences and bioeconomy sectors with an extensive network of contacts. Around 20% of this network are bioeconomy actors. The applicants can receive initial advice via start-up and innovation vouchers. It is based on 1 to 1 consultation. Based on these initial consultation, further services related to accelerator phase (e.g., networking, mentoring, access to funding) might be offered. Proof of concept through demonstrator pilots are welcome; biorefinery concepts are accepted, as far as the focus lies in the material use. The initiative is a measure of the regional bioeconomy strategy and has become a focal point for the targeted development of start-ups and SMEs in the domain of bioeconomy.

Type of Practice: Financial Business Support

Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning, Info & Advisory

Region: Baden-Württemberg, Germany

Year Implemented: 2021

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Other

Level of uptake: Since the start in BÖ thematic initiative (that is part of the bioeconomic start-up ecosystem), has 22 participants (Feb. 2022)

Years of operation: 2

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Any start-up focused on circular bioeconomy should contribute to a positive environmental impact. Supply chains will develop within these new firms that will replace fossil fuel-based supply chains as well as larger environmental benefits of the reduced use of fossil based inputs.

Social Impacts

With the resulting environmental benefits from the practice, it is likely to have positive social impacts and innovation also at an individual and community level.

Economic Impacts

Further development of the bioeconomy sector is expected increase in bio-based innovation, so this is expected to drive larger turnover.

Replication Potential

It has potential to be transferred to other regions, as far as the start-up bioeconomy-related ecosystem is sufficiently established. As there are 4 different building blocks of the ecosystem, the ones suitable for transfer should be assessed case by case.

Further Information

Websites:

<https://www.bio-pro.de/projekte/bereich-biooekonomie/start-boe>

<https://www.startupbw.de/>

Problem Statement

There is a need to increase the number of biorefineries and production plants based in biological raw materials in Bavaria.

Executive Summary

BayBioökonomie-Scale-Up is an initiative aimed at supporting the scale up of biorefineries in Bavaria.

Description

Within the bioeconomy strategy Future Bioeconomy Bavaria, the Bavarian state government is paving the way to a sustainable and ecologically responsible as well as socially just and thus future-oriented way of life and business in Bavaria. One part of the extensive package of measures is the "BayBioökonomie-Scale-Up" funding program.

Type of Practice: Financial Business Support
Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial, Networking
Region: Bavaria, Germany
Year Implemented: 2022

This measure is part of the implementation of the Bavaria’s Bioeconomy Strategy. It is a funding programme addressed to innovative polymers based on sustainable raw materials, with a 2-stage application form (April and June 2022). The guidelines were reformulated in Sept. 2022 and in Nov. 2022 was scheduled to have a second call. It funds the build-up of bioeconomy related production plants (industrial bioeconomy) based on raw materials and with a minimum TRL of 8. The plants developed should have a positive environmental and climate impact, and the raw materials should be at least 60% from biological sources (residue and waste materials not included).

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple
Stakeholder beneficiaries: SMEs
Level of uptake: Not known to date.
Years of operation: 1
Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Eligible projects should have a positive environmental and climate impact.

Social Impacts

The funded programmes are expected to have positive social effects as they are associated with bioeconomy startups and will result in job creation, while some of the topics are also consumer-focused.

Economic Impacts

Strengthening the bioeconomy sector in Bavaria, will develop not only a resilient sustainable sector, but will also increase the competitiveness of regional companies, and enhance the innovation of the region.

Replication Potential

Not known, but dependent on the financial resources available and territorial specificities of the region/country it can be transferred to regions with available biological raw materials to develop biorefineries.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.stmwi.bayern.de/foerderungen/biooekonomie-scale-up/>

4: National Procurement Database for Biobased Products

Problem Statement

Companies and local governments often face challenges in identifying which bio-based materials are on the market, and what is the benefit from these materials.

Executive Summary

Database provides an overview of the different BBPs which are produced in NL and currently available on the market and provides purchasers from governments and companies a tool to meet sustainability targets in their tenders.

Description

Governments are the largest purchasers in the Netherlands. The central government has determined that the procurement policy of national, provincial, and municipal governments must become significantly more sustainable. Research among government buyers shows that they see the use of bio-based products as an important opportunity to achieve these sustainability goals.

However, they indicate that the realization is made more difficult by the lack of a good overview of available products and suppliers. To meet this need, the provinces of Zeeland, Overijssel, North Brabant and North Holland have taken the initiative to set up a National Procurement Database for Biobased Products.

Type of Practice: Public Procurement

Type of Instrument: Voluntary Instruments, Financial and Fiscal Instruments, Networking, Collaboration and Joint Planning, Information and Advisory Instruments

Region: NL (Zeeland, North Brabant, Overijssel and North Holland)

The Circular Biobased Delta Foundation is responsible for project implementation on behalf of the provinces. The Centre of Expertise Biobased Economy is the responsible knowledge partner and Performis BV (publisher of www.agro-chemie.nl) is responsible as media partner for the construction, design, and continuity of the database. Approximately 500 companies have been contacted to add their bio-based products. The database will be accessible to everyone after going live. So, for all buyers from governments, companies, and organizations, and for the general public. The database and products are broken down by sector including packaging, food and catering and healthcare. The new database answers many questions from buyers. When is a product bio-based? What is it made of then? What offer is there in the specific purchasing categories? How much more

sustainable are these products than their fossil alternatives? How can I compare different products and materials on sustainability characteristics? Public and corporate procurement officers can use the new database as a tool to meet sustainability targets in their tenders. Suppliers can enter their bio-based products into the new database free of charge.

In addition to the actual database, a digital environment will be set up where buyers can find background information about, for example, developments in biobased applications and the process of sustainable purchasing.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: 3 regions participating, 500 companies contacted to upload their practices.

Years of operation: 1

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

The tool enables public bodies, industry, and the public to understand what biobased alternative options are available in different product categories. These can then be procured by the customer. It also allows them to understand the bio-based content of these materials, and the sustainability benefit associated with the different bio-based materials.

Social Impacts

Increases awareness and potential access to bio-based materials for public bodies, industries and the public. Growing markets for local suppliers of bio-based products can also help to create local jobs.

Economic Impacts

The tool helps to stimulate the market for new bio-based products. It supports innovative companies developing bio-based solutions to exhibit their offerings.

Replication Potential

Is an initiative of three regions, Zeeland, North Brabant, Overijssel and North Holland, but is already planned to spread between regions.

Further Information

Website:

<https://biobasedinkopen.nl/>

Problem Statement

Understanding how the region can make a substantial contribution to securing the targets laid down in the Dutch Climate Agreement and Climate Act

Executive Summary

The Biobased Delta has laid out a 10-year plan that aims to reduce CO₂ emissions in the Dutch Delta region by 10 Mt/a by 2030.

Description

The plan comprises a wide portfolio of projects, ranging from production of new biomass-based chemicals to plastics recycling routes. This study, commissioned by Circular Biobased Delta and with funding from the three provinces of Zeeland, Noord-Brabant and Zuid-Holland, is the first to quantify the respective contributions of the individual projects to overall CO₂ emissions reduction. To this end the CO₂ emissions embodied in each project were compared with those associated with current production methods. We conclude that these projects will together achieve a total reduction of 5.4 Mt CO₂-eq./a in 2030. We also estimate the investments required to implement the projects as well as likely investment schedules and the emission cuts ultimately achieved. This study makes the reduction potential and relative importance of each of the constituent projects tangible and will allow Circular Biobased Delta as well as policymakers to take targeted follow-up action: practical implementation of plans that are already sufficiently concrete, fleshing out those that are still in their infancy and materialization of the

Type of Practice: Regulatory
Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration and Joint Planning Model, Fiscal and Financial Model
Region: Dutch Delta region
Year Implemented: 2021

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple
Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple
Level of uptake: Many projects are already operational
Years of operation: 2
Status: Active

additional projects that will be needed to secure the first of the envisaged targets: 10 Mt/a CO₂ reduction in 2030.

Environmental Impacts

Developing scalable projects with projection on how these can deliver emissions reductions for the regions is estimated to deliver a reduction of 5.4 Mt CO₂-eq./a in 2030 from a Dutch Delta region target of 10 Mt/a by 2030.

Social Impacts

Increases opportunities to produce products in a local setting and for local companies to expand and create new jobs. Can create new sustainable products for the consumer market.

Economic Impacts

The practice reduce imports of products by creating locally based supply chains. Work has allowed the region to understand the economic considerations for implementation of these initiatives and to consider which other projects should be initiated to help to further the targets.

Replication Potential

It is a first of its kind region, so replication has not happened yet. However, it is a collaboration of multiple regions and with success there is replication potential to other regions.

Further Information

Website:

<https://cedelft.eu/publications/co2-reduction-with-the-circular-biobased-delta/>

6: Bioeconomy Congress

Problem Statement

The problem addressed is the need to increase the information exchange among several stakeholders in rural, industrial, and urban areas in the topic of bioeconomy, as well as increasing the international exchange.

Executive Summary

In the congress important topics regarding bioeconomy are addressed by information sessions, discussion panels, workshops, excursions, and seminars including real-life practices.

Description

The international “Bioeconomy Congress Baden-Württemberg” was first established as part of the Baden-Württemberg Bioeconomy research programme initiated by the Ministry of Science, Research, and the Arts. It was first organised in 2014. It currently continues with the aim to promote networking and cooperation among several actors, and knowledge exchange about researcher, businesses and policymakers, with local and regional activities. The societal engagement is a key aspect of the initiative.

Type of Practice: Networking

Type of Instrument: Information & Advisory Instrument, Networking, Collaboration and Joint Planning Model,

Region: Baden-Württemberg, Germany

During the congress important topics regarding bioeconomy are addressed by information sessions, discussion panels, workshops, excursions, and seminars including real-life practices. The topics include among others primary production, industry, sustainability, environmental and climate protection, and waste management. The congress takes place every two-years. In year 2022 the fourth edition took place focusing on the contributions of the bioeconomy to the European Green Deal.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: The congress has led to the further development of the region's bioeconomy. Over 300 participate in the most recent congress.

Years of operation: 4

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Discussion of status of the state strategy for a sustainable bioeconomy and its potential for achieving the goals of the European Green Deal and the state's climate protection goals.

Social Impacts

The Bioeconomy Congress Baden-Württemberg has been successful in increasing the awareness on bioeconomy best-practices, raising trust of several stakeholders, and engaging them through the biannual congress as well as through social engagement.

Economic Impacts

The participation of companies working in the bioeconomy and their contributions are highlighted and new collaborations are developed

Replication Potential

The practice can be replicated by other regions to bring together different types of stakeholders. It could also be implemented at several levels such as districts, municipalities, etc.

For example, a similar case is the International Bioeconomy Conference organised annually in the federal State of Saxony-Anhalt, that will celebrate its 11th edition in 2023.

Further Information

Website:

<https://biooekonomie.baden-wuerttemberg.de/,Len/Bioeconomycongress>

7: Netherlands Green Deal

Problem Statement

In developing new and sustainable innovations, non-financial roadblocks often appear as barriers to implementation of the new business model or value chain.

Executive Summary

Taking steps towards sustainability, sometimes barriers are encountered. The Dutch Government wants to help to overcome these barriers by joining an initiative in a Green Deal agreement. In this way, the Green Deal approach aids the implementation of sustainable initiatives and accelerates the transition to a sustainable economy. So far, 235 Green Deals were closed in the Netherlands. The Green Deal approach is an accessible way for organizations, local and regional government, and interest groups to work with the Central Government on green growth and social issues. It is a joint initiative by the Dutch Ministries of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, Infrastructure and Water Management, the Interior and Kingdom Relations, and Agriculture, Nature, and Food Quality. The Netherlands Enterprise Agency supports the ministries with the implementation of the Green Deals.

Description

To help overcome non-financial roadblocks inhibiting the development of sustainable innovations the Dutch ministries implemented the Green Deal programme in 2011. A signed Green Deal is a mutual agreement or covenant under private law between a coalition of companies, civil society organizations and local and regional government. The deal defines the initiative, the actions, and the input by participants as clearly as possible. The deals last on average about 2 to 3 years. A deal ends when all agreements are fulfilled, and the goals are achieved. Green Deals preferably inspire others and pave the way for the next initiatives. In this way, the Green Deals ensure broad follow-up and impact on the Dutch society.

Type of Practice: Regulatory

Type of Instrument: Regulatory model, Networking, Collaboration and Joint Planning Model, Fiscal and Financial Model

Region: Netherlands

Year Implemented: 2011

The central themes are energy, food, water, resources, biodiversity, mobility, bio-based economy, climate, and construction. Deals can focus on one theme but can cover multiple themes as well. A Green Deal can be an international cooperation, so interested parties from abroad can join a deal too. The official agreement will be drafted in Dutch, but an English version will be made available too.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: 235 green deals completed consisting of 1891 participating parties.

Years of operation: 12

Status: Yes

Environmental Impacts

To be accepted within the green deal programme, the business idea must demonstrate some environmental benefits - case studies of examples agreed under the green deal initiative e.g., the phosphate value chain agreement.

Social Impacts

The development of agreed initiatives represents new value chains and business models which can result in job creation. In addition, the programme takes a collaborative approach bring in the voices of different stakeholders.

Economic Impacts

The development of agreed initiatives represents new value chains and business models which typically result in new economic opportunities.

Replication Potential

No foreseen barrier to implementation in other regions, as the practice details would be applicable.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.greendeals.nl/english>

2.3.5 Eastern Europe Cluster

Within ROBIN, partners based within the Eastern Europe Custer, namely PEDAL and ZSK from Slovakia led the collection of good practices in that jurisdiction. This was focused on the territory of the Regional of Zilina, Slovakia, but in addition to Slovakia expanded more widely to include the following countries: Czech Republic, Hungary, Ukraine, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, and Moldova. 8 good practices have been collected from the region. The majority of these were Fiscal and Financial instruments, with a small number of Networking, Collaboration and Joint Planning instruments and Information and Advisory instruments as well as one Regulatory instrument. The type of instruments is shown in Figure 34 below. The full list of good practices from the Eastern Europe Region is outlined in Table 12, and the best practices from the region are included below.

Figure 34. Types of Good Practice in Eastern Europe Region

Table 12: Eastern Europe Good Practices

Good Practice Number	Good Practice Name	Jurisdiction, Country
1	The Greening Self-Assessment Tool for SME	Republic of Moldova
2	Landscape Recovery Program of the Košice region	Slovakia / Košice
3	Environmental approaches in Haňovice	Czech Republic / Olomouc region
4	Local suppliers providing food to regional schools and other types of facilities	Banská Bystrica Self-governing region, Slovakia
5	Regional municipal biomass project on Poľana	Banská Bystrica Self-governing region, Slovakia
6	Sustainable development at local level	Different regions in the Czech Republic
7	Lithuanian Bioeconomy Development Feasibility Study	Lithuania
8	National Reform Programme Hungary 2022 - Green Business Development	Hungary

1: The Greening Self-Assessment Tool for SME

Problem Statement

To support and develop entrepreneurial capacities of SMEs, adopting production processes and services to implement greening practices.

Executive Summary

In the frame of the National SMEs Greening Program, implemented by ODIMM - the Organisation for the Development of the SME Sector in the Republic of Moldova - a set of tools was developed with the purpose to promote, support, and develop entrepreneurial capacities of SMEs, adopting production processes and services to implement greening practices.

Description

The tool was developed by ODIMM at a cost of €5,000 covered by OECD in close consultation with Clean Technology Centre from Ireland which provided recommendations and shared their experience of a similar toolkit.

The Greening Self-Assessment Toolkit provides the scoring system for interested SMEs on 4 greening topics for the enterprise:

- Water management.
- Waste management.
- Energy efficiency.
- Greening management systems.

The purpose of the questionnaire is to conduct an overall analysis of the level of resource efficiency in the company. This tool gives a quick and useful analysis on what the company should do to grow its business more efficiently and optimize production costs.

Type of Practice: Financial Business Support

Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial, Info & advisory, voluntary

Region: Republic of Moldova

Year Implemented: 2020

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: SMEs

Level of uptake: No Data available

Years of operation: 3

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Improving environmental indicators and protecting the environment. Thanks to this tool, environmental targeting will evolve in the future, on which greening measures will be taken, which will naturally lead to the reduction of CO₂ emissions, waste recycling, efficient management of water resources, and the implementation of energy efficiency measures.

Social Impacts

SMEs will benefit from financial support in the form of a grant for the implementation of greening actions regarding the efficient use of resources, the application of sustainable production and consumption models, the introduction of eco-innovations in technological processes, waste reduction and management, pollution prevention and water resource management, etc.

Economic Impacts

Focusing on good business greening practices and activities that will reduce the impact of business on the environment. The SME will benefit from informative materials, consultancy, support services and training regarding the identification of solutions and the adoption of concrete actions to green the processes of production and provision of services, which will allow the increase of the company's potential to obtain a higher share on markets.

Replication Potential

No foreseen barrier to implementation in other regions, as the practice details would be applicable.

Further Information

Website:

<https://odimm.md/ro/ecoimm>

2: Landscape Recovery Program of the Košice region

Problem Statement

A programme aimed at ensuring the optimal use of land in response to the manifestations of climate change in the region.

Executive Summary

The plans of the 6 Water Councils that have been created in Košice Region within the Landscape Recovery Program 2021-2030 of individual regions included topics for comprehensive solutions for the WEF (water, energy, food) approach, like climate change effects on water supply; soil fertility; extreme heat and the occurrence of natural disasters.

Description

Established 6 Water councils have a total of 120 members (representatives of local government, regional authority, district authorities, agriculturists, activists, volunteers, forest wardens, woodlanders). Water councils aim to change the approach to the management of forest and agricultural land, as well as urban land, and to enable the establishment of water retention measures so that a substantial part of rainwater can be retained in the countryside.

Through the implementation of these measures, the region, in cooperation with partners, wants to contribute to the renewal of biodiversity processes, the increase of soil fertility, the increase of water resources and the improvement of the climate. In terms of practical implementation Water Councils were divided into 6 separate territories that work on plans for their own territories.

The Košice Region's challenge is to respond flexibly to climate change by optimally using the countryside. The most effective solution is the ecosystem restoration of water supply in the damaged and dehydrated landscape, retaining rainwater, slowing down its drainage and infiltration, consequently preventing floods. Integrated water and land-use management will provide adequate water supply and resilience for people, nature, and food security.

Type of Practice: Other

Type of Instrument: Information, education, and cooperation among several local actors with the aim to ensure formation of local communities, coordination.

Region: Slovakia / Košice

Year Implemented: 2019

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Communities / Public

Level of uptake: No Data

Years of operation: 4

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

One of the goals is to slow down the runoff of rainwater from runoff spots, to reduce the drift of waste, soil, and nutrients from the area. Retained rainwater will contribute to the restoration of biodiversity process, increasing soil fertility, creation of water resources and the recovery of the climate.

Social Impacts

Avoiding damage and health risks due to the impacts of climate change (torrential rain, prolonged drought) Maintaining economic activity in the region (e.g. agriculture).

Economic Impacts

Prevent the negative effects of climate change (drought) on business activities in agriculture, forestry, etc.

Replication Potential

It can be replicated on two levels the first is an approach to community building like the establishment of water councils and the general measures implemented, with the solution is the ecosystem restoration of water supply.

Further Information

Website:

https://web.vucke.sk/files/sk/kompetencie/regionalny-rozvoj/program-obnovy-krajiny/plan_vodnych_rad.pdf

3: Environmental approaches in Haňovice

Problem Statement

In the small village of Haňovice na Hané, thanks to cooperation with the local agricultural cooperative and the town of Litovel, it was possible to reduce the amount of energy consumed, prevent groundwater pollution, use renewable energy sources and create dozens of new jobs.

Executive Summary

Thanks to the exceptional cooperation with local businesses and the town of Litovel, large projects have been implemented in the small territory of the municipality, saving energy, and protecting the environment. These are a set of activities that make the most of renewable energy sources. The project will create new jobs.

Description

The biggest project in the village, which is also unique in the Czech Republic, is the construction of a 5 ha greenhouse for growing vegetables - mainly tomatoes. Production is expected to cover around 2-3 % of domestic consumption. Electricity and heat from the cooperative biogas plant will be used to operate the greenhouses. Rainwater from the roofs of the greenhouses and cooperative buildings will be used primarily for watering. The greenhouses will create between 30 and 35 new jobs for the municipality.

In 2012, the biogas station was at the beginning of the activity, which in recent years has improved the environment and reduced the costs of the village and businesses in the village. This was built in the village by a local agricultural cooperative. The energy produced in the biogas station is used not only for the premises of the cooperative or the planned hall to produce wires for 3D printers, but also in the buildings of the municipality. The heat pipe from the biogas station heats the premises of the cultural centre, the municipal office, the library, the hairdresser and other social rooms. The largest ever project in the village, which is also unique by the standards of the entire Czech Republic, is currently nearing completion. The local agricultural cooperative in the village is building greenhouses and production should cover roughly 2-3% of domestic market consumption. Electricity and heat from the biogas station will be used to operate the greenhouses.

Type of Practice: Social Innovation

Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning

Region: Czech Republic / Olomouc region

Year Implemented: 2017

Implementation

Deployment setting: Rural

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: Unknown to date, however there is large cross community cooperation across the various projects.

Years of operation: 5

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Electricity and heat from the biogas plant will be used to operate the greenhouses. Primarily rainwater from the roofs of the greenhouses and the cooperative buildings will be used for watering.

Social Impacts

The greenhouses created 30 to 35 new jobs for the municipality as well as the positive social impacts of locally produced produce and energy. The various projects will also strengthen a sense of community ownership and responsibility.

Economic Impacts

Immediate impacts will result in the saving on energy costs as the municipality is gradually replacing the old lamps on public lighting and in the cultural centre with energy-saving LED lamps etc as cost savings in self-generated energy.

Replication Potential

The model depends on close collaboration with the agricultural cooperative and municipality but this can be achieved in other regions.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.eon.cz/energy-globe/minule-rocniky/pristupy-k-zivotnimu-prostredi-v-hanovicich/>

4: Local suppliers providing food to regional schools and other types of facilities

Problem Statement

Banská Bystrica regions belongs to the least developed regions in Slovakia. The aim is to support local food producers, as well as ensure healthy food for the region's facilities and support a more sustainable sources by supporting short supply chains.

Executive Summary

The aim of the initiative is to prioritise locally sourced food. To ensure compliance with all regulations (especially public procurement act), food can be bought only from suppliers that are registered social enterprises under the Social Economy Act. The region therefore provided assistance in setting up a social enterprise.

Description

Based on an open call, local suppliers (registered social enterprises under the Social Economy Act), can participate in a tender. The successful farmers will deliver their products to 48 organisations, the possible volume of deliveries throughout the year is 4,440 tonnes of food and the expected value of the contracts could reach up to €3.53 million per year in the future.

Type of Practice: Public Procurement

Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial, Networking

Region: Slovakia / Banská Bystrica Self-governing region

Year Implemented: 2018

Implementation

Deployment setting: Rural

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: No data available

Years of operation: 5

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Support short and local value chain. Supporting sustainable approaches in agriculture.

Social Impacts

Ensuring food security. Creating job opportunities in one of the least advanced regions, including disadvantaged groups

Economic Impacts

Supporting local producers - the expected value of the contracts could reach up to €3.53 million per year in the future.

Replication Potential

No barrier to replication is foreseen.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.bbsk.sk/vyzva>

5: Regional municipal biomass project on Poľana

Problem Statement

A unique example of the joint action of several local governments in order to strengthen their own energy self-sufficiency.

Executive Summary

Joint project of 8 mountain villages around Banská. Bystrica provides local heat production from waste biomass to cover the energy needs of 32 municipal buildings. It is a collaboration of municipalities with strong support of an NGO - The project was strongly supported by an NGO CEPA and Friends of the Earth.

Description

The specific goals of the project are to reduce expenditures for heating at public buildings and to use local resources for communal development, Modernisation of heating plants in 9 villages, reduction of CO2 emissions (the total CO2 emissions will be reduced by approximately 8.5 thousand tons in 10 years) and to encourage other rural regions with similar renewable energy potential to use their local resources. With the main goal to increase the level of economic self-sufficiency at rural communities through the utilisation of local biomass in public buildings.

The project covers the entire chain from fuel preparation, storage, distribution to heat production in 15 modernized boiler rooms (3.2 MW), under the full control of local governments. The project was initiated by Friends of the Earth-CEPA and its preparation took almost 10 years. The result is the removal of coal from the fuel mix of municipalities, large annual savings in carbon emissions, heat and municipal finances, a substantial increase in hygiene conditions in buildings and air quality in municipalities and the stabilization of local economies. This is a unique example of the joint action of several local governments to strengthen their own energy self-sufficiency.

Type of Practice: Other

Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning

Region: Slovakia / Banská Bystrica Self-governing region

Year Implemented: 2003

Implementation

Deployment setting: Mountainous/upland

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: Coming together of 8 villages to increase energy independence

Years of operation: 20

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Removal of coal from the fuel mix of municipalities, large annual savings in carbon emissions - (the total CO₂ emissions should have been reduced by approximately 8.5 thousand tons in 10 years), air quality in municipalities.

Social Impacts

To increase the level of economic self-sufficiency of rural communities through the utilisation of local biomass in public buildings, a substantial increase in hygiene conditions in buildings.

Economic Impacts

To reduce expenditures for heating at public buildings and to use local resources for communal development, use of huge potential of local renewable resources.

Replication Potential

The mode can be replicated - the projects aim is to encourage other rural regions with similar renewable energy potential to use their local resources.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.inforse.org/europe/fae/Biomass%20for%20Polana%20region.htm>

6: Sustainable development at local level

Problem Statement

Education focused on the topics of how to start local sustainable development in practice, which will provide residents and government with the knowledge needed to make changes in business and lifestyle that would lead them to sustainability.

Executive Summary

The Charles University Environment Centre is (through a project) creating a system of lifelong learning to support people's skills and capacities for sustainable development in the regions of the Czech Republic, through the National Network of Local Action Groups.

Description

The project is connecting a well working network of Local Action Groups (created according to the LEADER method) with a academia. This approach is based on the belief that the current problems facing the regions cannot be solved only "from the table" (albeit with a scientific basis); practice alone will not provide the solution, because in many ways the basic conditions are changing, new stimuli and risks are emerging. That is why the Charles University as the coordinator wants to link different perspectives and approaches - creating a collaborative network to promote sustainable development based on local resources and knowledge.

Type of Practice: Educational

Type of Instrument: Info & Advisory, Networking, Voluntary

Region: Different regions in the Czech Republic

Year Implemented: 2019

Seminars held aimed at Local action groups and Mayors will cover the areas of:

- Waste & Carbon Free Czech Republic.
- Opportunities and barriers to the development of rural areas and small towns in the Czech Republic.
- The Czech Republic – a sustainably beautiful country.
- New economic opportunities within a sustainable remit and a sustainable business
- Climatically safe Czech Republic and opportunities for mitigation.
- Local specifics as an opportunity for sustainable development.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Rural

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: unknown

Years of operation: 4

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Education on transition towards circular economy, decarbonization, adaptation to climate changes, biodiversity, sustainable businesses can increase the action potential of local leaders.

Social Impacts

Contributing to improving life conditions in (remote) regions of the country where development opportunities are still limited or based on environmentally and/or socially unfavourable practices, supporting participatory approaches, community building, recognizing role of culture and education, supporting collaboration of professionals from different disciplines to shape public space, dialogue and community planning.

Economic Impacts

Creating new sustainable economic opportunities, Energy production at local level, new opportunities in construction, transport, etc., Development of labour market, entrepreneurship and community on the local level, collaborative networks, support small businesses.

Replication Potential

The LEADER approach is recognized within EU. The nation-wide network of Local Action Groups has a strong potential for collaboration, sharing good practices.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.nsmascr.cz/pro-mas/vzdelavani-pro-mas-1/mistni-udrzitelny-rozvoj-v-praxi-mas/>.

<https://rce.czp.cuni.cz/index.php/en/projects/112-sustainable-development-at-local-level-linking-theory-and-practice>

7: Lithuanian Bioeconomy Development Feasibility Study

Problem Statement

To increase the use of biomass for producing higher value, added products, to manage biowaste more efficiently.

Executive Summary

Recommendations on the development of bioeconomy in Lithuania and innovation encouraging measures in this sector by forming a plan of the proposed measures.

Description

The purpose of this Study is to evaluate the state and the potential of bioeconomy in Lithuania, to consider the best practices of the EU Member States and Norway and to present the conclusions and recommendations for the development of bioeconomy in Lithuania and the innovation encouraging measures in this sector, to identify the areas of bioeconomy where the Lithuania has the greatest potential.

Since 2010, Lithuania has been among leaders of bioeconomy growth in EU in all biomass production and fully bio-based manufacturing sectors – the first in terms of the growth of the paper sector, the third – in terms of the growth of fisheries, the fourth – in terms of the growth of the agricultural sector, manufacture of beverages and tobacco and manufacture of wood products (except for the furniture production) and the fifth – in terms of the growth of forestry and logging subsector.

The study finds that future Lithuanian bioeconomy strategy should give the priority to food security, combine food security with sustainable use of renewable resources for industrial purposes and assurance of environmental protection, apply the cascading principle in the biomass value chain,

Type of Practice: Other

Typology of Practice: Info & Advisory

Region: Lithuania

Year Implemented: 2017

Implementation

Deployment setting: Rural

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Public Bodies

Level of uptake: Unknown as this is a feasibility study of the overall bioeconomy.

Years of operation: 6

Status: Active

first of all using biomass in the production of the highest value-added products and maximise recycling and reuse and minimise waste.

Environmental Impacts

To combine food security with sustainable use of renewable resources for industrial purposes and assurance of environmental protection.

Social Impacts

Cross-sectoral relationships and interactions (between the biomass-producing sector and the sector transforming it into value-added products).

Economic Impacts

Development of business competencies (professional advisory, training, business development assistance services for enterprises); improving investment in climate, investment dissemination of good practice (by way of business missions, business contact fairs, information and contact networks).

Replication Potential

No unforeseen barriers to replication in other regions.

Further Information

Website:

[https://eimin.lrv.lt/uploads/eimin/documents/files/Inovacijos/bioekonomikos%20studija/Lithuanian%20Bioeconomy%20Study_EN\(1\).pdf](https://eimin.lrv.lt/uploads/eimin/documents/files/Inovacijos/bioekonomikos%20studija/Lithuanian%20Bioeconomy%20Study_EN(1).pdf)

8: National Reform Programme of Hungary 2022

Problem Statement

Provide financial support to the development of Hungarian SMEs with high growth potential and related to the green economy.

Executive Summary

The Green National Champions Programme aims to financially support the development of those Hungarian SMEs with high growth potential, operating in an environmental-conscious way and producing goods related to the green economy.

Description

The first phase was handled during the second half of 2020. Manufacturing SMEs were able to apply for 4 topics:

1. producing an energy efficiency product, e.g., solar panel system, boiler system (including bio-mass boilers), heat pumps and heat recovery systems, building boundary structures, door and window structures, lighting systems, and shading structures
2. producing a product related to water efficiency, e.g., water-saving tools and technologies, water retention, and/or recycling equipment.
3. producing a product related to electro-mobility
4. producing a product from secondary raw materials.

Type of Practice: Financial Business Support
Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial, Regulatory
Region: Hungary
Year Implemented: 2020

The second phase focused on the SMEs which are affected by the SUP directive (Single Use Plastics Directive) or those manufacturing substitute products instead of single-use plastic.

The third phase is in progress and contains all topics (a mix of 1st and 2nd phases). Only companies with a so-called pre-qualification certificate issued by IFKA - proving that they could contribute to the development of the Hungarian green economy - can apply for the dedicated financial source of the given calls.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: SMEs

Level of uptake: No data available

Years of operation: 3

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Reducing emissions, increasing energy efficiency, and recycling & reuse (Industrial) waste and by-products.

Social Impacts

The programme includes a creation of a green manufacturer and service catalogue, making sustainable and environmentally friendly products competitive and promoting clean technologies and industrial ecology within its social remit.

Economic Impacts

Targeted and comprehensive development of the domestic green economy, facilitating the production of goods by Hungarian companies (import substitution), and strengthening the development capacity, innovation, and digital performance of SMEs are outlined within the programme.

Replication Potential

It has potential, but transferability of the programme requires strong support from national / regional government towards development of the bioeconomy.

Further Information

Website: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/nrp_2022_hu-magyar_en.pdf

2.3.6 Mediterranean Cluster

Within ROBIN, partners based within the Mediterranean Europe Custer, namely CTA and CAG from Spain led the collection of good practices in that jurisdiction. This was focused on the territory of the Region of Andalusia, but in addition to Spain expanded more widely to include the following countries; Portugal, Italy and Malta. 12 good practices have been collected from the region. Compared to some other regions the number of Fiscal and Financial instrument examples was low, with a high level of “other” examples, mainly focusing on value chain innovation. In addition, there were examples of Information and Advisory instruments, Regulatory instruments and Networking, Collaboration, and Joint Planning instruments. The type of instruments is shown in Figure 35 below. The full list of good practices from the Mediterranean Region is outlined in Table 13, and the best practices from the region are included below.

Figure 35. Types of Good Practice in Mediterranean Region

Table 13. Mediterranean Good Practices

Good Practice Number	Good Practice Name	Jurisdiction, Country
1	"Bioeconomy Technical Platform" Call	Piemonte, Italy
2	BIOVOICES Video Shorts in social media	Italy
3	Interactive map Atresbio	Andalusia, Spain
4	Novamont@school	Italy
5	Blue Bio Value	Portugal
6	Greenhouse soil bio solarisation in horticulture	Andalusia, Almeria, Spain
7	Green manures and cover crops in field and horticultural crops	Andalusia, Almeria, Spain
8	Use of waste to promote biological control and biodiversity	Andalusia, Almeria, Spain
9	Use of alternative materials for plastic staking elements	Andalusia, Almeria, Spain
10	Use of alternative materials for plastic mulching films	Andalusia, Almeria, Spain
11	Use of treated sewage sludge in the agricultural sector	Andalusia, Spain
12	Ban on single use carrier bags	Italy

1: "Bioeconomy Technical Platform" Call

Problem Statement

Action to support stakeholders in their development of bioeconomy related processes.

Executive Summary

The initiative is to be traced back to the scheme already used for the previous Technological Platforms of the Piedmont Region. It's a call aimed to finance industrial research projects and / or experimental development projects.

Description

Industrial research projects and / or experimental development projects that the Piedmont Region intends to finance with the "Bioeconomy Technological Platform" call, in the form of a contribution to expenditure, must also promote the development of innovative solutions with the following priority objectives:

support industrial research and innovation in technologies, encourage collaboration between companies and the research system for the development of projects that respond to the needs of innovation and competitiveness in the so-called "Bioeconomy" sector where possible, favour the participation of subjects of heterogeneous sectorial origin in order to guarantee, in addition to a response to strengthening research and innovation in their respective fields, the integration of the themes aimed at the realization of projects relating to the CIRCULAR ECONOMY facilitate the exchange of knowledge and skills between companies, research organizations and encourage the creation of aggregations favour the repercussions on the territory also in terms of employment growth and the competitiveness of the Piedmontese production system increase the training of new

Type of Practice: Financial Support System.

Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial

Region: Piemonte (Italia)

Year Implemented: 2018

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: No data

Years of operation: 1

Status: Call Closed

industrial researchers in the fields of the so-called Bioeconomy, through the experimentation of apprenticeship projects in higher education and research.

Environmental Impacts

Within the circular bioeconomy aspect, it aims to optimise the use of natural and water resources, of the reuse of by-products, of the reduction of the environmental impact in the agro-food industry, conversion of non-food biomass and native livestock manure to produce chemicals, biofuels, and bioplastics.

Social Impacts

Facilitate the exchange of knowledge and skills between companies, research organizations and encourage the creation of aggregations, favour the repercussions on the territory also in terms of employment growth and the competitiveness of the Piedmontese production system, increase the training of new industrial researchers in the fields of the so-called Bioeconomy, through the experimentation of apprenticeship projects in higher education and research.

Economic Impacts

Support industrial research and innovation in technologies, encourage collaboration between companies and the research system for the development of projects that respond to the needs of innovation and competitiveness in the so-called "Bioeconomy" sector, where possible, favour the participation of subjects of heterogeneous sectorial origin in order to guarantee, in addition to a response to strengthening research and innovation in their respective fields, the integration of the themes aimed at the realization of projects relating to the circular bioeconomy.

Replication Potential

This financing scheme has been developed for other sectors in the region as it has been already used for the previous Technological Platforms of the Piedmont Region.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.regione.piemonte.it/web/temi/fondi-progetti-europei/fondo-europeo-sviluppo-regionale-fesr/programmazione-2014-2020/piattaforma-tecnologica-bioeconomia#>

2: Biovoices - Video shorts in social media

Problem Statement

Bioeconomy, despite its many applications, has not yet entered the public consciousness as an exciting solution to address societal challenges. Raising overall awareness and understanding of the societal, economic, and environmental impacts of bio-based products and processes and the bioeconomy at large is of utmost importance for the future development of a smart, sustainable, and inclusive bioeconomy and to educate to a more sustainable consumption and lifestyle patterns.

Executive Summary

BIOVOICES (<https://www.biovoices.eu/>) and Transition2Bio (<https://www.transition2bio.eu/>), projects experimented successfully the engagement of famous people to multiply the educational effect, by leveraging existing trusted relations they have with their followers. These people were the centre of a communication campaign launched through social media.

Description

The projects involved two famous Italian TV presenters, already known as sensitive to environmental issues: Syusy Blady and her daughter Zoe. Their social media channels reach 750.000 followers, and they are well-known as unconventional travellers in primary TV formats.

The idea was to show and explain, in a very simple and inspirational way, the circular bioeconomy in everyday life. In 10 video shorts called “Lo sai che?” (Do you know that?), Syusy and Zoe, engage a funny competition to show one each other, in a playful banter, who knows more about

bioeconomy in a generational mother and daughter rapid word exchange. Before getting in contact with the projects, they never heard about bioeconomy. Therefore, the first step was to inspire them presenting several stories on how waste can become a resource (e.g. apple skin can become leather, leftovers from winemaking can become cosmetics, etc.), to raise their enthusiasm and interest. Once inspired, the next step was to empower them with solid knowledge as well as bio-based products and curiosities, and create a series of stories, each one addressing an application field of the bioeconomy.

Finally, after the video shooting and editing, a contents check was performed, to prevent misleading communication. In this phase, insights like prices of bio-based products, communication messages and data were provided in a nice graphical format.

Type of Practice: Educational

Type of Instrument: Info & Advisory

Region: Italy

Year Implemented: 2021

The videos were distributed through social media channels as a weekly appointment with the bioeconomy, targeting the Italian public (including mature audiences, as planned), reaching nearly

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: 900,000 views in several profiles

Years of operation: 1

Status: Not active

900.000 views in several profiles.

Environmental Impacts

The core aim of this project is through its short educational videos about bioeconomy, involving famous people, on social media to promote bioeconomy development and sustainable consumption and lifestyles. Thus, the environmental benefits will be broad but impactful.

Social Impacts

Enhanced knowledge about bioeconomy, The target group should be convinced of the value of the bio-based products, in order to be credible and the testimonial should share and tell their “real experiences” about bio-based products which would also mean that they had to use them in order to convey contents about the bioeconomy and its impacts on the economy, environment and society

Economic Impacts

In the long term as awareness grows of the overall benefits of a sustainable bioeconomy, the natural economic benefits will develop as the sector grows from the awareness developed through programmes like this.

Replication Potential

The model can be transferred but depends on collaboration and participation of the correct regional actors or celebrities.

Further Information

Website:

<https://library.iated.org/view/ALBERTINI2022EMP>

3: Interactive map Atresbio

Problem Statement

Foster the coordination of available regional resources, promoting the transfer of technology and knowledge.

Executive Summary

Interactive map ATRESBIO has the aim of promoting value chains to obtain bioproducts derived from biomass from olive groves, horticulture and algae in Andalusia. This tool analyses Andalusian capacities in research and in 10 key innovation services.

Description

The objective of the map is to identify, coordinate and give visibility to regional capacities for research and the provision of innovation services in the bioeconomy. The map includes a search engine that allows to filter by province, sector (olive, horticulture, algal biomass and others) and service.

All the entities identified on the map offer some of the 10 advanced innovation services that the ATRESBIO project has considered key to the development of the Andalusian bioeconomy:

- Industrial proof-of-concept.
- Patent and IP related aspects.
- Life-cycle assessment.
- Technology and economic appraisal.
- Feedstock analysis.
- Market research.
- Sustainability assessment and regulatory compliance and reporting.
- Business Planning and business plan reviewing.
- Access to investors.

Type of Practice: Networking

Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning

Region: Andalucía

Year Implemented: 2022

- Support to proposals to EU funding calls.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: 128 participants

Years of operation: 1

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Within the stated aims of the practice, “Support the positioning of Andalusia as a region of international reference in bioeconomy”, will result in the natural environmental impacts of a developed bioeconomy and the resulting sustainable practices that entails.

Social Impacts

Also, with a developed bioeconomy comes the resulting social benefits of a sustainable environment and most importantly a sustainable and stable employment market.

Economic Impacts

These studies inform companies regarding the technical feasibility and possibilities of turning their innovative technology into economically viable products. The results of these studies allow companies to determine the next steps of their innovation and their business development strategy.

The data generated can be used to carry out techno-economic assessments and Life Cycle Analysis (LCA), to identify strategic partners in the industry or to attract and convince potential investors.

Replication Potential

This practice is fully transferable to other regions.

Further Information

Website:

<https://atresbio.corporaciontecnologica.com/en/interactive-map/>

4: Novamont@school

Problem Statement

Need for society awareness, especially for students, concerning bioeconomy, circular bioeconomy, environment, and sustainability issues.

Executive Summary

"Novamont@Scuola" from company Novamont wants to contribute to the development of environmental education courses in schools and to spread knowledge on the topics of the bioeconomy and bioplastics in a simple and fun way.

Description

"Novamont@school" is the training project created by NOVAMONT to disseminate knowledge on the issues of bioeconomy and circular economy among Italian upper and lower secondary school and university students. Thanks to the project, the research centres and the plants of the group periodically open their doors to show our production processes, our vision on new consumption and behaviour models inspired by the bioeconomy and to make known the innovative products of chemistry from renewable sources. An opportunity to share our values and business model, focused on the reconnection between the economy and society and contributing to jobs growth and innovation of our country, of which the new generations are the main resource.

Type of Practice: Educational

Type of Instrument: Info & Advisory

Region: Italy

Year Implemented: 2017

After the success of the past editions, in 2018 Novamont@school initiative will be held on March 15th and 16th at Terni plant, the production centre of Mater-Bi biodegradable and compostable bioplastics family, on April 13th at the directional and research centre at Novara and on April 18th at Mater-Biotech premises, a company 100% controlled from Novamont which represents the world's first industrial plant capable of producing bio butanediol (1,4 BDO) directly from sugars.

Also, they have created educational tools and edutainment activities, which can easily be integrated with school learning paths and thus encourage sustainable behaviours in the new generations. These are: The NOVAMONT alphabet: Find out more about the world of bioplastics and bioproducts with the NOVAMONT sustainability alphabet, Recycling: Separate waste collection is a widespread practice in many Italian cities. Test yourself with Recycling, the waste recovery and recycling game and find out how to help the environment! Vivichem kit: With the Vivichem kit, students are stimulated, through questions and experiments to be reproduced in the laboratory, to learn more about the dynamics and products of a modern biorefinery: from renewable raw materials to the end of life of the products.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Not Identified

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Communities / Public

Level of uptake: Not Available

Years of operation:

Status: Active - Although information about the training sessions has not been found for later than 2018.

Environmental Impacts

With tools like the 'The NOVAMONT alphabet' environmental knowledge is developed and tools such as these can easily be integrated with school learning paths and thus encourage sustainable behaviours in the new generations.

Social Impacts

Better education for the young generation on the topics, the project wants to contribute to the development of environmental education courses in schools and to spread knowledge on the topics of the bioeconomy and bioplastics in a simple and fun way.

Economic Impacts

With the research centres and the plants of the group opening their doors to show our production processes, their vision on new consumption and behaviour models inspired by the bioeconomy and the innovative products of chemistry from renewable sources are shared. This shared business model, focused on the reconnection between the economy and society will contribute to jobs growth and innovation of the bioeconomy.

Replication Potential

Not transferred but easy to replicate by other large corporations/key players of bio-based industry in other countries and regions.

Further Information

Websites:

<https://www.novamont.com/eng/read-news/novamontschool-2018/>

<https://www.novamont.com/novamont-scuola>

Problem Statement

Program for the transformation of the blue bioeconomy sector, both at the national and international level, supporting the entry and growth of startups offering new sustainable products and services into the marine biotechnology market and in industries of high economic value.

Executive Summary

Blue Bio Value is the first major joint initiative launched by the Calouste Gulbenkian and the Ocean Azul Foundations. It is an acceleration and incubation programme for companies in the blue bioeconomy sector. The programme’s primary goal is to pave the way for Portugal to become a global leader in the marine biotechnology industry.

The programme supports entrepreneurs with commercially viable projects that use marine resources sustainably and help tackle today’s major societal challenges.

Description

The Oceano Azul Foundation was established in 2017, with the motivation to contribute to a healthier and more productive ocean. Under the motto “From the ocean’s point of view”, the Foundation works around three concepts: blue generation, blue natural capital, and blue network. Using a science-based approach, the model of change of the Oceano Azul Foundation integrates these three concepts supporting projects on literacy, conservation, sustainable fisheries, campaigns, blue economy and capacity building namely working with governments, foundations and civil society organizations, within the UN and the EU systems, to advance the international ocean agenda. The Calouste Gulbenkian Foundation envisions the Blue Bio Value Program to become a reference program for the transformation of the blue bioeconomy sector, both at the national and international level, supporting the entry and growth of startups offering new sustainable products and services into the marine biotechnology market and in industries of high economic value.

Type of Practice: Other
Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning
Region: Portugal
Year Implemented: 2017

Implementation

Deployment setting: Coastal

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Startups linked to biotechnology/blue bioeconomy.

Level of uptake: 59 participants

Years of operation: 6

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Blue Bio Value focuses on four challenges, feeding growing populations sustainably, climate change and CO₂ emissions control, scarcity of resources, and reduced plastic use. Successful solutions to these challenges will have positive and long-lasting impacts.

Social Impacts

Blue Bio Value aims to protect biodiversity and tackle climate change, while contributing to growth, employment, and human well-being.

Economic Impacts

By positioning the ocean at the centre stage of sustainable development, the emerging ocean industries that compose the blue bioeconomy today will become established industries and drive a sustainable circular bioeconomy.

Replication Potential

This practice is fully transferable to other coastal regions. This practice is focused on the blue bioeconomy so naturally should be replicated within a region with comparable resources.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.bluebiovalue.com/>

6: Greenhouse soil bio-solarisation in horticulture

Problem Statement

This practice is an action to help the practitioners to build appropriate crop rotations and innovative control strategies. It has been shared with network practitioners to prevent and reduce soil-borne diseases.

Executive Summary

The addition of fresh organic matter (i.e., crop residues) into the soil before solarisation is called bio-solarisation. This practice can increase the efficacy of solarisation by the incorporation of organic matter as fertilizers, improving the health of the soil and the amount and diversity of non-pathogenic microorganisms in the soil. Using bio-solarisation has been shown to be an efficient practice for the management of crop residues, solving the problem of handling these residues by offering a technique that respects the environment.

Description

This practice has been driven by the Best4Soil thematic network, which purposes to maintain, improve or re-establish soil health in Europe. This network involves 20 European countries, where the knowledge of soil health with the communities of practice has been exchanged.

The advantages of using the bio-solarisation technique include increased temperature due to the sheet and the decomposition of organic matter, improved water use and soil structure, reduced erosion and salinity, increased organic matter content, organic matter solubilization, CO2 capture during the development of the biofumigant crop, and the acceleration of in situ decomposition of plant waste from crops which reduces the transition time between crops. Solarisation is traditionally used in Southern Europe, where long periods of sunshine are sufficiently present. In regions where solarisation is not used, the potential of this practice could be a topic for a community of practices using organic matter.

The practice has been developed through Bes4soil Project, which has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020. This practice is included as environmental action in National Directives for the preparation of bid specifications for environmental actions, concerning action 7.6 (use of solarization or bio-solarisation techniques). This practice is promoted in Spain by Instituto Andaluz de Investigación y Formación Agraria, Pesquera y de la Producción Ecológica (IFAPA).

Type of Practice: Other

Typology of Practice: Technological Innovation

Practice: Agriculture

Region: Spain/Andalusia/Almería

Year Implemented: 2018

Implementation

Deployment setting: Rural

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Producers associations or cooperatives

Level of uptake: This practice inter-connects growers, advisers, educators, and researchers.

Years of operation: 6

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

The practice will involve the incorporation of crop residues as an organic amendment to soils, regularizing pathogens such as fumigant material and green manure. It respects the environment and provides a reference for horticultural production systems, even for the transition to organic farming.

Social Impacts

Innovative control strategies are provided through easily understandable tutorial videos and through factsheets which give more in-depth information. Avoiding social problems in terms of organic plant remains contamination and its consequent social impact.

Economic Impacts

The effects of the practice will result in reducing costs in relation to plastic solarisation, it is not necessary to buy plastics, reducing cost of chemical fumigants, eventual valorisation, and management of own crop residues. As well as creating market opportunities.

Replication Potential

It is replicable and the model has been transferred to 20 European countries.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.best4soil.eu/>

7: Green manures and cover crops in field and horticultural crops

Problem Statement

This practice is an action to help the practitioners to build appropriate crop rotations and innovative control strategies. It has been shared with network practitioners to prevent and reduce soil-borne diseases.

Executive Summary

The use of cover crops and green manures has some potential to control soil-borne diseases of field and horticultural crops. Cover crops have positive effects on soil structure, soil erosion, reducing nutrient leaching, weed suppression, and feeding the soil microbiome. Some species used as cover crops can also fix nutrients (nitrogen by legumes) or make nutrient more available (phosphorus by buckwheat). Used as green manures, they also help to sequester carbon.

Description

"This practice has been driven by the Best4Soil thematic network, which purposes to maintain, improve or re-establish soil health in Europe. This network involves 20 European countries, where the knowledge of soil health with the communities of practice has been exchanged.

This practice promotes the use of cover crops and green manures. The difference between these two types of crops is their final use. The above-ground part of green manures is incorporated into the soil at the end of the growing period with the aim of returning accumulated nutrients (e.g., nitrogen) or useful secondary metabolites (e.g., glycosylates) to the soil. Cover crops are grown for different reasons, such as to reduce leaching of nutrients (e.g., nitrate, then also designated as catch crops), avoid erosion, improve soil structure, or suppress weeds. A combined use is also possible, a crop can serve first as cover crop (e.g., for weed control) and then be incorporated as green manure (e.g., for nutrient input). The practice has been developed through Bes4soil Project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020.

Type of Practice: Other

Type of Instrument: Technological Innovation

Region: Spain/Andalusia/Almería

Year Implemented: 2018

This practice is included as environmental action in National Directives for the preparation of bid specifications for environmental actions, concerning action 7.27 (Use of vegetable covers in fruit crops as an alternative to conventional management). This practice is promoted in Spain by IFAPA.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Rural

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Producers associations or cooperatives

Level of uptake: This practice inter-connects growers, advisers, educators, and researchers.

Years of operation: 5

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

The practice will result in the reduction of the leaching of nutrients, avoiding erosion, improving soil structure, or suppressing weeds. Also, the promotion of soil microbiological biodiversity and improving soil water availability.

Social Impacts

Greater satisfaction and social benefit due to the multiple positive externalities derived from good practice. Innovative control strategies are provided through easily understandable tutorial videos and through factsheets which give more in-depth information.

Economic Impacts

The practice aims to drive new quality product attributes and market opportunities. New business models based on bioeconomy positive externalities will also develop.

Replication Potential

It is replicable and the model has been transferred to 20 European countries.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.best4soil.eu/>

8: Use of waste to promote biological control and biodiversity

Problem Statement

This practice has been identified as a transfer activity mainly aimed at farmers and technicians and at society itself to raise awareness that the management of agricultural waste must be seen from the perspective of the bioeconomy and the circular economy.

Executive Summary

The agricultural activity of greenhouse crops generates different residues, many of which can be reused or recycled. The practice includes training in the classification, managing and valorising of wastes, concretely the following activities:

- An exhibition area to raise awareness of the importance of implementing ecological infrastructures that favour biological control for conservation and biodiversity.
- Hedges of autochthonous plants which are of interest for increasing the populations of natural enemies in the environment.
- Shelters for insects and pollinators (hotels), built with previous classified residues.

Description

This practice has been driven and promoted by the technology transfer project RECICLAND, an acronym for "Demonstration and information activities for the management of solid waste derived from protected horticulture". An initiative of the Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Sustainable Development of the Andalusian Regional Government, and is managed through the Institute for Agricultural and Fisheries Research and Training (IFAPA), with EAFRD funding. The agricultural activity of greenhouse crops generates different types of waste. In addition to plant waste, other types of waste are produced, such as plastic crates, wood, wires, pipes, cardboard, drums, etc. Its management is also very important to keep greenhouse environments clean, contributing not only to improving the natural landscape but also to promoting biodiversity. Pallets and the timber can be reused in different construction elements, combined with other types of materials. Wood can be used for the construction of nest boxes, which serve as a shelter (hotels) for pollinators and can be of different sizes and shapes. The presence of these constructive elements, together with hedges of autochthonous plants in the surroundings of the greenhouses, favours their propagation and diversification, promoting biological control for conservation and biodiversity. In this way, this practice includes training in sorting, management, and recovery of different types of waste of greenhouse crops. This practice is included as environmental action in National Directives for the preparation of bid specifications for environmental actions, concerning action 7.31 (treatment, recovery, and sorting of waste).

Type of Practice: Other

Type of Instrument: Environmental Action, Info & Advisory

Region: Spain/Andalusia/Almería

Year Implemented: 2019

Implementation

Deployment setting: Rural

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Producers associations or cooperatives

Level of uptake: Mainly aimed at farmers and technicians and at society.

Years of operation: 4

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Recovering and promoting autochthonous plants and promoting biodiversity as well as promoting pollination through autochthonous insects and biological control, and therefore animal biodiversity. This will keep greenhouse environments clean, contributing not only to the improvement of the quality landscape but also to the promotion of biodiversity.

Social Impacts

Influencing product quality, due to biological control and the resulting health benefits associated. Satisfaction and higher utility of consumer segments will result. Creating good habits for both farmers and society (e.g., in gardens) to favour biodiversity.

Economic Impacts

Implementation of the practice will reduce the cost of managing certain agricultural waste, where the main problem is its seasonality. Cost reduction due to the use of biological control of autochthonous pollinating insects and increased productivity because of pollination.

Replication Potential

It has been transferred in Andalusia through demonstrative activities as conferences, visits, etc. to farmers, technicians, and civil society.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/agriculturaypesca/ifapa/recicland/node/14>

9: Use of alternative materials for plastic staking elements

Problem Statement

This practice has been identified as an innovative solution to overcome the problem of inorganic waste generated in horticulture in Andalusia.

Executive Summary

This practice proposes alternatives to materials plastic staking elements, that are used in the greenhouse in horticulture to support plant growth. It has proposed the following alternatives:

- Use of conventional twine (staking elements made from polypropylene).
- Use of 100% biodegradable twine (non-plastic staking elements made from biopolymers).
- Use of 100% compostable twine (non-plastic staking elements made from natural fibres).

The problems generated by materials plastic staking elements, especially with the remains of these staking elements in vegetable waste (which makes the treatment or composting of plant remains difficult), make the sector a higher predisposition to adopt these alternatives.

se of 100% biodegradable twine (non-plastic staking elements made from biopolymers).

- Use of 100% compostable twine (non-plastic staking elements made from natural fibres)

Description

This practice has been driven by the European Project REINWASTE (REmanufacture the food supply chain by testing INNovative solutions for zero inorganic WASTE). REINWASTE aims to bring a concrete contribution to the reduction of inorganic waste, favouring the adoption of greener innovative concepts by agriculture and food industry, with a focus on SMEs. It participates 10 clusters from three countries: Spain, France and Italy and it has received funding from the Interreg Euro-Med Programme (Testing). It enhances transnational network competence, selects, and tests the best available solutions and quickly transfers this knowledge.

Type of Practice: Other

Type of Technological Innovation

Instrument: Agriculture

Region: Spain/Andalusia/Almería

Year Implemented: 2020

The practice aimed at evaluating at a technical, socio-economic, environmental, and regulatory level, the use of twines produced with sustainable materials as alternatives to the plastic polypropylene twine currently used in farms. The most utilised staking is made of threads composed of synthetic fibre (polyethylene and polypropylene) which forces to remove vegetable waste mixed with the rest of the plastic staking elements when it is taken to composting plants. Removing this plastic from vegetable waste before sending it to composting plants is not a common practice. Therefore, there

is a potential risk of rejection of the material by the treatment plant since plant residues are not usually accepted with plastic traces. The use of alternative materials contributes to reduce these problems.

This practice is included as environmental action in National Directives for the preparation of bid specifications for environmental, concerning action 7.28 (use of biodegradable staking supporting material and biodegradable staking).

This practice is promoted in Spain by (IFAPA)

Implementation

Deployment setting: Rural

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Producers associations or cooperatives

Level of uptake: It has applied to the primary sector (horticulture producers' greenhouses)

Years of operation: 3

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

The use of biodegradable and compostable materials, which can be transformed together with the plant waste into compost. Improvement in the management of plant waste, avoiding the mixture of residues. This will contribute to the development in using natural fibre in agriculture sector.

Social Impacts

New self-management activities will increase social utility and satisfaction of the farmers. Promoting research and transfer of results of sustainable alternatives through different channels. Developing a regulatory framework that includes all types of inorganic waste in a differentiated manner.

Economic Impacts

Allowing waste plants to reduce costs of separation of staking plastics from plant waste will have a direct economic impact. Allowing farmers to make their compost, with all the advantages that this involves. Promoting quality certifications related to reduce inorganic waste will drive these activities.

Replication Potential

It has been transferred to the horticulture sector through different channels and is transferable to other similar sectors.

Further Information

Website:

<https://reinwaste.interreg-med.eu/>

10: Use of alternative materials for plastic mulching films

Problem Statement

This practice has been identified as an innovative solution to overcome the problem of inorganic waste generated in horticulture in Andalusia.

Executive Summary

In horticultural greenhouses, the mulching plastic film is used for several purposes, like weed control, soil temperature increase, water evaporation reduction and avoiding contact between soil and fruit/vegetable.

With this practice, two different kinds of plastic mulching films were used, one compostable and the other soil-biodegradable. It also evaluated the conventional use of low-density polyethylene mulching films.

The substitution of conventional mulching films with other biodegradable and/or compostable ones is an alternative for the difficult-to-manage waste of conventional low-density polyethylene.

Description

This practice has been driven by the European Project REINWASTE (REmanufacture the food supply chain by testing INNovative solutions for zero inorganic WASTE). REINWASTE aims to bring a concrete contribution to the reduction of inorganic waste, favouring the adoption of greener innovative concepts by agriculture and food industry, with a focus on SMEs. It participates three European countries: Spain, France and Italy and it has received funding from the Interreg Euro-Med Programme (Testing). It enhances transnational network competence, selects and tests the best available solutions and quickly transfers this knowledge.

Type of Practice: Other

Type of Instrument: Technological Innovation
of Instrument: Agriculture

Region: Spain/Andalusia/Almería

Year Implemented: 2020

The problem related to plastics mulching lies in the difficult acceptance of these by waste treatment plants since these materials are usually in poor conditions and mixed with dust, sand and vegetable remains, and need certain conditioning before being processed. The use of alternative materials for mulching films such as compostable and/or biodegradable mulching instead of conventional low-density polyethylene, means the adoption of agricultural practices that are more respectful with the environment and that contribute to the circular economy.

This practice is included as environmental action in National Directives for the preparation of bid specifications for environmental actions, concerning action 7.29 (use in the exploitation of biodegradable and compostable plastics).

Implementation

Deployment setting: Rural

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Producers associations or cooperatives

Level of uptake: It has applied to the primary sector (horticulture producers' greenhouses)

Years of operation: 3

Status: Active

This practice is promoted in Spain by IFAPA

Environmental Impacts

Significant improvements in terms of more environmentally friendly mulching plastics as well as the promotion of quality certifications related to respect for the environment, specifically the reduction of inorganic waste.

Social Impacts

Promotion of research and transfer of results of sustainable alternatives through different channels. Also developing a regulatory framework that includes all types of inorganic waste in a differentiated manner. Overall, it will drive the social awareness of the problem of inorganic waste in the horticultural sector.

Economic Impacts

The promoting quality certifications related to reduce inorganic waste which will encourage farmers to reduce the cost of conventional mulching films. The practice overtime will develop new quality attributes and new markets opportunities based on “zero plastics”.

Replication Potential

It has been transferred to the horticulture sector through different channels and is transferable to other similar sectors.

Further Information

Website:

<https://reinwaste.interreg-med.eu/>

11: Use of treated sewage sludge in the agricultural sector

Problem Statement

The use of treated sewage sludge in agriculture has been regulated, specifically in the soils of the Andalusian region.

Executive Summary

Through this practice, waste is valorised and represents a benefit to agriculture in line with what is proposed in the Andalusian Strategy for Circular Bioeconomy, by converting waste streams into value-added products (in particular, through the contribution of organic matter and phosphorus, deficient materials in Mediterranean soils) to improve production and efficiency in the use of sustainable resources. Treated sewage sludge will maintain its waste status until its effective incorporation into the soil, and as such must be handled and applied by the entities legally established for this purpose.

Description

The main driver and promoter of this practice is the Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development (Consejería de Agricultura, Pesca, Agua y Desarrollo Rural. Junta de Andalucía) of the Andalusian government.

Treated sewage sludges are generally sludge from a wastewater treatment plant that has undergone specific treatment in such a way that, through biological, chemical, or thermal methods, it significantly reduces its fermentability and its potential to cause health and environmental nuisance and damage. Sludge management involves waste producers, waste managers who are responsible for the collection, storage, transport, treatment and/or application of treated sludge and farmers.

This practice has been developed in a law (Orden de 6 de agosto de 2018, conjunta de la Consejería de Agricultura, Pesca y Desarrollo Rural y de la Consejería de Medio Ambiente y Ordenación del Territorio, por la que se regula la utilización de lodos tratados de depuradora en el sector agrario). Only the residues defined in Annex I of this law may be used in agricultural soils once they receive the appropriate treatment defined in Annex II. The detailed definition of these authorized treatments constitutes a legislative innovation at the national level.

The objective of this practice is to update and improve the monitoring and control mechanisms on the use of treated sludge from the treatment plant in the agricultural sector in the Autonomous Community of Andalusia, guaranteeing adequate recovery in agricultural soils.

Type of Practice: Other

Type of Instrument: Regulatory, Legislation. Environmental Action

Region: Spain/Andalusia

Year Implemented: 2018

Implementation

Deployment setting: Rural

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Producers associations or cooperatives

Level of uptake: There are more than 4.600 agriculture areas have availed of this practice.

Years of operation: 5

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

The valorisation of waste through treatment of sewage sludge optimises a valuable sidestream and is a direct improvement in the management of treated sewage sludge. The reintroduction of nutrients that would be otherwise lost has a direct benefit to agriculture and through the replacement of mineral fertilisers.

Social Impacts

Awareness-raising on the use of waste (treated sewage sludge) and the development of a regulatory framework that includes this kind of waste. Also, the obvious elimination of bad odours and the proliferation of unwanted insects.

Economic Impacts

Reducing consumption of traditional products (mineral fertilisers, which have been increasing in cost) on agricultural soils, reducing the costs for farmer. Increasing management cost of treated sewage sludge will be mitigated through these new practices.

Replication Potential

It has been transferred to the eight provinces of Andalusia.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturapescaaguaydesarrollorural/areas/agricultura/produccion-agricola/paginas/lodos.html>

12: Ban on single use carrier bags

Problem Statement

Countries face challenges dealing with plastic waste with plastic carrier bags among consumers a major factor in this build up.

Executive Summary

The Italian law on plastic shopping bags came into force on 1st January 2011. It bans the use of conventional plastic shopping bags, which must be replaced by biodegradable bags. This law has not only helped change the polymer that is normally used to produce these bags (polyethylene PE) to biodegradable polymers but has also led to a decrease in the overall consumption of these bags.

Description

Italy has a special position in Europe for the use of compostable bioplastics. The use of compostable bags, combined with its organic waste treatment sector and a law banning the

use of conventional plastic shopping bags²⁶, is probably one of the factors that have enabled Italy to take a leading position in the recycling of food waste compared with the European average (47% compared with a European average of 16%). The Italian law on plastic shopping bags came into force on 1st January 2011. It bans the use of conventional plastic shopping bags, which must be replaced by biodegradable bags. This law has not only helped change the polymer that is normally used to produce these bags (polyethylene PE) to biodegradable polymers but has also led to a decrease in the overall consumption of these bags. No one-to-one replacement of conventional plastic

shopping bags with bioplastic bags occurred after law came into force, but on the contrary, as shown in Figure 10, plastic shopping bag consumption fell from almost 180 tons in 2010 to 74.5 tons in 2020. The effect of the law was therefore very positive, because the consumption of plastic shopping bags fell by 60% over 10 years.

Type of Practice: Regulatory
Type of Instrument: Regulatory model
Region: Italy
Year Implemented: 2011

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: 50% reduction in carrier bags

Years of operation: 12

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Reducing carrier bags by 50% in retail 5 years. 50% of bags for separate collection of organic waste are shopping bags giving higher quality compost. Increase in use of biodegradable (including marine biodegradable plastics). Increase in use of bio-based content in plastics with reduced emissions.

Social Impacts

Creation of local supply chain, through the development of bioplastics based on Italy Agri supply chain. Estimated creation of 3,000 direct jobs in 5 years.

Economic Impacts

Investment of approximately 1 billion in Italian bio-based biorefinery sector within the 5 years following implementation.

Replication Potential

No foreseen barriers to transfer to other regions, although level of bioplastic production will depend on available feedstocks.

Further Information

Website:

https://issuu.com/edizioniambiente/docs/bioplastics_case_study_of_bioeconomy_in_italy

2.3.7 North-West Europe Cluster

Within ROBIN, partners based within the North-West Europe Cluster, namely MTU and SRA from Ireland led the collection of good practices in that jurisdiction. This was focused on the territory of the Southern Region of Ireland, but in addition to Ireland expanded more widely to include the following countries: UK, Sweden, Norway, Finland and Iceland. 24 good practices have been collected from the region. Again, the majority of these were Fiscal and Financial instruments with a smaller number of examples across Information and Advisory instruments, Networking, Collaboration and Joint Planning instruments, Regulatory instruments, Voluntary instruments, and other instruments.

The type of instruments is shown in Figure 36 below. The full list of good practices from the North-West Europe Region is outlined in Table 14, and the best practices from the region are included below.

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Figure 36: Types of Good Practice in North-West Region

Table 14. North-West Europe Good Practices

Good Practice Number	Good Practice Name	Jurisdiction, Country
1	BioVale Innovation Biocamp	Yorkshire and Humber, UK
2	Region of Skåne's Innovation-oriented Public Procurement Programme	Skåne, Sweden
3	Kalundborg Eco- Industrial Park	Kalundborg, Eco-Industrial Park
4	European Innovation Partnerships – Agriculture (EIP-Agri)	Ireland, other Countries
5	Bioeconomy Ireland Week	Ireland
6	Agri-Circular-Bioeconomy (ABC Economy)	Tipperary and Mongahan, Ireland
7	ICT-BIOCHAIN	Southeast Ireland, Andalusia, Spain
8	Green Business Models Programme	Central Jutland, Denmark
9	LEADER Programme for Rural Development (2014-2020)	Ireland (with local projects nationwide)
10	Växjö Energi	Växjö, Sweden
11	Pairc NaMara (Nua Na Mara)	Galway, Ireland
12	Green Enterprise: Innovation for a Circular Economy Fund	Ireland (with projects implemented regionally)
13	Woodland Support Projects Fund 2021-2022	Ireland (with projects implemented regionally)
14	Paper Province	Värmland, Sweden
15	Kerry Sustainable Energy Co-Op	Kerry, Ireland
16	Local Enterprise Office Green for Micro Programme	Ireland (with local projects nationwide)
17	Greve Biogas "Magic Factory"	Oslofjord, Norway
18	Ireland's Knowledge Centre For Carbon, Climate And Community Action (IKC3)	Ireland (Nationwide but with regional demonstrators)

Good Practice Number	Good Practice Name	Jurisdiction, Country
19	Skillnet Ireland-Climate Ready Academy Waste and Circular Economy Leaders Programme	Ireland (Nationwide but with regional participation)
20	Biorefinery Innovation Platform: Accelerate to commercialisation	Ornskoldsvik, Sweden
21	Edible Landscape Project CLG	Northwest Region, Ireland
22	Enterprise Ireland Climate Action Voucher	Ireland (with projects implemented regionally)
23	The Sustainable Tipperary Energy Roadshow	Tipperary, Ireland
24	Environmental Protection Agency Green Public Procurement	Ireland (with projects implemented regionally)

1 – BIOVALE Innovation Biocamp

Problem Statement

Many bio-based SME's face the challenge of bringing their innovations into a real-world business scenario.

Executive Summary

The Innovation Biocamp funded through the Biobase4SME programme was a week-long incubator programme operating between 2017 and 2019 aimed at providing high-potential biobased companies with hands-on tools needed to commercialise their biobased ideas and grow their companies.

Description

The Innovation Biocamp funded through the Biobase4SME programme was a week-long incubator programme aimed at providing high-potential biobased companies with hands-on tools needed to commercialise their biobased ideas and grow their companies. The Innovation Biocamp included a series of lectures from experts in key aspects of business growth, such as value propositions, business modelling, financing growth and risk management. Each lecture was followed by group exercises mediated by an experienced facilitator. Participants then worked with mentors to apply this learning to their own company. The training culminated in live pitches to a panel of specialist investors. Participant also benefited from peer-to-peer learning and networking with biobased companies across North-West Europe. A highly engaged and participative group of delegates worked well together for all the discussions, exercises and activities and could be divided into 3 categories:

Type of Practice: Financial Business Support

Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial

Region: Yorkshire and Humberland, UK

Year: 2017-2019

Founders just starting out (in business < than 1 year)

Founders of more established companies (in business > than 1 year)

Employees of start-up companies

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: SME's

Level of uptake: 50 entrepreneurs/7 countries

Years of operation: 3

Status: Model has been developed for use in other contexts.

Environmental Impacts

Funding received by companies through support from the Biocamps has resulted in the development of new sustainable products and practices making it to market.

Social Impacts

Support from the BioCamps proved instrumental securing investment for the creation of new jobs.

Economic Impacts

Economic success from the programme can be seen by developments of a number of programme participants: Holiferm awarded £400K to build a pilot plant for a separation fermentation process that provides a low-cost route to creating a range of biosurfactants. Oceanium securing £2 Million investment to scale up its proprietary seaweed biorefinery and processing model for applications including use in plant-based foods and sustainable packaging material as an alternative to plastic.

Bio Bean securing £5 Million investment to industrialise the process of recycling waste coffee grounds into advanced biofuels and biochemicals.

Replication Potential

The continued success of the model has led to BioVale delivering further one- and two-day training and online events for the THYME project, N8 AgriFood and the High-Value bio renewables network. As the model has been developed in context of Interreg NWE with participant from multiple regions. It appears suitable for deployment within new regions.

Further Information

<https://www.biovale.org/about/our-impact/biovale-biocamps-case-study/>

2:Region of Skåne's Innovation-oriented Public Procurement Programme

Problem Statement

Following an analysis carried out in 2011 of the regions of Skåne's impacts on climate change emissions, the regional council discovered that 40% of the Skåne's CO₂ emissions were generated through its healthcare sector with a large contribution from disposable products.

Executive Summary

Skåne introduced an innovation-oriented procurement programme focused on the sustainable procurement of bio-based aprons as a mechanism to reduce healthcare emissions.

Description

With 40% of the Skåne's CO₂ emissions generated through its healthcare sector, a major focused of the regional government shift to the significant impact of single-use (or disposable) products, such as protective aprons to this problem. In 2014, Skåne's healthcare sector was responsible for using and disposing of 5.2 million single-use aprons, generating the equivalent of 300 tonnes of CO₂ emissions. The Region of Skåne understood that the climate impact caused by these kinds of products can be reduced by limiting unnecessary consumption, but also finding new materials offering better performance and lower weight, as well as replacing fossil-based materials with fossil-free alternatives through, for example, innovation procurement.

Type of Practice: Public Procurement

Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning

Region: SE, Skåne

Year Implemented: 2014

As a climate-neutral disposable protective apron was not available on the market at that time, the Region of Skåne embarked on an innovation-oriented public procurement process to purchase aprons mostly made from renewable (bio-based) material. The process began in 2014 and concluded in May 2016 with the contract awarded to a company for the supply of disposable aprons consisting of 91% renewable material.

For the Region of Skåne, the procurement exercise meant not only that it was possible to stimulate innovation, which led to the development of a more climate-neutral product, but that it was also possible to create a model for how a PPI can be implemented, with lessons - and newly developed materials - that can be implemented in future processes.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Urban

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Public Bodies

Level of uptake: The tender comprised the supply of supply of 5.2 million bio-based disposable aprons.

Years of operation: 2014 - 2016

Status: Not Active

Environmental Impacts

The innovation procurement process was applied as a pilot project with support from the Swedish Energy Agency to support the target of the region to be fossil-free in 2020. The Skåne Region developed a Carbon Footprint Calculation tool to monitor CO₂ emissions from product groups with a high climate impact. The calculations take costs, emissions, the product's weight, and consumption per month into account. According to the Carbon Footprint Calculator, and with reference to, as benchmark, conventional plastic aprons, the purchase/use of bio-based aprons will result in savings of 250 tonnes per year of CO₂ emissions.

Social Impacts

The Winning company was an innovative regional company and some of the raw materials used were sourced locally and sustainably: starch from Kristianstad and chalk from Örebro.

Economic Impacts

A public procurement innovation procedure like this can lead to the development of a functional new product but can also result in developing new skills among suppliers and procurers.

Replication Potential

No information on whether this has been replicated to other sectors, jurisdictions, but the framework for tendering would be useful for other regions aiming to replicate the practice.

Further Information

Website: <https://www.biobasedconsultancy.com/en/procurement-tools111/good-practice-examples/biobased-aprons>

3: Kalundborg Eco-Industrial park

Problem Statement

The Kalundborg Eco-Industrial Park responds to the need to improve our use of resources, to on one hand, reduce the footprint of organisations and make more efficient and sustainable use of resources, while on the other hand helping companies to improve their profitability through synergies and sharing of resources.

Executive Summary

Kalundborg is the world's leading industrial symbiosis eco-system and creates profits through a circular approach to production. Its ecosystem benefits local public and private companies through the sustainable use and sharing of resources.

Description

Kalundborg Symbiosis is a partnership between fourteen public and private companies in Kalundborg. Together, since 1972, Kalundborg have developed the world's first industrial symbiosis with a circular approach to production.

The main principle is that a waste stream in one company becomes a resource in another, benefiting both the environment and the economy. In a local partnership, the initiative focuses on reuse resources, thus both saving money and minimising waste. The ecosystem includes actors across multiple domains (renewable and fossil-based energy, biotech/biology, pharmacy, glass) sharing more than 25 different resource streams. After each material—steam, wastewater, and sludge, to name a few—are used, the industrial park converts its

Type of Practice: Other

Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial

Region: DK, Kalundborg

Year Implemented: 1959 - commencement of Symbiosis 1972-present.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Urban

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: Fourteen public and private companies form part of this initiative, but the model is still growing.

Years of operation: 1959 - commencement of Symbiosis 1972-present

Status: Active

waste into upcycled resources. The electric company gives excess heat to factories. The organic waste of a biology plant yields biogas for the refinery. Pharmaceutical sludge is sent to farmers to fertilize crops. The steam that was initially a by-product for the electric utility is now the main product and income driver. What was once industrial waste has become revenue.

Environmental Impacts

The innovation procurement process was applied as a pilot project with support from the Swedish Energy Agency to support the target of the region to be fossil-free in 2020. The Skåne Region developed a Carbon Footprint Calculation tool to monitor CO₂ emissions from product groups with a high climate impact. Finally, Skåne Region developed a Carbon Footprint Calculation tool⁵ to monitor CO₂ emissions from product groups with a high climate impact. The calculations take costs, emissions, the product's weight, and consumption per month into account. According to the Carbon Footprint Calculator, and with reference to, as benchmark, conventional plastic aprons, the purchase/use of bio-based aprons will result in savings of 250 tonnes per year of CO₂ emissions.

Social Impacts

The Winning company was an innovative regional company and some of the raw materials used were sourced locally and sustainably: starch from Kristianstad and chalk from Örebro.

Economic Impacts

The main principle is that a waste stream in one company becomes a resource in another, benefiting both the environment and the economy. In the local partnership, the sharing and reuse resources saves both money and minimises waste.

Replication Potential

No information on whether this has been replicated to other sectors, jurisdictions.

Further Information

Websites:

<http://www.symbiosis.dk/en/>

<https://www.engieimpact.com/insights/eco-industrial-park-case-study-kalundborg>

4: EIP-Agri

Problem Statement

Farmers and rural areas are under pressure to maintain competitiveness while also producing sustainable and healthy food and ensuring our land continues to provide us with ecosystem services. Pressure can be environmental, economic or social and are often a combination of these.

Executive Summary

EIP-Agri supports a bottom-up approach to resolving key challenges that exist in the agricultural sector, combining the expertise of farmers, researchers, and policy makers. These operational groups develop innovative and practical solutions often to addressing sustainability challenges. A number of these initiatives hold a bioeconomy focus.

Description

The agricultural European Innovation Partnership (EIP-AGRI) works to foster competitive and sustainable farming and forestry that 'achieves more and better from less'. It contributes to ensuring a steady supply of food, feed, and biomaterials, developing its work in harmony with the essential natural resources on which farming depends. The EIP-AGRI brings together innovation actors (farmers, advisers, researchers, businesses, NGOs, and others) in agriculture and forestry, at EU level. Together they form an EU-wide EIP network. EIP Within this network, Operational Groups, Multi-actor projects and Thematic Networks are all key building blocks. Many EIP-Agri's projects use a results-based payments model, which sets specific sustainability criteria which should be met by farmers within the programme and links payments to the fulfilment of these criteria. Several projects are in operation which relate to different aspects of the bioeconomy including biorefinery, bio-based fertilisers, bioenergy, and enhancing biodiversity.

Type of Practice: Networking

Type of Instrument: Info & Advisory

Region: Ireland & European Union

Year Implemented: 2012

Different types of available funding sources can help get an agricultural innovation project started, such as the European Rural Development policy or the EU's research and innovation programme formerly Horizon 2020 and currently Horizon Europe. The EIP-AGRI contributes to integrating different funding streams so that they contribute together to a same goal and duplicate results.

Rural Development supports Operational Groups and Innovation Support Services within a country or region. Horizon funds multi-actor projects and thematic networks involving partners from at least three EU countries. Other policies may offer additional opportunities.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Rural

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Producers associations or cooperatives

Level of uptake: Varies from project to project.

Years of operation: 11

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Varies from project to project but resolving environmental challenges is a key objective.

Social Impacts

Varies from project to project, but normally involves collaboration with rural stakeholders (e.g., primary producers) and other actors (e.g., research and policy) for the purposes of innovation.

Economic Impacts

Varies from project to project, but many projects focus on new economic opportunities (e.g., diversification, organic farming, soil carbon sequestration etc.)

Replication Potential

The EIP-Agri model has been implemented in many countries, territories, and regions. A key aspect of EIP-Agri OGs is the creation of practice abstracts to support wider replication of the practice.

Further Information

Website:

<https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en>

5: Bioeconomy Ireland Week

Problem Statement

The bioeconomy is still a relatively niche concept among many stakeholders, and many stakeholders do not realise that they are already part of the bioeconomy. The week is about boosting awareness of the bioeconomy to help future development of the sector.

Executive Summary

Bioeconomy Ireland Week is week-long calendar of activities aimed at improving knowledge and awareness of the bioeconomy among various bioeconomy stakeholders in Ireland, from primary producers to consumers and everyone in between.

Description

Bioeconomy Ireland Week, now in its third year is a weeklong calendar of activities aimed at increasing awareness and knowledge of the bioeconomy and helping to grow Ireland's bioeconomy network. Targeted events aimed at different stakeholders are developed through the week. Key activities have included Research Information Days and Department Launch Events, site visits and field trips, webinars covering various sectors of the bioeconomy, networking events, and an interactive map series aimed at highlighting the development of different sectors of the bioeconomy.

Bioeconomy Ireland Week has grown and expanded over consecutive years, with a growing number of stakeholders, events, and audiences. Recent years have seen collaborative events held with libraries, supermarkets and pubs aimed at pushing the bioeconomy further into the public domain. While the initiative is a national level event, many of the events have a regional focus, and the fundamentals may be adapted to a regional level.

Type of Practice: Info & Advisory

Type of Instrument: Educational, Networking

Region: Ireland

Year Implemented: 2019

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: Generally, hundreds of participants and new members joining each year.

Years of operation: 4

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

The bioeconomy vision is to unlock the full potential of all types of sustainably sourced biomass including residual biomasses, such as crop residues, industrial side-streams, and food waste, as well as organic municipal waste by transforming it into value-added products will have far reaching environmental benefits as the bioeconomy is developed, events like bioeconomy week will promote this development.

Social Impacts

The collaboration of events and awareness raising initiatives involving industry, local communities, producers, researchers, and students throughout Ireland. A broad range of stakeholders from across Ireland's bioeconomy demonstrating how individually and collectively the natural environment can be utilized in a sustainable and circular way to help archive a fair and prosperous society.

Economic Impacts

On a broad level, bioeconomy week promotes knowledge sharing and building awareness of the bioeconomy across a variety of sectors within the country, thus will help build the bioeconomy and the resulting sustainable economic advantages in the long run.

Replication Potential

The model has potential to be replicated at a national or regional level. Scotland recently launched its first Bioeconomy Week in 2022.

Further Information

Websites:

<https://irishbioeconomy.ucd.ie/biw/>

<https://www.teagasc.ie/rural-economy/rural-economy/spatial-analysis/bioeconomy-ireland-week-2022-map-series/>

Problem Statement

Local regions need support in identifying bio-based value chains for further development, analysis of these value chain opportunities and creation of eco-system to further develop these.

Executive Summary

ABC Economy supports local authorities and regions with a framework for understanding the potential of the bio-based economies, identify and assess new value chains and conditions to support their development. The project has also developed an innovation blueprint for regions and councils to support their bioeconomy developments.

Description

ABC Economy focuses on identifying and enveloping new sustainable value chains for the bioeconomy in Ireland by maximising value and minimising environmental impacts through cascading biomass to create biobased products and generate energy. To begin with ABC Economy characterised biomass in each region and assess the potential processes for bioproduct and energy production.

ABC Economy engaged with key stakeholders two focal regional government localities, Tipperary County Council and Monaghan County Council, to identify and assess sustainable value chains based on available bioresources.

Type of Practice: Other
Type of Instrument: Info & Advisory, Framework Development
Region: Ireland (Tipperary and Monaghan Councils)
Year Implemented: 2019

Key stakeholders (primary producer, processors, waste management companies, etc.) were engaged throughout the project to identify important resources, constraints to valorisation, and potential opportunities. Central to ABC Economy is sustainability analysis to determine synergies and trade-offs between using biomass for energy generation and biobased products. The project will highlight possibilities to minimise trade-offs by considering the environmental /economic / social impacts. The project integrates LCA to assess selected value chains. Finally, the project delivered an innovation blueprint, or guide for developing the bioeconomy for local and regional authorities based on learnings to the project, which can support further regions from developing their bioeconomies. Key strands include: 1. Determining local and regional biomass quantities and characteristics 2. Identifying technologies and business models 3. Conducting sustainability, feasibility, market, and policy analyses 4. Engage local stakeholders 5. Foster Innovation Sprints 6. Create knowledge and innovation networks 7. Develop awareness and competencies.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Public Bodies

Level of uptake: No Data

Years of operation: 3

Status: Not Active

Environmental Impacts

Case studies have been evaluated using life cycle assessment to assess the impact of selected value chains in the two focal regions. Examples include a poultry manure to anaerobic digestion model in Monaghan and a grass silage and cattle slurry to anaerobic digestion model in Tipperary. The study found opportunities to reduce environmental impacts depending on scenarios selected.

Social Impacts

Key stakeholders (primary producer, processors, waste management companies, etc.) will be engaged throughout the project to identify important resources, constraints to valorisation, and potential opportunities and analysis to determine synergies and trade-offs between using biomass for energy generation and biobased products.

Economic Impacts

Development of new sustainable value chains for the bioeconomy in Ireland by maximising value and minimising environmental impacts through cascading biomass to create biobased products and generate energy.

Replication Potential

The approach was conducted for two regions, Monaghan, and Tipperary. No barriers exist to replication in other rural regions.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.abceconomy.ie/>

Problem Statement

Biomass supply chains are often dispersed or difficult to mobilise for the purposes of developing new value chains. This challenge can provide a barrier to new value chain develop due to high costs, emissions as well as logistical challenges in developing these supply chains.

Executive Summary

ICT-BIOCHAIN funded through the BBI JU, aims to improve the efficiency of biomass supply chains, through integration of digital technologies and modelling within the two model demonstrator regions for sustainable chemical production.

Description

The ICT-BIOCHAIN project works towards the established of digital innovation hubs within two designated EU model demonstrator regions for sustainable chemical production in Ireland and Spain. These digital innovation hubs, create an innovation network consisting of bio-based industries and companies, bio-based technology developers, ICT technology developers and business experts to providing a support framework and network in which companies can access different services within the eco-system. The main purposes is to find solutions to increase the efficiency and sustainability of biomass supply chains through the integration of ICT technologies, and therefore, the hub allows ICT developers and their networks, as part of a competence centre, to explore opportunities for their technology innovations to provide solutions for biomass practitioners. Specific projects were provided technical, or business supports depending on the requirements. The project also piloted a promising tool for mapping and modelling of biological resources on a regional basis. Tested within Andalucía and South-East Ireland, the tool evaluates the biomass arisings, fates, composition, and price and allows an understand on the freight cost for interregional biomass transfer.

Type of Practice: Non-Financial Business Support

Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial, Networking

Region: IE & ES (South-East Ireland and Andalucía)

Year Implemented: 20018

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: Approx 15-20 members per region with 3 value chains supported.

Years of operation: 3

Status: Not Active

Environmental Impacts

No specific data, but opportunity to mobilise and utilise waste streams, and ability to make more precise and sustainable supply were part of the objectives and identified as good practices.

Social Impacts

The development of competence centres will provide access to the best knowledge, information, and technology to promote opportunities for ICT, IoT and Industry to be integrated into biomass supply chains.

Economic Impacts

No specific data however, several companies and technologies were introduced, developing collaborations via the hubs.

Replication Potential

The approach was pilot within two designated regions. In addition, the project included a number of learning regions which benefited from the ICT-BIOCHAIN Roadmap, delivered through train-the-trainer workshops.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/project/ict-biochain/>

8: *The Sustainable Tipperary Energy Roadshow 2022*

Problem Statement

There has never been a sustainability and future proofing event like this across the county of Tipperary before. Therefore, this Roadshow resolved a barrier that existed in terms of SME's and communities gaining practical measures that they can apply quickly and effectively to their organisations.

Executive Summary

The event brings together like minded companies working on renewable energy, circular economy, maximising resources and lowering carbon footprint. The event offered advice and details of grants and services available to fulfil organisations Sustainability goals.

Description

The Roadshow was run by Local Enterprise Office Tipperary in association with County Tipperary Chamber and County Tipperary Skillnet. The event is in association with 'Sustainable Tipp' which is the title of a co-operative energy transformation of Tipperary's housing, commercial, public and community sectors over three years. It is a support mechanism for communities, farmers, homeowners, and business owners to save energy and money and become more sustainable. The Roadshow consisted of information stands from appropriate agencies where businesses, community groups and individuals could discuss and gather advice and information on the various schemes and grants available to enable the transition to reduced energy costs and alternative sources of energy. There were also information breakout rooms which informed businesses and communities about the various funding mechanisms available for energy efficient measures and sustainability options and measures that will help decrease transport costs,

Type of Practice: Other
Type of Instrument: Info & Advisory, Networking
Region: Ireland, Southern Region, Tipperary
Year Implemented: 2022

Implementation

Deployment setting: Rural
Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple
Level of uptake: For the 2022 Roadshow there are three separate expos across three venues in the county of Tipperary.
Years of operation: 1
Status: Active

development of sustainable practices and reduction in the carbon footprint. There was also networking opportunities for those attending.

Environmental Impacts

This event is that it brings together like minded companies working on renewable energy, circular economy, maximising resources and lowering carbon footprint. It offers advice and details of grants and services available to fulfil organisations sustainability goals. Information will be offered on alternative sources of energy and measures that will help decrease transport costs, development of sustainable practices and reduction in the carbon footprint.

Social Impacts

The social impact of this event is that it will bring together likeminded organisations that that are working on renewable energy, circular economy, maximising resources and lowering carbon footprint and they will advise and educate the Tipperary business community.

Economic Impacts

The economic impact of the roadshow is that it will provide information from appropriate agencies where businesses, community groups and individuals can discuss and gather advice and information on the various schemes and grants available to enable the transition to reduced energy costs. It will also inform businesses and communities about the various funding mechanisms available for energy efficient measures and sustainability options and will also focus on measures that will help decrease transport costs.

Replication Potential

It is not clear, as this is the first renewable energy roadshow event of its kind in Tipperary. There have been bigger more national led events such as the SEAI (Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland) Energy Show 2022 and the Irish Renewable Energy Summit however events such as The Sustainable Tipperary Energy Roadshow 2022 may pave the way for more a regional specific approach to such events.

Further Information

Website:

<http://sustainabletipp.ie/sustainable-tipp-energy-expo-roadshow/>

9: LEADER Programme for Rural Development 2014-2020

Problem Statement

The LEADER Programme for Rural Development has been integral to delivering locally led projects that have brought major benefits to communities across Rural Ireland. The programme has filled a rural development gap where a ground up approach is taken to empower local communities to deliver projects that will revitalise our towns and villages.

Executive Summary

In Ireland, under the LEADER Programme for 2014-2020, a budget of €250 million in grant aid is being provided to support rural communities and local businesses. The LEADER Programme is administered at a local level by 29 Local Action Groups (LAGs) who operate on administrative or county boundaries and are made up of local representatives from the community, public and private sector.

Description

The LEADER programme aims to support the local development of Ireland’s rural areas. Rural areas are defined as all parts of Ireland except for the areas within the boundaries of the five main cities of Dublin, Cork, Limerick, Waterford, and Galway. Each Local Action Group (LAG) is responsible for selecting and awarding LEADER funding to projects within their geographical area. A project must be aligned with the priorities of the Local Development Strategy (LDS). The LDS is a 5-year plan that was developed by the LAG, in conjunction with the rural community, to support the sustainable development of the area. The LEADER programme accepts applications

Type of Practice: Financial Business Support

Typology of Practice: Fiscal & Financial

Region: Ireland, National and EU wide

Year Implemented: 2014

Implementation

Deployment setting: Rural

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: The LEADER Programme has been integral to delivering thousands of locally led projects that have brought major benefits to communities across Rural Ireland.

Years of operation: 6

Status: Not Active

based on projects which improve rural tourism, enterprise development, broadband basic services targeted at hard-to-reach communities, rural youth protection and sustainable use of water resources, local biodiversity and renewable energy.

Environmental Impacts

Grant aid is offered to projects that fall under the theme of 'Rural Environment'. This includes projects which are involved in the protection and sustainable use of water resources, local biodiversity, and renewable energy. A booklet produced by the National Rural Network as part of Bioeconomy Ireland Week 2021 showcases 10 Bioeconomy projects/initiatives supported by the LEADER programme, Example- Continuous Cover Forestry, Castlecomer, Co. Kilkenny. LEADER Programme supported the purchase of a small scale, light weight tracked forestry machine to determine if a viable income could be generated from a Continuous Cover Forestry. Results from the project have a wider application for hardwood plantations regionally.

Social Impacts

Grant aid is offered to projects that fall under the theme of 'Social Inclusion'. This includes projects which are involved in Basic Services targeted at hard-to-reach communities and rural youth.

Economic Impacts

Grant aid is offered to projects that fall under the theme of 'Economic Development, Enterprise Development and Job Creation'. This includes projects which are involved in rural tourism, enterprise development, rural towns, and broadband.

Replication Potential

Since its launch in 1991, LEADER has provided rural communities across the European Union with the resources to enable local partners to actively engage and direct the local development of their area, through community-led local development. October 2022 Minister for Rural and Community Development, Heather Humphreys, announced the details of the €180 million LEADER Programme for 2023-2027.

Further Information

Websites:

<https://www.gov.ie/en/service/87e09-leader-programme-for-rural-development/>

<https://www.nationalruralnetwork.ie/leader/leader-news/leader-and-the-bioeconomy-2021-booklet/>

10: EPA Green Public Procurement

Problem Statement

The public sector has a vital role to play in leading Ireland’s transition to a sustainable and carbon-neutral economy and society. Green Public Procurement (GPP) is one of the primary ways in which public bodies will help to shape this transition, and to meet the 2030 targets for reducing CO2e emissions and improving energy efficiency.

Executive Summary

Green Public Procurement (GPP) is a process where public authorities in Ireland seek to source goods, services or works with a reduced environmental impact. GPP is acknowledged as a vital policy lever in meeting environmental policy objectives.

Description

Ireland has committed to implementing GPP in all tenders using public funds by 2023. This will require a major shift in the practices of public bodies and the businesses they contract with. By 2023, all procurement using public funds will need to include green criteria. This is being supported by a national training programme on GPP, which was launched in 2020. The sectors covered are road transport vehicles and services, ICT products and services, food and catering services, cleaning products and services, design, construction and management of office buildings, indoor and outdoor lighting, heating equipment, energy related products, paper products and printing services and textile

Type of Practice: Public Procurement

Typology of Practice: Regulatory

Region: Ireland

Year Implemented: 2012

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: Government Departments in Ireland reported a total spend of on contracts over €25,000, that were procured using green criteria in 2020. This represents an average of 17% of the total spend reported on contracts over €25,000 (this ranges between individual Departments from 0% to 100% of total spend reported). This also represents 26% of the total number of contracts over €25,000.

Years of operation: 11

Status: Active

products and services.

Environmental Impacts

A Waste Action Plan for a Circular Economy, Ireland's National Waste Policy 2020-2025, acknowledges GPP as a vital policy lever in driving the prevention of waste and related environmental policy objectives. GPP takes a broader view of environmental sustainability by addressing issues such as the circular economy, land use, biodiversity, and air, water, and soil pollution.

Social Impacts

GPP includes the social dimension of public contracts by taking account of their impact on employment, social inclusion, human rights and ethical or fair trade. Increasingly, public authorities are implementing an approach to procurement which takes both environmental and social factors into account. This is important as a way of building public support for procurement which is seen to benefit both people and the planet.

Economic Impacts

As the cost of emissions increases and regulations tighten, companies and products which have not invested in low-carbon products and processes will become more expensive. Purchasing greener products at an early stage of their development allows public bodies to benefit from innovation and to help shape future product and service offerings.

Replication Potential

The European Commission and several European countries, including Ireland, have developed guidance in this area, in the form of national GPP criteria.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.epa.ie/publications/circular-economy/resources/GPP-Guidance-for-the-Irish-Public-Sector.pdf>

11: Enterprise Ireland Climate Action Voucher

Problem Statement

The Climate Action voucher helps to overcome the barrier and support companies as they prepare for the low carbon, more resource efficient economy of the future. The Climate Action Voucher is designed to allow eligible companies to avail of Technical and/or Advisory supports from external experts in an easy way, with minimal cost, delay or administration that may often deter them. It is expected that outcomes of this short assignment will lead to further training/technical feasibility/capital projects/innovation, i.e., an objective is to start companies on a journey of activities.

Executive Summary

The Climate Action Voucher is available to eligible companies to access up to 2 days independent technical or advisory services support related to the current and future operations of their business. The voucher may be used to obtain services from approved providers. The Climate Action Voucher is funded under the Climate Planning Fund for Business, which is operating under the Green Transition Fund.

Description

As part of Ireland's National Recovery and Resilience Plan funded by the European Union, the Green Transition Fund is supporting the decarbonisation of Irish enterprise. The Climate Action Voucher is part of the Climate Planning Fund for Business stream of the fund and covers either technical or advisory services related to the operations of the business from an approved service provider up to a value of €1,800. A maximum daily rate of €900 per day applies. The support is provided over a relatively short period but can be spread out over a maximum of 6 weeks. Eligible Projects must include one of the following activities:

Type of Practice: Financial Business Support

Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial

Region: Ireland

Year Implemented: 2021

1. Develop a Sustainability/Decarbonisation Action Plan
2. Develop a Circular Economy Action Plan

Eligible activities do not include energy audits or general consultancy, design, installation or commissioning, or project implementation.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: No Data available

Years of operation: 2

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Companies will be able to plan and be able to move towards a low carbon, more resource efficient economy of the future and they will be supported in their decarbonisation journey, therefore supporting the achievement of a 51% reduction in emissions by 2030.

Social Impacts

For companies, the Climate Action Voucher could lead to further training/technical feasibility/innovation/ capital projects, i.e., it will start companies on a journey of activities.

Economic Impacts

Strong environmental credentials will better position companies to secure public and private tenders.

Replication Potential

There is large potential for other regions/counties around Europe to replicate/transfer a good practice similar to the Climate Action Voucher as part of their overall green/sustainable/circular transition funds. The reduction in emissions by 2030 across all sectors of the economy represents a whole-of-society challenge, and good practices such as the Climate Action Voucher can support business in their journey towards this goal.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.enterprise-ireland.com/en/Productivity/Build-a-green-sustainable-Business/Climate-Action-Voucher/Climate-Action-Voucher-Reference-Document.pdf>

12: Green Enterprise: Innovation for a Circular Economy Fund

Problem Statement

A Green Enterprise circular economy approach provides opportunities for enterprises to enhance competitiveness and reduce business costs. This approach will help build Ireland's capacity to transition to a low-carbon, resilient, circular economy.

Executive Summary

The EPA's (Environmental Protection Agency) Green Enterprise: Innovation for a Circular Economy is an annual funding call to support innovators in Ireland to develop, demonstrate and implement circular economy approaches in their business models. It is managed through the EPA's National Circular Economy Programme and is co-funded by EPA Research.

Description

Applications for funding in the range of €50k-€100k are invited, to support Irish businesses develop circular solutions in product and service design, production, distribution, and use of resources (including resources and raw materials). The fund is aimed at innovative projects targeting the area of Packaging, Plastics, Textiles, Construction & buildings, Food, water & nutrients, Electronics & ICT and Batteries & vehicles. Circular business models contribute to a climate-neutral, resource-efficient economy, but also offer competitive opportunities, and appeal to customers and consumers looking for sustainable options.

Type of Practice: Financial Business Support

Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial

Region: Ireland

Year Implemented: 2021

Objectives of the fund include enhancing competitiveness and resilience circular economy approaches in their business models as well as influencing and informing policy in the sector. Actions of the funded projects must develop sustainable solutions and articulate case studies and demonstrations. The desired outcomes of funded initiatives that they will have an impact on the circular economy, with SDG related objectives and targets that will further inform government policy.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: There are 21 Green Enterprise projects currently underway.

Years of operation: 2

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Sustainable projects will be developed. Projects funded will work towards preventing plastic waste and increase the recyclability of plastic products, create and showcase new and innovative solutions to tackling food waste and innovation in the construction and demolition sector to meet circular economy ambitions.

Social Impacts

Projects will work towards informing and influencing Government policy when it comes to the circular economy.

Economic Impacts

Circular Economy projects will have the potential to enhance competitiveness and resilience of enterprises .

Replication Potential

Objectives of this fund is that it will influence and inform policy, enhance competitiveness and performance, develop sustainable solutions, articulate case studies and demonstrations and impact n circular economy and Sustainable Development Goal objectives and targets. These are all objectives that would be priorities of other regions/countries, therefore this green enterprise fund could be very effectively replicated widely.

Further Information

Website:

https://www.epa.ie/publications/research/current-call-documents/2022_GE_Technical-Description_final.pdf

13: Woodland Support Projects Fund 2021-2022

Problem Statement

The Woodland Support Projects Fund is under the Forestry Programme 2014-2020 which identified a need to increase the level of forest cover, increase the supply of forest-based biomass, support private forest holders in actively managing their forest and enhance the environmental and social benefits of new and existing forests. The fund also recognised the need to encourage farmers and other landowners to plant and to raise the profile of forestry as a public good and a commercially viable enterprise.

Executive Summary

To encourage farmers and other landowners in Ireland to plant and to raise the profile of forestry as a public good and a commercially viable enterprise, the Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (‘DAFM’) is invites applications for funding of projects which support and highlight forestry.

Description

Farmers and other landowners can apply for funding to help cover the cost of forestry projects. Among other criteria, The Woodland Support Fund, is for projects that support and highlight productive forestry and timber products, in the context of climate action and the bioeconomy. Proposals submitted under this heading could include measures that focus on the economic benefit of forestry for farmers, the role played in diversifying farm income, the associated tax benefits, and the fact that forestry can work alongside the existing farm enterprise. A Call for Proposals for Woodland Support Funding was launched in 2021 and 39 projects aimed at raising

Type of Practice: Non-Financial Business Support

Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial

Region: Ireland

Year Implemented: 2021

Implementation

Deployment setting: Rural

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Other

Level of uptake: Over 61 applications were received of which 39 individual projects have now been selected for funding for 2021-2022 funding call.

Years of operation: 2

Status: Active

awareness of the multi-functional benefits of forestry were approved. Results from these projects will inform practice in relation to the bioeconomy and forestry both regionally and nationally.

Environmental Impacts

Support and highlight the environmental benefits of woodlands. Support and highlight productive forestry and timber products, in the context of climate action and the bioeconomy. Support and highlight sustainable forest management among forest owners.

Social Impacts

Projects will support and highlight the benefits of woodlands, focussing on farmers, and / or community engagement and /or general wellness.

Economic Impacts

Projects will promote the economic benefit of forestry for farmers, the role played in diversifying farm income, the associated tax benefits, and the fact that forestry can work alongside the existing farm enterprise. Other economic impacts are the promotion through funded projects of forestry for rural communities through the economic activity of associated businesses such as contractors, sawmills and manufacturers of timber products.

Replication Potential

Woodlands and Forestry has many benefits for society including economic, social and environmental ones. Therefore, any region which has forests and woodlands could have the potential to implement a good governance practice such as the Woodland Support Projects Fund.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/87bb6-open-call-for-proposals-for-woodland-support-projects-for-20212022-specification-and-application-form/>

14: Local Enterprise Office Green for Micro Programme

Problem Statement

With climate change, changing regulations, rising resource costs and changing customer expectations, adopting an eco-friendlier approach is something small companies want to do but often don't know where to start or if it will be of benefit to them. The LEO's Green for Micro Programme overcomes this barrier for companies by allowing them to avail of free advice and technical support, covering topics such as resource efficiency, understanding their carbon footprint and implementing an environmental management system.

Executive Summary

Green for Micro is a free Local Enterprise Office training programme for small businesses with 10 (or fewer) employees. Businesses can avail of advice and technical support, covering topics such as resource efficiency, understanding your carbon footprint and implementing an environmental management system. Find out what steps to take to reduce costs and lower your greenhouse gas emissions. Training is provided in two stages:

1. A webinar, covering examples of green initiatives and their benefits.
2. Two days of mentoring with a 'green consultant' or trainer, including specific recommendations for your business.

Description

The objectives of the Green for Micro programme are to help prepare small businesses for the low carbon, more resource efficient economy of the future. This is a free programme suitable for all microenterprises with up to ten employees, but it is particularly suited to businesses in construction and the built environment, retail, manufacturing, textiles and fashion, food, electronics, plastics, and packaging. As part of the programme, organisations can apply for two days of mentoring with a specialist Green Consultant – this will include recommendations on specific changes businesses can implement. A Green Consultant will be chosen from the Enterprise Ireland Green Directory or from your Local Enterprise Office mentor panel. The specific needs of the company will be matched to the Green Consultant's area of expertise to offer a specifically stated programme to the company.

Type of Practice: Non-Financial Business Support

Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial

Region: Ireland

Year Implemented: 2021

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: SMEs

Level of uptake: No data available

Years of operation: 2

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

The environmental impact of programmes such as Green for Micro is that it helps small companies work towards being more resource efficient, reduce their environmental footprint and greenhouse gas emissions and increase resilience to climate change actions.

Social Impacts

The social image of programmes such as Green for Micro is that it supports businesses to increase their access to customers and improve their corporate image when it comes to sustainability. It also works to offer small businesses support to help with their green transition free of charge, giving them access to resources they may not have had due to economic restraint. Also, individuals who work in the companies may be inspired to be more environmentally and sustainably conscious in their own lives from the company they work taking part in such programmes.

Economic Impacts

The economic impact of the programmes such as Green for Micro is that it helps small companies increase their cost savings and it is an opportunity for higher and additional value on products and services.

Replication Potential

The replication potential of this programme is very high as it is a simple two step programme that is free so therefore would have high uptake amongst small companies looking for non-financial support option and resources when it comes to preparing them for the low carbon, more resource efficient economy of the future.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.localenterprise.ie/Green/What-is-Green-for-Micro/What-is-Green-For-Micro.html>

Problem Statement

Skillnet Ireland have identified a need for businesses to improve their waste management policies and develop detailed actions plans for their business that are anchored in Ireland's Waste Action Plan for a Circular Economy.

Executive Summary

This programme provides participants with an understanding of current waste management best practices and guidance on how to move their business from a 'take-make-waste' consumption model that cannot be sustained to one based on a circular economy.

Description

The Climate Ready Academy aims to support Irish businesses in developing the skills and talent required to navigate our changing climate and environment. This programme provides businesses with skills and knowledge needed to take the lead in managing their organisations waste, while also demonstrating effective ways to decrease operation cost whilst protecting the environment. The programme is funded for eligible firms and is made up of a series of workshop webinars on the following themes over eight weeks:

1. Drivers & principles of circular economy
2. Tools to assess and improve circularity
3. Circular economy business models; barriers and guidance to transitioning to circular mode
4. 8 step flexible framework for implementing the principles of circular economy

Type of Practice: Educational
Type of Instrument: Info & Advisory, Educational
Region: Ireland
Year Implemented: Programme not starting until February 2023, but the Climate Ready Academy was launched in 2022 and is ran by the National Business Support Agency, Skillnet Ireland, which was founded in 1999.

The final output of the programme is that participants will create a bespoke waste charter and action plan to use in their business.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: No Data

Years of operation: Starting February 2023

Status: Programme not starting until February 2023, but the Climate Ready Academy was launched in 2022 and is ran by the National Business Support Agency, Skillnet Ireland, which was founded in 1999.

Environmental Impacts

Participants will create a bespoke waste charter and action plan to deploy in their business which in turn will have a positive impact when it comes to the businesses waste management moving to one with a strong circular economy policy foundation.

Social Impacts

The programme has the dual target of developing trainee skills at an individual level, and supporting and influencing those in charge of waste management in their organisation to be more socially conscious both personally and professionally when it comes to consumption and waste.

Economic Impacts

Businesses will gain the knowledge and skills how to identify key insights into effective waste management and deliver waste efficient services and save money at their site.

Replication Potential

There is replication potential in other regions as the premise and aims of the practice are transferable.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.climatereadyacademy.ie/waste-and-circular-economy-leaders/#:~:text=The%20Waste%20and%20Circular%20Economy,Plan%20for%20a%20Circular%20Economy.>

16: Kerry Sustainable Energy Co-Op

Problem Statement

KSEC aims to overcome the barriers of energy security of energy supply to members, substituting reliance on imported and non-renewable energy with locally sourced and owned energy . They also aim to educate and reduce fuel poverty in the county.

Executive Summary

A community-based Co-Op actively promoting and supporting more local ownership of renewable energy, creating benefits for the local community. Aiming substitute reliance on imported and non-renewable energy with locally sourced and owned energy while educating and assisting ourselves and the wider community on how to reduce energy wastage as we seek to fulfil the vision of a 100% renewable energy Kerry by 2030.

Description

KSEC Mission Statement “Our mission is to enable local communities in Kerry to become more resilient and self-reliant by developing and supporting strategies and practical initiatives that replace dependence on fossil fuels by sustainable renewable and economic alternatives.” With a primary driving force of reducing fuel poverty and encouraging local energy production independence KSEC aims to develop the local production and retailing of clean energy. This will be driven through developing local businesses based on clean energy that will utilise the abundance of both local and national expertise available. KSEC also sees the opportunity to develop Kerry as a prime location for the testing of new sustainable energy technology prototypes due to its location to many of the necessary feedstocks. On an engagement and social level KSEC develop programs to increase awareness in communities around the areas of fuel poverty and overcoming this through the need and benefits of renewable energy. On a national level KSEC engage with other co-operatives to improve regulative and legislative barriers to developing local energy co-ops. Some of the ongoing programmes include Killorglin Energy Masterplan, evaluate the energy usage of the Killorglin area and opportunities that can arise and Wood Purchase Project which offers members the opportunity to purchase locally produced firewood. KSEC has received funding from Kerry County Council Community Support Fund and the Rural Development (Leader) Programme and the SEAI.

Type of Practice: Non-Financial Business Support

Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial

Region: Ireland / Kerry

Year Implemented: 2016

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Communities / Public

Level of uptake: Active in County Kerry – Education Programs, Community Engagement, Business Supports etc.

Years of operation: 7

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Reducing the reliance on imported fossil-based energy will lead to a reduction in the associated environmental impact. Locally produced biobased energy production will over time contribute to climate change targets.

Social Impacts

Building awareness in communities about the need for and benefits of renewable energy leading to reduction of fuel poverty. KSEC uses local materials and equipment and contractors to implement their projects generating local employment. As the co-op grows it will be able to employ people to operate the business and manage its projects. Social Impact is closely linked to Economic Impact.

Economic Impacts

Generate revenue for the members and/or reduce energy expenditure. The co-op can decide to reinvest some of its profit into projects benefitting the wider community Revenue is naturally re-invested in the local economy.

Replication Potential

KSEC engages with other energy co-ops at a national level to share joints learnings.

Further Information

Website:

<https://ksec.ie/>

17: Pairc na Mara (Nua Na Mara)

Problem Statement

The development of the marine sector has the potential to provide significant direct socio-economic benefits for the region and to generate other stimuli to further integrate the development of the local economy. The proposed location offers the potential to develop a sustainable aquaculture cluster around the existing range of activities in the area.

Executive Summary

Páirc na Mara is proposed as Ireland’s first dedicated Marine Innovation Park. Páirc na Mara will be developed as a state of the art, low carbon, Marine Business Park, encompassing a variety of marine related activities, where productive sector enterprises, public bodies, state development agencies and the research community will work together to add value to their products and services and to maximise the development potential of the marine sector in the region.

Description

The Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine have identified the ocean as a national asset, “It supports a diverse marine economy with strategically significant potential to tap into the €1,200 billion global marine market for seafood, blue tourism, oil and gas resources, marine renewable energy, and new applications for health, medicine and technology”. A key element of Páirc na mara is Nua na Mara which is being championed by Údarás na Gaeltachta. Nua na Mara is an enterprise founded by Údarás na Gealtacha and Enterprise Ireland, and is an entity dedicated to supporting the development of marine start-ups, early-stage companies, and existing businesses. Nua na Mara will leverage their connections within the marine industry here in Ireland and further afield to help marine start-ups to bridge the gap in linking innovation, application, concepts, and commercialisation. Nua na Mara gives access to the world class research, testing and enterprise development facilities for the marine sector provided by GMIT and NUI Galway. Nua na Mara aims to support and nurture SME’s and start-ups with supports such

Type of Practice: Other

Typology of Practice: Networking, Social Innovation, Financial Support, Business Innovation & Education.

Region: Ireland / Galway

Year Implemented: Proposed

Implementation

Deployment setting: Coastal

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: Proposed Project

Years of operation: Proposed Project

Status: Proposed

as training and development, providing knowledge on funding and grant aid, linking to facilities, and acts as a gateway to key stakeholders in the marine industry. Supported by many projects of Údarás na Gaeltachta, including EU funded projects SW-Grow (seaweed industry in the Northern Periphery and Arctic region), EMPORIA4KT (blue economy support mechanism) & ACCESS2SEA (aquaculture support).

Environmental Impacts

From an aquacultural development potential: Marine aquaculture operations typically have a smaller carbon footprint and require less land and fresh water. A recent planning decision has been made against the park citing concerns over the use of fresh water and its effect on the local ecosystem, and an inadequate environmental impact statement.

Social Impacts

Increase knowledge and develop skills and expertise in the sector, creating a sustainable aquaculture industry in the area that would 'revitalise' the region.

Economic Impacts

Encourage more marine related start-up enterprises, Accelerate the upscaling of existing SMEs through access to shared infrastructure and development supports and attract foreign direct investment to the sector and the region.

Replication Potential

It has the potential to be a world class example of an innovation campus established to help marine start-ups to bridge the gap in linking innovation, application, concepts, and commercialisation. The model could be transferred to other coastal regions.

Further Information

Website:

<https://paircnamara.ie/en/nua-na-mara/>

18: Paper Province

Problem Statement

The Paper Province is a cluster that develops the regions forest-based bioeconomy to collaborate on the use forest raw materials to develop a local sustainable bioeconomy.

Executive Summary

The cluster of more than 100 member companies was started in 1999 by seven companies with a common need, recruiting competent staff. The initial need was later developed to the present Paper Province where they collaborate to use forest raw materials to achieve a world-leading cluster within the forest bioeconomy.

Description

Paper Province is a world-leading business cluster within the forest bioeconomy, with a primary aim towards sustainable development. Located in a region with a naturally abundant feedstock (wood from forests), the cluster's ethos through innovation they can help make the shift to a fossil-free society. Sustainability is core to their activities as they see the forest belonging to the future. The cluster is built upon 4 pillars – Innovation and Development: assisting in taking members raw materials to their highest potential. Supply of a skilled workforce: developing educational programmes that develop skills and interest in the forest bioeconomy. Internationalisation: connect with foreign organisations which leads to a two-way information exchange beneficial for all parties. Regional Mobilisation: In the Värmland region and the surrounding area the cluster works to contribute to a sustainable future. Their members include bio-energy suppliers and a variety of bio-based suppliers. In 2017 Paper Province was awarded with the EU's highest cluster award - Cluster Management Excellence Gold.

Type of Practice: Other

Type of Instrument: Educational, Financial Support, Business Innovation & Education.

Region: Sweden / Värmland

Year Implemented: 1999

Implementation

Deployment setting: Rural

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: Strong uptake – cluster has more than 120 members

Years of operation: 23

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

The Cluster puts sustainability core to its ethos, focusing on Sustainable Development Goals: Goal 9: A sustainable industry, innovation, and infrastructure & Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production.

Social Impacts

Focusing on Sustainable Development Goal 5: Gender equality, they want to change the industry from male dominance see it as having a negative impact on long term competitiveness and innovation.

Economic Impacts

The cluster has harnessed growth and collaboration over more than 20 years and successfully developed a thriving forest-based bioeconomy in the region.

Replication Potential

The model has replication potential, it engages in shared learning activities on a national and international basis for shared learning.

Further Information

Website:

<https://paperprovince.com/en/>

19: Greve Biogas "Magic Factory"

Problem Statement

The municipal governments had a vision of achieving more sustainable biogas-fuelled infrastructure, e.g., public transport. They established a partnership to produce biogas from manure and household food waste to fuel public buses and waste collection vehicles, and bio digestate to replace chemical fertilisers.

Executive Summary

The Magic Factory is a biogas plant cooperatively owned and managed by two multi-municipality partnerships, Greve Biogas and Vesar refuse collection. It produces biogas from household food waste and agricultural manure, biofertilizers from digestate, and has an on-site Educational Centre for Sustainability and has a goal is to become an international pioneer for green carbon capture. The biogas is used as environmentally friendly fuel for vehicles such as public busses and trucks.

Description

The Magic Factory is a biogas plant cooperatively owned and managed by two multi-municipality partnerships, Greve Biogas and Vesar refuse collection. It produces biogas from household food waste and agricultural manure, and biofertilizers from digestate which is sold to local farmers. The food waste comes from households in Eastern Norway and the manure comes from farms in the region. Approximately 110,000 tons of food waste and manure are recycled per annum, producing biogas equivalent to 6.8 million litres of diesel fuel. There is an on-site Educational Centre for Sustainability for sharing knowledge with school students. The Magic Factory's goal is to become an international pioneer for green carbon capture. Carbon capture takes place through renewable and green CO2 from the factory being used inside industrially adapted greenhouses for food production, together with bio-fertilizer from the factory. A Magic Pilot Greenhouse is under construction for testing, with a plan for rolling out industrial greenhouses for local food production.

Type of Practice: Other

Type of Instrument: Public-public partnership, Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning

Region: NO/Oslofjord

Year Implemented: 2016

Implementation

Deployment setting: Coastal

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: 1.2 million households, 11 municipalities

Years of operation: 7

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Fossil fuel displacement with biogas in public transport, municipal waste collection, and greenhouses, displacement of synthetic fertilisers with biofertilizers, efficient municipal waste management.

Social Impacts

Efficient municipal waste management, public transport fuelled by locally produced biogas, extra income for farmers and local biofertilizer supply, local waste management education centre focused on children and teenagers.

Economic Impacts

Local production of biogas for public vehicles, income for farmers for manure, continued collaboration with agriculture for developing storage facilities and spreader technology for bio-fertilizer, and the greenhouse sector for the establishment of industrial Bio-CCP (Carbon Capture Products) greenhouses.

Replication Potential

The site has become a national pilot plant and can be replicated in other contexts where biogas-powered vehicles are prevalent.

Further Information

Website:

<https://denmagiskefabrikken.no/>

20: *Biorefinery Innovation Platform: Accelerate to commercialisation*

Problem Statement

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are important for regional bioeconomy development, but they often lack the scope to do their own research and development activities. The accelerator aims to strengthen the innovation environment in bio-refinery, bio-based processes, green products, chemicals, and materials.

Executive Summary

Biorefinery Innovation Platform: Accelerate to commercialisation is an initiative of the Processum Biorefinery cluster and pilot park. The goals are to support bioeconomy innovation, develop a sustainable regional innovation platform for biorefinery development, and develop international innovation collaborations within the biorefinery's value chains.

Description

The project Biorefinery Innovation Platform: Accelerate to commercialization is operated by Processum and the project's approach is largely based on a model developed by Processum, where the core of the work is to initiate, conduct and support need-driven research and innovation in collaboration with industry, academia, and society. Processum has since 2007 hosted a long-term initiative to develop an innovation environment, where the bio-based business community constitutes the core, but many different actors collaborate within the regional innovation platform.

Type of Practice: Non-Financial Business Support

Type of Instrument: Innovation accelerator, Fiscal & Financial

Region: SE/Ornskoldsvik

Year Implemented: 2019

The cluster consists of around 20 companies, but universities, authorities, incubator companies and start-up companies are also important partners. Together, we work openly and constantly to welcome new players who have an interest in the development of the biorefinery area and share the vision of sustainable development based on bio-based processes, green products, chemicals and materials.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Coastal

Stakeholder beneficiaries: SME's

Level of uptake: 82 biorefinery projects since the start of IB:ACCEL. 370 companies and 53 research organisations participating in IB:ACCEL.

Years of operation: 4

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

The transition into circular economics means the transition into a system where we consume dramatically fewer natural resources. The value of products is kept a lot longer than today, and companies can make a profit by having their customers subscribe to product function rather than buying new products. RISE research into circular economics includes the use of secondary resources such as plastics, food waste, building and demolition waste, biomass, and metals.

Social Impacts

RISE works as a catalyst and offers education and training based on our scientific research. Within the educational concept "Learning by RISE", they offer both longer and shorter knowledge-strengthening activities, education and training.

Economic Impacts

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are an important part of Sweden's business and development, but they can rarely conduct their own research and development activities. The practice's primary goal 2019-2022 is to increase the number of innovation processes involving innovative SMEs and the pace of innovation processes within the biorefinery's value chains.

Replication Potential

This practice is fully transferable to other regions, and similar clusters exist in other regions.

Further Information

Website:

www.ri.se/en/node/15341

21: Växjö Energi

Problem Statement

Växjö municipality's overall goal is to become a fossil fuel-free municipality by 2030, with fossil fuel-free district heating and cooling.

Executive Summary

is an energy and communication company owned by Växjö municipality. Växjö municipality's overall goal is to become a fossil fuel-free municipality by 2030, with fossil fuel-free district heating and cooling. Since 2019, in line with this goal, the district heating, district cooling and electricity provided by Växjö Energi are produced from renewable biofuel from forests, i.e., branches, tree-tops, and other residues, with fossil-free operations in the entire business (logistics and other aspects). The initiative now wants to go further to develop a carbon-capture and storage facility.

Description

Since December 2019, our entire operation has been fossil-free. All our district heating, district cooling and electricity is produced from renewable biofuel from the forest. That is, branches, tops and other remnants from the Småland forests that would otherwise have gone to waste. Växjö Energi has been producing heat and electricity from residues from the forest since the 80s, but with the new biofuel-fired combined heat and power plant Sandvik 3 was started in 2015, they have been able to reduce the use of fossil fuels, peat, and oil, while at the same time significantly increasing electricity production.

The company collect the biofuel in the form of logging residues from the forest from the local area, the emissions from the transports are also low. Växjö municipality's overall goal is to become a fossil fuel-free municipality in 2030. The fact that Växjö Energi can now offer fossil fuel-free district heating and cooling is crucial to achieving that goal.

The principle on which district heating is based is that water circulates in a closed pipe system. The water is heated at the heat source, in our case the Sandviksverket, and is led out to properties where the heat is given off to the customers' heating and hot water systems. The cooled water is then led back to the heat source (cogeneration plant) to be reheated and led out again.

Type of Practice: Other

Type of Instrument: Regional Development planning

Region: SE/Växjö

Year Implemented: 2019

Implementation

Deployment setting: Urban

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: No Data available, however has been fossil free since 2019 and is crucial to a fossil fuel-free future in the municipality in 2030.

Years of operation: 4

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

The district heating, district cooling and electricity is produced from renewable biofuel from the forest. This makes use of and burn things that would otherwise have gone to waste - everything from bark and shavings to branches and tops. The ash that remains after burning is returned to the forest, which returns nourishment to nature. The expansion of the district heating network and the investment in biofuel-based district heating production have contributed to reducing emissions of fossil fuels in Växjö municipality by nearly 70 percent per inhabitant since 1993.

Social Impacts

Outside of the direct social impacts of a sustainable district system, the company carry out outreach programmes like a challenge programme with Linnaeus University Civil engineering students the task of taking on the role of production planner for electricity and heat production, where the students had to demonstrate strategic thinking, creativity, and perseverance.

Economic Impacts

A sustainable district heating system run on feedstocks that are completely renewable and would otherwise be discarded not only has a cost input benefit, but those cost savings follow through to the end user.

Replication Potential

Replication would be difficult in a region that does not have an established district heating system, due to the high infrastructural set up costs. However, the ethos can be taken up by other energy production entities in other regions and perhaps adapted to their own infrastructure.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.veab.se/om-oss/>

22: Green Business Models Programme

Problem Statement

SMEs lack the insight and overall knowledge of developing concrete and practical 'green' business models to develop a realistic and sustainable practical long term business model.

Executive Summary

An EU-backed initiative based in Denmark's Central Jutland region has helped several local SMEs to develop concrete and practical 'green' business models. The project, Focused value chain collaboration – design for optimal use of resources, helped participants become more sustainable and embrace the circular economy. Tailored business model support that has helped them optimise their value chains, making them more sustainable (and forcing their suppliers to become more sustainable).

Description

The programme coordinators began by screening 80 companies before selecting the participants. The SMEs were then matched with appropriate consultants who could understand their business needs and objectives. Assessments were carried out using the project's bespoke adviser exchange tool, as well as through phone interviews with company managers. Workshops were held and visits to companies took place as part of the comprehensive assessment process.

As business models were developed, companies were encouraged to embrace innovative methods to help make their processes more efficient. For example, some drafted a 'design letter' for a product or service that keeps materials in use for longer and which can be recycled with maximum efficiency. Participants also forged links with other businesses who could use waste and offcuts as raw material for their own products.

Type of Practice: Non-Financial Business Support

Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Finance

Region: DK/Central Jutland

Year Implemented: 2014

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: SMEs

Level of uptake: 80 companies applied before screening down to 39 successful participants.

Years of operation: 2014

Status: Not Active

Environmental Impacts

Introducing green business models has led to an estimated annual decrease in greenhouse gas emissions equivalent to 2 857 tonnes of CO₂ and a reduction in the use of energy and materials.

Social Impacts

Green business modelling is now part of the participating companies 'DNA' and has had a knock on effect, suppliers to these companies have become more sustainable as they need to follow the aims of the green business models enacted by their customers.

Economic Impacts

Sustainable business models will overtime become the norm. Companies that have already embraced this will find themselves at an economic advantage as business with fossil fuel-based supply chains come under the increasing cost pressure that will bring.

Replication Potential

This program is completely replicable and any region can adapt it to local industry that is interested in embracing greener business models.

Further Information

Website:

https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/projects/Denmark/green-business-modelling-brings-rewards-for-danish-smes

23: Ireland's Knowledge Centre for Carbon, Climate And Community Action (IKC3)

Problem Statement

To develop a transition to a decarbonized economy, Knowledge and Skills need to be developed within higher education to enable enterprise and society meet the priority skills needs that is needed.

Executive Summary

Funded as part of the Governments Future Jobs Initiative IKC3 has received funding from the Higher Education Authority (HEA) under the Human Capital Initiative 3 (HCI3) designed to deliver investment targeting increased capacity in higher education to meet priority skills needs which includes the Climate Change and Sustainable Living. The ICK3 will deploy a quintuple helix model of innovation to education, integrating state of the art pedagogies and learning pathways.

Description

The IKC3 project will develop a national platform for co-development and co-delivery of knowledge and skills to support and enable enterprise and society to adapt and transition to decarbonized economy and embrace sustainable living. Developed by a consortium of Munster Technological University, Trinity College Dublin, and University College Dublin and involves a wide-reaching network of partners involved with decarbonization, bioeconomy and climate change which include companies, enterprise clusters, local government, civic and social innovators. A sustainable, circular, low carbon economy is vital to meet the growing issue of climate change and within the first 3 years of the project a radical approach will be developed focusing on a quintuple helix model of innovation to education, integrating state of the art pedagogies and learning pathways. These will include stackable micro-courses, summer schools, dual and collaborative learning via deep learning demonstrations, micro-credentials, and digitization. The resulting platform will be able to adapt to the needs of new skills and knowledge that Ireland's higher education system can contribute towards decarbonization.

Type of Practice: Educational

Typology of Practice: Info & Advisory

Region: Ireland

Year Implemented: 2022

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: The project is still within its first year of operation but is linked through an extensive national and EU wide network of partners, including the European Institute of Innovation and Technology Climate-KIC, Sustainable Innovations Spain, European HEIs, companies, enterprise clusters, local government, civic and social innovators.

Years of operation: 1

Status:

Environmental Impacts

Over the course of the project the IKC3 will influence the development of higher education's response to the challenge of climate change and decarbonization. This will directly support enterprise and society to adapt and transition to decarbonized economy and embrace sustainable living.

Social Impacts

With the investment in increasing capacity within higher education, micro-courses, summer schools, dual and collaborative learning practices will be developed directly influencing society to adapt to the new realities that face us with climate change.

Economic Impacts

A primary motivator for the IKC3 project comes from the funding of the Human Capital Initiative 3 (HCI3) which is designed to deliver higher capacity in higher education, thus delivering the skills and knowledge that will drive enterprise adapt their businesses to be more resilient and sustainable in the years ahead.

Replication Potential

The framework is flexible and could be adapted for other regions.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.ittralee.ie/en/InformationAbout/NewsandEvents/News/MainContent,68507,en.html>

24: Edible Landscape Project CLG

Problem Statement

The issue of climate change has become a worrying and growing issue recently. Some children are very concerned or anxious about this issue and there is a need for educational material and guidance for teachers to guide children and assist learning in this area and lesson planning.

Executive Summary

ELP has devised a novel Education Program for Irish primary schools to encourage more schoolchildren to grow and consume food in an environmentally sustainable, climate smart way. This solution focused, Food Forest- Climate Education Program was developed by teachers, for teachers, and in November 2021 was launched in local primary schools in Co. Mayo.

Description

Empowering local communities to engage positively with climate change through education. The Edible Landscape Project want to make ethical decision-making regarding food choices and have integrity in everything they do. Understanding that the issue of climate change has become a worrying and growing issue recently. Some children are very concerned or anxious and the program we have compiled is intended to be a positive, solutions-based approach to the issue. Each of the strand units and learning outcomes are clearly stated as they are in the curriculum, to assist lesson planning. Participating primary school teachers receive a pack containing a set of Lesson Plans which are directly curriculum linked. The resources provided are intended to teach students how our food choices can have both a positive and negative impact on climate change. The Edible Landscape Project have devised a novel Education Program for Irish primary schools to encourage more schoolchildren to grow and consume food in an environmentally sustainable, climate smart way. This solution focused,

Type of Practice: Educational

Type of Instrument: Voluntary, Info & Advisory

Region: Ireland / Northwest / Mayo

Year Implemented: 2015

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Communities / Public

Level of uptake: Local schools in the area – limited due to resources.

Years of operation: 2

Status: Active

Food Forest- Climate Education Program was developed by teachers, for teachers, and in November 2021 was launched in local primary schools in Co. Mayo. Projects include TREE TOWNS INITIATIVE, BIA-AWARENESS (Grafting & Pruning), BIA-SECURITY, BIA-DIVERSITY (second level programme for transition years).

Environmental Impacts

Whilst still at a small scale, the program will as it expands increase knowledge of the bioeconomy and sustainability within younger generations will help develop sustainable approaches and thinking.

Social Impacts

The project is predominately a social one. The impacts in the schools participating have been immediate and an integral part of the school's culture. Children have become involved as a group, developing their sense of community, and learning what they can do to help climate change on a personal level and lowering their own social anxiety.

Economic Impacts

Whilst no current direct economic benefits exist, as the project grows the increased knowledge of the bioeconomy and sustainability within younger generations will help develop sustainable approaches and thinking.

Replication Potential

This project is unique in its approach to climate action and anxiety in the educational environment. Co-ordinators have not found any other project comparable within the European Union and they have not found any other with similar methodology or approach in terms of a systems thinking approach and using the food forest as a learning toolbox.

Further Information

Website:

<https://ediblelandscape.ie/>

2.3.8 Western Europe Cluster

As no regional government ROBIN partner were based in the Western Europe region, WHITE and task leader MTU led the collection of good practices in that jurisdiction. This was focused on the territories of Belgium, Luxembourg, and France. 12 good practices have been collected from the region. In this case the majority of these were Networking, Collaboration and Joint Planning instruments with Fiscal and Financial instruments also featuring strongly and a smaller number of examples across Information and Advisory instruments and Regulatory instruments.

The type of instruments is shown in Figure 37 below. The full list of good practices from Western Europe Region is outlined in Table 15, and the best practices from the region are included below.

Figure 37. Types of Good Practice in Western Europe Region

Table 15. Western Europe Good Practices

Good Practice Number	Good Practice Name	Jurisdiction, Country
1	Paris Region Sufficiency Factory	Île-de-France, France
2	Bio-based Circular Economy	Pays de la Loire, France
3	West Grid Synergy project	Mauges region, France
4	Reducing Bio-waste from Domestic Waste	Mauges region, France
5	DERVAL AGRI' METHANE site - (Farm carbon footprint reduction through fermentable waste valorization by anaerobic digestion)	Derval, France
6	"Terres Fert'île" (fertile island) project	L'île d'Yeu, France
7	Regional Biomass Scheme	Pays de la Loire, France
8	Catalisti	Flanders, Belgium
9	Blue Cluster	Flanders, Belgium
10	Moonshot	Flanders, Belgium
11	Ecological Investment Support in Flanders	Flanders, Belgium
12	Grand Est Bioeconomy Eco-System	Grand Est, France

1: Paris Region Sufficiency Factory

Problem Statement

Energy efficiency is no longer enough to counteract the increasing energy demand. The region of Ile-de-France aims to develop initiatives to promote energy efficiency.

Executive Summary

The Regional Energy and Climate Agency (AREC) by bringing together AREC and local actors, the think tank aims at supporting local authorities and enterprises to initiate and implement energy sufficiency strategies. To that end, capacity building sessions targeted electing people will be developed.

Description

With the organisation of the first regional conference on energy sufficiency in December 2021 allowed to present the activities of the working group engaged in the workshops organised since 2019. Indeed, workshops participants (experts, local authorities, enterprises, energy & environmental associations and AREC) developed an analysis of a fair, sustainable, desirable sufficiency for the region. Best practices and scenarios of sufficiency were presented by the national energy agency ADEME, AREC and energy agencies, but also universities, architects and sociologists who have highlighted the societal dimension of energy sufficiency.

Type of Practice: Social Innovation

Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning

Region: France/ Île-de-France

Year Implemented: 2019

The initiative will collect the regional, national, European, and global initiatives and highlight the best practices on cartographies and in videos. An assessment will be carried out on the indicators of success, levers and barriers, pilot, cost, targets, and specific objectives of such projects. This

Implementation

Deployment setting: Urban

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Communities/public

Level of uptake: No data

Years of operation: 4

Status: Active

assessment intends to build images of energy sufficiency in the Ile-de-France region that make it appealing, based on the sociology and behaviour of individuals and organisations. They also aim to formulate recommendations for a regional energy sufficiency approach that will enable Ile-de-France local authorities to get on board by examining the levers to be activated and the barriers to be removed and help local authorities commit to a long-term approach and build their own narrative.

Environmental Impacts

Yes, the initiative aims to inform people on how to change their behaviour regarding energy and how to build the capacity to save energy. This initiative has long-term environmental impact.

Social Impacts

The initiative brings together multiple actors to support local authorities and enterprises to initiate and implement energy sufficiency strategies. To that end, capacity building sessions targeted electing people will be developed.

Economic Impacts

In a long-term perspective the energy sufficiency practices will result to reduced cost of energy bills.

Replication Potential

Yes, there is replication potential to other regions as well.

Further Information

Website:

<https://fedarene.org/best-practice/energy-sufficiency-in-the-ile-de-france-region/>

2: *Bio-based circular economy*

Problem Statement

Limited information and understanding exists within the public realm towards the bioeconomy and this is acting as a barrier to the further development of a bio-based circular economy.

Executive Summary

Awareness raising campaign to inform the citizens further on the topic of agriculture, agrifood and fishing.

Description

The public still largely remains uninformed about the bioeconomy. They require more information and background knowledge to form an opinion on it. What is clear, however, is that public engagement is critical to improve the public acceptance of the bioeconomy, including bio-based products and processes. Improving knowledge, education and awareness plays a key role in securing citizen's support for the bioeconomy, but other aspects are pertinent as well, involving civil society and reinforcing the regional dimension. This paper provides recommendations on how to effectively put these objectives in practice.

Type of Practice: Other

Type of Instrument: Info & Advisory

Region: France/ Pays de la Loire

Year Implemented: 2019

The Pays de la Loire (Western France) regional council approved a circular economy action plan in October 2019, which identified the agrifood industry and maritime industry as high potential sectors, amongst others. Together with other stakeholders in the BIOREGIO project, the regional council published a roadmap called "Biobased Circular Economy Action Plan" to foster the biobased circular economy in Pays de la Loire. This has proven to be a useful starting point for developing a sustainable and circular bioeconomy strategy at the regional level.

The Roadmap identifies agriculture, agrifood and fishing as the leading economic sectors in the Pays de la Loire Region and elaborates on four actions that are implemented over the period 2020-2021; communication, awareness raising and information based on concrete examples; enhancing the bio-based circular economy component in the Circular Economy Regional Call for Projects; enhancing supervision and coherence of initiatives on the territory; and implementing action research involving research laboratory and local authorities.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Coastal

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: No data

Years of operation: 4

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Increasing the knowledge of circular economy practices could have a long-term environmental impact as the bio-based circular economy develops within the region.

Social Impacts

This good practice has a more direct social impact since it targets society and aims to raise awareness to the public on the bioeconomy potential.

Economic Impacts

Increasing the knowledge of circular economy practices could have a long-term economic impact.

Replication Potential

Yes, there is replication potential to other regions as well.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.ecologic.eu/sites/default/files/publication/2021/2813-Improving-the-public-acceptance-of-bio-based-products-and-processes.pdf>

3: West Grid Synergy project

Problem Statement

Promote green gas production to provide network solutions for several energy intensive industries. Deployment of digital technology on gas networks will enable all types of consumers to control their consumption, producers to better manage their installations, local authorities to better manage their action plans and network managers to be more efficient in managing and operating their networks.

Executive Summary

The West Grid Synergy Project aims to increase the use of green gas. The West Grid Synergy Project enables the commissioning of 43km pilot-scale biogas backbone in Mauges region will ensure that green gas production meets consumption, connect 3 anaerobic digestion (AD) units, provide network solution for several energy-intensive industries, serve new natural gas municipalities and enable development of mobility specific to CNG (aka Compressed Natural Gas) /bio-GNV (the renewable version of NGV - Natural Gas Vehicle).

Description

The project focuses on new technical solutions and infrastructures and raising awareness, acceptability, involvement, and support for local and regional actors of the gas networks of tomorrow.

Commissioning of 43km pilot-scale biogas backbone in Mauges region will ensure that green gas production meets consumption, connect 3 anaerobic digestion units, provide network solution for several energy-intensive industries, serve new natural gas municipalities and enable development of mobility specific to CNG/bio-GNV. Deployment of digital technology on gas networks will enable all types of consumers to control their consumption, producers to better manage their installations, local authorities to better manage their action plans and network managers to be more efficient in managing and operating their networks.

Type of Practice: Other

Type of Instrument: Regulatory

Region: France/ Mauges region

Year Implemented: 2018

This digital revolution is essential for raising awareness among the population and for involving users and territories in energy issues. Innovative predictive maintenance solutions will be tested to enable gas network infrastructures to provide better service at the lowest cost. Flexibility throughout the value chain will be enabled by developing synergies between energy networks with the electricity grid. It also involves development of new hybrid technologies that promote energy synergies for domestic and industrial consumers.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Urban

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Large Companies

Level of uptake: No Data

Years of operation: 5

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Already in progress The Mauges biogas backbone connects to the gas network and the meshes of the Pontivy Community distribution network merge consumption loops. These developments have favored the emergence of biomethane production projects, the absorption of their production being secured locally.

Social Impacts

The initiative brings together multiple actors and with Deployment of digital technology on gas networks will enable all types of consumers to control their consumption, producers to better manage their installations, local authorities to better manage their action plans and network managers to be more efficient in managing and operating their networks.

Economic Impacts

Promoting green gas production will maximise the integration of renewable energy in the territories at the best cost, improving the efficiency of natural gas networks with digital technology.

Replication Potential

No foreseen barriers to replication where infrastructure exists.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.interregeurope.eu/good-practices/west-grid-synergy-project-wgs-project>

<https://www.westgridsynergy.fr/>

4: Reducing bio-waste from domestic waste

Problem Statement

The operational costs of household waste disposal were increasing every year, so a waste management trade union proposed this practice to reduce the costs of household waste disposal.

Executive Summary

Initiative that aims to incentivize households to separate waste and use composters.

Description

Prior to the project, waste was collected every week, whereas a study showed that not every household would take trash bins outside for disposal (only 10% would) or that trash bins would be only half full. To allow households to separate and treat their fermentable waste at source, Mauges Communauté has supplied composters. Households wishing to install a composter had to pay a contribution, 50% of the price was being paid by Mauges Communauté thanks to funding from the Environment and Energy Agency (ADEME). 10,000 households have been equipped with composters. The composter came with a user guide, and an advisor was available to explain how to use it. Mauges Communauté has therefore implemented a waste management program, collecting trash every 15 days in an automated way and invoicing households per number and volume of trash bins treated. Thus, households were financially incentivised to reduce their quantity of waste.

Type of Practice: Public Procurement
Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial
Region: France/ Mauges region
Year Implemented: 2019

To reduce waste production biowaste had to be removed from domestic waste. Mauges Communauté has supplied composters to allow households to separate and treat their fermentable waste at source. Households wishing to install a composter had to pay a contribution, 50% of the price being paid by Mauges Communauté thanks to funding from the Environment and Energy Agency.

Funding stopped but Mauges Communauté continues to provide composters and to finance half for households wishing to get one. As a result, the number of households with a composter is constantly increasing, and the implementation of collective composters has started.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Urban

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Communities/public

Level of uptake: 10,000 households have been equipped with composters.

Years of operation: 3

Status: Not Active - ADEME funding stopped but Mauges Communauté continues to provide composters and to finance half for households wishing to get one. Thus, the number of households with a composter is constantly increasing, and the implementation of collective composters has started.

Environmental Impacts

Reducing operational costs of household waste incentivizes citizens to divide the waste collected.

Social Impacts

Could be considered as a collective effort and that could have a social impact. This can be directly seen by the continuation of the practice once the funding stopped.

Economic Impacts

Reducing operation costs of household waste.

Replication Potential

No foreseen barriers to replication, however, there has to be education to the use of the composters to be successful. The Mauges Communauté composter came with a user guide, and an advisor was available to explain how to use it.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.interregeurope.eu/good-practices/reducing-biowaste-from-domestic-waste>

<https://www.maugescommunaute.fr/des-services/gestion-des-dechets/>

5: DERVAL AGRI' METHANE site - (Farm carbon footprint reduction)

Problem Statement

To address the problem of waste and livestock manure production, the SAS DERVAL AGRI'METHANE company set up an anaerobic digestion (AD) site in the municipality.

Executive Summary

Organic effluents from local farms and bio-waste are being recycled and their recovery results in the production of hot water which is being used to supply multiple networks and a school.

Description

The region of Derval is home to many farms and industries. In order to address the problem of waste and livestock manure production, the SAS DERVAL AGRI'METHANE company set up an anaerobic digestion site in the municipality in 2016. This territorial and multi-partnership anaerobic digestion unit results from a complementary collaboration between SUEZ (waste treatment & disposal company), Chambre of Agriculture of Loire Atlantique, vocational school Saint Clair de Derval, LAD-SELA (economic and construction company), and 5 local agricultural holdings.

Type of Practice: Other

Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning

Region: France/ Derval

Year Implemented: 2016

DERVAL AGRI' METHANE (DAM) is equipped with the following AD installations; a digester with an actual volume of 2492 m³ and a post-digester of the same volume. The storage volume of the biogas is 2,400 m³ distributed over the digester and the post- digester. The AD unit recycles organic effluents from 5 partner farms as well as bio-waste collected by SUEZ (waste treatment and disposal company): it makes possible to recycle these products while emitting a high quality digestate. The recovery of this fermentable waste results in production of thermal energy (hot water), which is used internally to run production equipment's, delivers heating to the network for intermunicipal aquatic complex and Derval school.

Finally, a phase separation allows the production of liquid and solid digestate: the latter are returned to the surrounding farms for spreading on fields. DERVAL AGRI' METHANE (DAM) then is an important local actor in bio-based circular economy.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Urban

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: 15 agricultural holdings and 11 municipalities

Years of operation: 2016

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

There are many direct impacts, renewable energy production that replaces fossil energy, digestate that replaces synthetic fertilisers and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions amongst others.

Social Impacts

This good practice brings together farmers, local authorities, the State and the Chamber of Agriculture, and a school, in the context of fermentable waste recovery.

Economic Impacts

Thermal energy produced by fermentable waste could be a cheaper solution in comparison with the traditional way of energy supply. To farmers it provides a reduction in costs for nutrients and creation of a new income.

Replication Potential

Local structures (15 agricultural holdings and 11 municipalities) benefit from thermal energy produced as well as from digestates: the spreading has just started (located within a radius of less than 25 km around the plot of the AD unit), and farmers are enthusiastic.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.interregeurope.eu/good-practices/farm-carbon-footprint-reduction-through-fermentable-waste-valorization-by-anaerobic-digestion>

6: "Terres Fert'île" (fertile island) project

Problem Statement

Lack of farming land and farmers' concern about saturating the local market.

Executive Summary

Actions have been deployed to provide new farming lands to local actors so they could take bigger advantage of the local production.

Description

"Terres Fert'île" (fertile island) project started in 2014 in order to increase local food production. Partners include city council, local farmers, and citizens through local organizations. Strategic focus has been put on identifying obstacles and removing them. Other actions have focused on better understanding local market and on finding ways to increase outlet for local production. Kitchens in schools and senior housing have been identified as potential partners and workshops have been organised to pinpoint how to promote a more important proportion of local production in their supplies.

Type of Practice: Other
Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning
Region: France/ L'Ile d'Yeu
Year Implemented: 2014

Further on the bio-based circular economy, a program has been implemented to reduce and reuse organic waste. These actions range from reducing food waste to promoting composting. For example, green waste is transformed into compost with an accelerated process in a new facility.

Partners from the city council, local farmers, and citizens through local organizations are collaborating with the aim to identify obstacles and remove them. Two main issues have been identified: lack of farming land and farmers' concern about saturating local market. Actions have been deployed to provide new farming lands: identification of abandoned lands in agriculture-compatible areas, research of owners, clearing of wild lands. Other actions have focused on better

Implementation

Deployment setting: Coastal

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Communities/public

Level of uptake: More than 600

Years of operation: 9

Status: Active

understanding local market and on finding ways to increase outlet for local production. Kitchens in schools and senior housing have been identified as potential partners and workshops have been organised to pinpoint how to promote a more important proportion of local production in their supplies.

Environmental Impacts

15 000 m² of new farmland was created within the project as well as a reduction of 7% of total waste shipped from the island and that increased to 31% reduction from household waste.

Social Impacts

3 workshops for kitchen workers of school and senior housing restaurants and 30 workshops on composting, food waste and gardening which had an attendance of over 600 people.

Economic Impacts

Supporting local economy and buy local products.

Replication Potential

Operations on waste reductions are not new but the specificities of the island can help other territories to find solutions to small-scale problems.

The Terres Fertile initiative is a comprehensive project focusing on the problem of food production in a very small territory. The implication of all local actors (municipality, farmers, associations, and volunteers) and the way they managed to work together can be an interesting example to study for similar projects.

Further Information

Website:

<https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/good-practices/item/2949/food-production-and-waste-disposal-on-an-island-local-loop-on-l-ile-d-yeu/>

7: Regional Biomass Scheme

Problem Statement

Energy transition for green growth defines ambitious objectives for the development of renewable energies, in particular energies produced from biomass.

Executive Summary

Promote the development of projects on converting biomass into energy: heating networks, wood-fired boilers, anaerobic digestion and biogas use to reduce fossil fuels.

Description

The objectives of the regional biomass plan are to draw up an inventory of the biomass resources likely to have an energy use and to determine the orientations and actions to be implemented at the regional or infra-regional scale to encourage the mobilization of these resources and the development of the corresponding energy sectors. The biomass scheme is part of a set of public policies aimed at moving towards a “low carbon” economy . The use of biomass, a renewable resource with a low carbon footprint, is set to increase in the years to come in many sectors of activity: for food, materials, green chemistry, energy, etc. Compared to these different uses of biomass, energy production represents a lower added value and is very often used as a “last resort”.

Type of Practice: Other

Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning

Region: Belgium / Flanders

Year Implemented: 2019

Consisting of two parts, the scheme is essentially an inventory which has identified significant biomass resources that can be mobilized in Pays de la Loire for energy recovery, from agriculture, forestry, wood industries and bio-waste and a quantitative objective for the mobilization of these resources by 2030 as well as the regional and sub-regional measures to be implemented to achieve these objectives.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: 160 members

Years of operation: 4

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Reducing production of chemicals and plastics from fossil fuels, as well as pollution reduction through recycling, and production biodegradable plastics. The inventory carried out as part of the development of the regional biomass plan shows that the Pays de la Loire region offers considerable potential for biomass resources. Additional resources can also be mobilized by 2030 without calling into question the natural balance and making it possible to envisage the production of local renewable energy.

Social Impacts

The Scheme also aims to mobilize local players (farmers, communities, companies, scientists, associations, citizens) in the recovery of biomass, which constitutes a real asset for the territories. It is indeed a source of wealth creation offering local benefits.

Economic Impacts

The exploitation of this additional biomass would make it possible to better maintain the bocages and forests, to promote their renewal and the storage of carbon. A virtuous circle reinforced by the complementarity of the sectors of construction, which uses mature wood, and energy production, which uses coproducts from the management and processing of wood.

Replication Potential

No foreseen barriers to replication, however the national and regional strategies did promote and underpin this practice and this would be an important factor in the initial implementation.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.pays-de-la-loire.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/schema-regional-biomasse-srb-r1824.html>

http://www.pays-de-la-loire.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/doc_com_9p_plaquette_biomasse_web.pdf

Problem Statement

The chemical and plastics industries are becoming more and more unsustainable both from a resources point of view and on a cost basis as fossil-based inputs face supply issues.

Executive Summary

Their mission is to actively contribute to sustainable and competitive chemical & plastics industries, as well as related sectors in Flanders, by working on new value chains, improved innovation power, clustering knowledge, and a sustainable economy.

Description

As a spearhead cluster, they build partnerships between companies, universities, research institutes, associations and governments in Flanders. Through high-impact innovation projects, they support members in accelerating innovation into business. The cluster identifies and initiates collaborative innovation projects aimed at creating new sustainable business opportunities for members. Through open innovation projects with support from the Flemish government, they champion cooperation throughout the industrial value chain to facilitate industrial innovations. Their expertise lies in combining expertise across sectors and disciplines and making innovation central to the clusters members. The cluster works with likeminded companies, sectors, other clusters, and international peers.

Type of Practice: Networking
Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning
Region: Belgium / Flanders
Year Implemented: 2019

They facilitate alignment and agreement between project partners and have the necessary competences to facilitate grant applications for projects and fulfilling members needs by offering specific services and by enabling collaborations with innovative partners to quickly come to concrete solutions.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Coastal

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: 160 members

Years of operation: 4

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Reducing production of chemicals and plastics from fossil fuels, as well as pollution reduction through recycling, and production biodegradable plastics.

Social Impacts

This good practice brings together multiple actors from numerous industries interested a holistic approach to sustainable practices.

Economic Impacts

As a spearhead cluster, Catalisti build partnerships between companies, universities, research institutes, associations, and governments in Flanders. Through high-impact innovation projects, we support our members in accelerating innovation into business.

Replication Potential

No foreseen barriers to replication, however key to their success to date is support from the Flemish government and innovative holistic approach, which would be key to replication in another region.

Further Information

Website:

<https://catalisti.be>

Problem Statement

The blue economy already accounts for almost 154,000 full-time jobs in Flanders and for more than 5% of the Flemish GDP. Blue Cluster wants to stimulate the blue economy even more by facilitating innovation with respect for people, planet and prosperity.

Executive Summary

Blue Cluster is 100% committed to stimulating blue growth in Flanders and creating maximum positive impact for its members and partners. They do so by building cross-sectoral networks, stimulating innovation and drawing up a joint "blue" strategy.

Description

At the end of 2017, Colruyt, DEME, Econopolis, INVE, Jan De Nul, Sioen Industries, Tractebel Engineering, Vanbreda Risk & Benefits, Vyncke and ZERI set up the non-profit organization Blue Cluster. The aim is to set up improved, cross-sectoral partnerships and closer cooperation between knowledge centres and government institutions to encourage new investments and realize innovative projects in the Belgian part of the North Sea and beyond.

Type of Practice: Networking

Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning

Region: Belgium / Flanders

Year Implemented: 2019

To provide optimal support to members and partners and to achieve sustainable blue growth, Blue Cluster focuses on three pillars: 1) Networking: Networking is at the heart of what we do. They cross traditional industry boundaries and bring together SMEs and corporates, public agencies, academic research groups, education, and end users from both Flanders and abroad. 2) Innovation: Networking generates innovative ideas. Blue Cluster helps turn these ideas into concepts and projects, step by step. 3) Strategy: Innovation, in turn, deepens our knowledge of the blue economy and helps us define the right strategic course for blue growth in Flanders.

Aiming to de-risk innovation The Blue Cluster is a bottom-up initiative and not the continuation of an existing organization. The connecting factor is based on the link with the sea, where there is a need for far-reaching cooperation between sectors that traditionally cooperate less often.

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: 32 projects

Years of operation: 4

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Blue Cluster brings together entrepreneurs, researchers, policy makers and citizens to design sustainable business models, set up creative partnerships and develop groundbreaking technology within the blue economy. As the seas and oceans account for 71% of our planet a sustainable blue bioeconomy will protect that.

Social Impacts

The Flemish blue bioeconomy accounts for 150,000 full time jobs, further growing this crucial aspect of the economy will bring the inherent benefits than come from a string sustainably resilient sector.

Economic Impacts

The blue bioeconomy accounts for than 5% of Flemish GDP, the cluster wants to stimulate the blue economy even more by facilitating innovation.

Replication Potential

This is replicable in regions with similar geographic attributes as the Flemish coast.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.blauwecluster.be>

10: Moonshot

Problem Statement

In 2016, industrial sectors accounted for 36% (27.9 million ton of CO₂ equivalent), or more than a third, of all greenhouse gas emissions in Flanders (77.7 Mt CO₂ eq).

Executive Summary

Flemish universities, research institutes and industries develop breakthrough technologies by 2040 to create new climate-friendly processes and products. Innovation will help Flemish industries make the big leap: carbon circular and low in CO₂ by 2050.

Description

Meeting 2030/2050 climate commitments will require a radical reduction of CO₂ and other greenhouse gas emissions, the most important driving force behind global warming. The Flemish government, for example, supports the European long-term objective of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 80-95% by 2050 compared to 1990. To do so, Flanders will need an ambitious approach to break with the past and achieve a more sustainable society. As a significant source of CO₂ emissions, the Flemish industry has a key role to play in shifting to a more sustainable society. Through breakthrough technologies, the Flemish industry can translate climate ambitions into climate actions. This is where the idea for a long-term industrial innovation programme, a Moonshot project was envisioned.

Type of Practice: Financial Business Support

Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial

Region: Belgium / Flanders

Year Implemented: 2019

From 2020 to 2040, the Flemish Government is investing EUR 20 million in Flanders Industry Innovation Moonshot every year, totalling 400 million euro. These funds will, through innovative research, enable the development of breakthrough technologies by 2040. Thanks to these

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: 71 companies participate in first industrial Advisory Boards in 2021.

Years of operation: 4

Status: Active

technologies, the Flemish industry will be able to implement new climate-friendly processes and produce new climate-friendly products. These innovative products and processes will help Flanders to make the big leap: making its industry carbon circular and low in CO₂ by 2050, reducing its CO₂ emissions, and meeting its climate commitments.

Environmental Impacts

Considering ten-year investment cycles, the combined 2040 and 2050 targets give the Flemish industry a ten-year window to implement breakthrough technologies, become carbon circular and low in CO₂ by 2050, and support Flanders in fulfilling its climate commitments.

Social Impacts

Close cooperation across clusters, sectors and industries will ensure that breakthrough technologies are efficiently and effectively adopted across the Flemish industrial landscape. This way, cross-sectoral synergies and spill overs can be fully exploited.

Economic Impacts

To meet these targets, the Flemish Government will invest €20 million in the Moonshot initiative every year from 2020 to 2040, totalling €400 million.

Replication Potential

This practice can be put into place at a national level in other countries, however the Flemish government is backing the initiative with a substantial capital investment and that too would have to be replicated.

Further Information

Website:

<https://moonshotflanders.be/>

11: Ecological Investment Support in Flanders

Problem Statement

Expense of environmental and sustainable energy technologies can be hindering to wide-scale uptake.

Executive Summary

This measure provides a financial incentive to companies that are going to make ecological investments in the Flemish Region. In this way, the Flemish government hopes to encourage investments in cutting-edge green technology (technology that by its unique business-specific character cannot be standardised).

Description

The Ecology Premium Plus (EP-Plus) is only granted to investments in technologies that feature on a limitative technology list or LTL. This list contains about 30 technologies within 3 categories: environmental technologies; energy technologies; renewable energy and combined heat and power. The Strategic Ecology Support (STRES) is an additional funding tool for companies using technologies which – due to their exceptional and unique character – do not feature on the LTL list and are being deployed in ‘strategic’ environmental projects. With this ecology bonus, Flanders’ government aims to encourage companies to organize production processes in an eco-friendlier and energy-efficient way by funding part of the additional costs involved in such an investment. The ecology bonus amounts to 20%, 30% or 40% of the additional costs, depending on the scope of the enterprise and technology.

With the ecology premium, the Government of Flanders wants to encourage companies to organize their production process in a sustainable, climate-friendly, circular, and energy-efficient way, and is thereby paying part of the extra investment costs that such an investment entail.

Type of Practice: Financial Business Support

Type of Instrument: Fiscal & Financial

Region: Belgium / Flanders

Year Implemented: 2013

Implementation

Deployment setting: Multiple

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: No Data available

Years of operation: 10

Status: Active

Environmental Impacts

Reducing emissions through renewable energy technologies and other environmental technologies. Companies with one or more large energy-intensive sites in the Flemish Region can only receive an ecology premium plus if these sites have acceded to the Flemish energy policy agreements and also comply with them .

Social Impacts

Not Applicable.

Economic Impacts

The total amount of ecology premiums awarded is a maximum of € 1 million per company over a period of 3 years, counting from the date of submission of the first positively decided aid application. A specific subsidy like this aims to develop sustainable practice amongst existing industries and new industrial initiatives.

Replication Potential

No foreseen barriers to replication, however subsidies of this nature do require monitoring and oversight to ensure adherence.

Further Information

Website:

<https://www.flandersinvestmentandtrade.com/invest/en/investing-in-flanders/grant-incentives/flanders-actively-supports-ecological-investments>

12: Grand Est Bioeconomy Eco-System

Problem Statement

Increasing capacity and innovation within the bioeconomy in rural regions can be a challenge for rural stakeholders.

Executive Summary

The Grand Est Bioeconomy Ecosystem, with its centre point of the Pomacle Bazancourt Biorefinery, represents a long standing and leading example of a cooperative based regional biorefinery which fully integrates farmers, industry, research, and regional government in a competitive and sustainable business model.

Description

The Pomacle-Bazancourt biorefinery is based on the continuing development of the Crisal Union cooperative since the 1950s. In the 1990s, the site acquired an agro-industrial complex with the construction of a starch-glucose factory operated by the Chamtor company and an innovation centre, through the launch of a research centre shared between beet growers and cereals, Agro-industry Research and Development (ARD). After this point, policy supports occurs to ensure the development of the site and many different companies join the movement.

Today, the Bazancourt-Pomacle biorefinery is a multi-company ecosystem, which mainly transforms wheat and beet to produce products intended for the food industries – a priority – but also to the chemical, cosmetic, pharmaceutical industries ticks, the packing and packaging industry, fuels and combustibles...but also a site that hosts an innovation platform to cover a wide field of investigations, from the laboratory research stage to the industrial demonstration. One of the most important

Type of Practice: Networking

Type of Instrument: Networking, Collaboration & Joint Planning, Info & Advisory

Region: France, Grand Est

Year Implemented: 1948

Implementation

Deployment setting: Rural

Stakeholder beneficiaries: Multiple

Level of uptake: The initiative has expanded with new businesses being developed on site over time.

Years of operation: 75

Status: Active

success factors, was the strong dedication from all local authorities (the Marne department, then the Champagne-Ardenne region and finally Reims Métropole) to develop the site.

Environmental Impacts

4 million tons of biomass processed annually, producing food and feed, but also biofuels, biobased chemicals, cosmetics, and other products. In addition, the site enables participants and companies to use resources much more sustainably, through sharing of material and energy resources, steam and CO2 capture in a model of industrial symbiosis.

Social Impacts

The cooperative structure has enabled farmers to share in value creation in a sustainable model. The campus also has close relationships with several local educational institute and allows access to programmes for students to learn about the campus activities.

Economic Impacts

The site has enabled more companies to join seeking innovation for sustainable product development. The sharing of resources allows companies to reduce their cost, but the eco-system, along with pilot and demonstration facilities creates a collaborative environment for development of new business ideas. The site has allowed the region to diversity its produce and opened new markets, while also attracting new companies to the region.

Replication Potential

In the region, many other sites followed the example to structure a real bioeconomy ecosystem with the support of local authorities.

Further Information

Website:

<https://rubizmo.eu/attachment/render/c4ee5fa9-7dcc-4ea3-b880-6061d44fd7ef>

2.4 Take home messages from Good Practice Analysis

An inventory 75 Good Governance Practices for Supporting Local Operators and Innovation developers in the Circular Bioeconomy were collected from diverse regions across Europe and analysed as part of Section 4. These Good Practices were classified according to the Typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models developed by the ROBIN project, and from these good practices 10 case studies were highlighted to showcase the potential of good practices across a broad range of instruments. The following are the main take home messages from the analysis.

- Good practices have been sourced from right across Europe. Many of the most impactful of these are occurring in the Mediterranean, Central, Northern and Western Europe, as indicated by the selected case studies, but many interesting examples can also be found in the Balkan and Eastern European Regions
- The largest share of practices was primarily linked to fiscal and financial instruments as well as networking, collaboration, and joint planning instruments, in addition to information and advisory instruments, with a smaller share of practices focused on regulatory instruments and voluntary instruments. However, many of the practices overlap between multiple instruments.
- The main transformation paths linked to these practices are the substitution of fossil fuels and developing more efficient biomass uses, with less emphasis on boosting primary sector productivity, and achieving value creation and addition from biomass.
- There is a good balance of enabling government function options seen within the practices, including awareness raising, bio-based R&D strategy, and subsidies.
- From the information collected, a lack of consideration around the constraints or risks associated with implementing ambitious bio-based practices or strategies may exist. More consideration needs to be given to the potential negative consequences of increasing biomass use on other aspects of the environment and society.
- The role of industry and society, in buying into bioeconomy models, to complement government efforts e.g., through triple or quadruple helix models is critical to achieve wider uptake.
- The development of penta-helix models of collaboration, which involves capital, is currently under-represented and will be essential to include in order to achieve scale within the bioeconomy.

Conclusions

From the analysis of T1.2 it was possible to identify 75 good governance practices for supporting local operators and innovation developers in circular bioeconomy. The practices cover 24 countries from across Europe. These are practices which have demonstrated positive results, have been tested and validated and have been or can be transferred or replicated. The practices cover a wide variety of types from funding programmes to incubators, incentive and procurement programmes, regulations, education and networking activities and social innovations. They are broadly across fiscal and financial instruments, regulatory instruments, information and advisory instruments, networking, collaboration and joint planning instruments, voluntary instruments, other instruments.

The good practices also cover a wide variety of deployment settings including urban, rural, coastal, peri-urban and uplands helping to ensure that the bioeconomy can be promoted in different territorial contexts. Most of the identified practices are applicable in multiple territorial settings. They also support and involve different stakeholders across primary production, research and development, public administration, business, and society, delivering economic, environmental, and societal impact for their regions.

From our inventory of good practices, we have selected 10 case studies to showcase, covering different geographical and territorial contexts, and covering different types including social media awareness campaigns, public procurement initiatives, social innovations, regulatory initiatives, and business models and sustainable community-based innovations.

Practices gathered within this report will be further analysed through WP2 within ROBIN regions as the regions co-design good governance models and practices. The information will also be useful to bioeconomy regions with different territorial contexts and needs to identify the types of practices available for supporting bioeconomy development within their regions.

In addition, the inventory developed in this report has been classified based on a new typology for Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models developed within the ROBIN project. This analysis has produced interesting findings and shows that while there are a lot of great, and transferrable, examples working well to support bioeconomy in the European region, there are still challenges that exist to ensure that the models can achieve their full potential.

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Annexes

Annex I – Case Study Guide

The Following Case Study Guide was used as guidance for MTU/S2i & AUTh when completing the case studies:

Instructions For Case Study Developers

Description of Task:

Task 1.3: Collection of Good Governance Practices for Supporting Local Operators and Innovation developers in the Circular Bioeconomy (M1-M6) (Leader: MTU, support by: All)

This task will perform a deep dive into good practices of regional governments supporting local operators and innovation developers via appropriate business models and social measures. A screening exercise will help us make an inventory (long list) of 50 good practices within and outside the ROBIN regions. Then, the good practices will be assessed against specific criteria to select a list of 10 cases to be further studied. Partners MTU, AUTh and S2i will develop at least 10 case studies showcasing how regional government has encouraged social innovation and business models to promote circular bioeconomy. The long list of good practices will be classified under the typology of T1.2, providing practical inspiration for our regions to improve their governance models. The results will be reported in D1.2.

Summary of assignment:

A series of good governance practice case studies will be developed that will exemplify the best of the 50 examples collected by the ROBIN partners. These 10 case studies will be based on the meeting specific criteria of best practice, while also ensuring a diversity of practice types, and give an in-depth overview of how these regional good governance practices have encouraged social innovation and business models to promote the circular bioeconomy.

Selection Criteria:

Define Selection methodology based upon Good Practices definitions (From Kick Off Presentation):

Various organisations have offered their interpretations as to what criteria lead to a practice being defined as ‘good’; most notably the FAO and ENRD

“A good practice is not only a practice that is good, but a practice that has been proven to work well and produce good results, and it is therefore recommended as a model. It is a successful experience, which has been tested and validated, in the broad sense, which has been repeated and deserves to be shared so that a greater number of people can adopt it” (FAO, 2013)

“Good practice” (ENRD, 2018) refers to strategies, programmes, projects, procedures, management, and implementation practices that should be at least:

- Implemented with positive results.
- Successful, (innovative), tested and validated: it contributes to the improved performance of an entrepreneurship/farm/organisation and this contribution is recognised.
- Transferable: it can be adopted in and adapted to other contexts.

Implementing the case study:

To ensure that each case study is similar in length and detail, the case study description shall follow as much as practically possible a standard format. The types of questions to be addressed are described in table below.

Following selection of the 10 good governance practices that are to be developed into case studies, other than an interview with a stakeholder involved with the good practice, there is no prescribed method or format to gather relevant data and information from internet, literature etc. on which the case study is to be based.

Suitable resources to supplement the interview may include the following:

- news items / articles (online, in trade journals, regional policy/strategy documents, etc.)
- conference proceedings
- formal literature
- As a minimum (one or several) interviews with good practice stakeholders.

For attractive reading, use of direct quotes from stakeholders is encouraged where permitted. It is necessary to inform (prospective) case study subjects and reach prior agreement prior to conducting the interview on organisation issues and practicalities.

Planning:

It is recommended that all three case study developers (MTU, AUTh and S2I) collaborate and develop a plan for implementing their case studies:

Activities to be covered in the plan development may include for each of the case studies:

- Engage with the selected stakeholder to collect information and quotes that can be used (commencement of interviews from 15th December to 20th January)
- Develop the case study (several iterations) (by relevant partner MTU, AuTh, S2i) (submission of final case studies to MTU by 20th of January)
- Consolidate the final 10 case studies and integrate alongside other good practices in D1.2 (by ROBIN partner MTU)

Format:

Length: 3-4 pages (1300 - 1700 words) Font: Arial Size:11 Spacing:1.5

Photos: Minimum of 2 per case study with permission (can also include logo where appropriate)

Theme / Category	Question / Guidance
Background of region in which good practice waste demonstrated	Provide some information about the region in which the good practice was demonstrated - the country and local situation. In what type of deployment setting did this take place (urban, rural, coastal etc?). At what stage of development is the bioeconomy at within this region? Does the local government place an active role in the bioeconomy development - if so, how?

Theme / Category	Question / Guidance
Context for deployment of good practice	What specific challenges were the good practices aiming to address? Was there baseline information available to assess the status of the situation? What was the inspiration/foundation for the implementation of the good practice? Who were involved in its development and how difficult was it to bring to fruition?
Implementation of the good practice	What steps were taken to launch the good practice? When was the good practice implemented and how long has it been implemented for? What has the uptake level being like and what type of stakeholders have benefited from the practice?
Involvement of regional government or public bodies in the development of the practice	Where relevant, describe the role of regional government or public bodies in developing or supporting the practice.
Results of Good Practice	What has been the result of implementation of the good practice? How have you measured/assessed this? Has it been successful in achieving the initial aims (if so, indicated how)? Has it delivered specific contributions on economic, environmental, and social sustainability in the context of the region's bioeconomy – if so, please describe how (be as quantitative as possible e.g., number of stakeholders, emissions reduction contribution etc).
Replication of Good Practice	Is there interest from other regions/bodies in relation to replication of this practice? Do you know if it has been replicated in other regions? If so, which regions? Do you see potential for its replication to other regions? If not, why not. If so, is it suitable for implementation in all regions, or specific regions (what are the dynamics required for replication). Are there barriers that regions should be prepared for if implementation this practice.
Case Study examples	Are there any specific case studies in your region you can mention which have benefited from the practice (e.g., a success case). This could be a company who has scaled, new products on the market, a specific target of regional government that has been achieved and so on.
Lessons Learned from Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lessons learned. What worked well? What did not work so well? What unexpected barriers had to be overcome? What would you do different (or in another order) next time? • Further take-home messages.
Future plans	Are there any future plans for development of the good practice
Further Information	References (relevant literature for further reading)

Annex 2 – Data Collection Template

The Following data collection template was used by partners when collecting the initial information for the long list of good practices:

<p>ROBIN DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH</p>		
Collection of Good Governance Practices for Supporting Local Operators and Innovation developers in the Circular Bioeconomy		
T1.3- Collection of Good Governance Practices for Supporting Local Operators and Innovation developers in the Circular Bioeconomy		
WP n° and title	WP1 – Setting the Scene	
Date	26/10/2022	
Version	Final	
<p>This Excel file will act as a Database for good practices to be identified during the project. Please fill in the "Database" sheet the information about the practices you identify. Each row of the "Database" sheet gathers information for one good practice.</p> <p>The "Back-up" sheet gathers the drop-down lists info of the "Database" sheet. Yo don-t have to fill anything here.</p>		
<p>Task Description: This task will perform a deep dive into good practices of regional governments supporting local operators and innovation developers via appropriate business models and social measures. A screening exercise will help us make an inventory (long list) of 50 good practices within and outside the ROBIN regions. Then, the good practices will be assessed against specific criteria to select a list of 10 cases to be further studied. Partners MTU, AUTh and S2I will develop at least 10 case studies showcasing how regional government has encouraged social innovation and business models to promote circular bioeconomy. The long list of good practices will be classified under the typology of T1.2, providing practical inspiration for our regions to improve their governance models.</p>		
Database fields		
0	Expected info	Expected format
Num	A numeration field for data management	A number
Good practice name	Name of the good governance practice identified	Short text (5-10 words)
Country / Region	Country/ region/locality where the practice has been implemented	Short text
Year Implemented	Year that the good practice was implemented within the specific region	A number
Problem Statement	Context of the deployment of good practice (Example: does the good practice help to resolve a barrier, or initiate an action to support local operators?)	Short text (50 words max.)
Executive summary	Descriptive and short summary of the selected good practice	Short text (50 - 100 words max.)
Type of practice	Choose from the drop down list the term which best describes the model of practice e.g. social innovation, public procurement model, educational model, incentive model, non-financial business support, other	Drop Down List
If Other	Complete if other is chosen in Type of practice column	Short text
Good Governance Practice Description	Longer Description of the Good Practice:	Long text (200 - 250 words max.)
	What were the main drivers?	
	What were the ambitions of the practice?	
	What barriers were needed to be overcome?	
	What was the enabling potential of implementation?	
	Was it developed through a project (FP, Interreg, EIP Agri, BBI, CBE JU etc)?	
Was it part of a governmental measure?		
Who was the promoter of the practice?		
Deployment Setting	Choose from the drop down list the geographical context of deployment (urban, Peri-urban, rural, coastal, mountainous / upland, multiple, other)	Drop Down List
If Other	Complete if other is chosen in Deployment Settings column	Short text
Replication potential	Has it been transferred or is it transferrable to other regions or sectors? If not, is there potential to transfer and replicate	Short text (1 - 20 words)
Regional deployment considerations	Important deployment barriers for other regions, if any	Short text (1-20 words)
Stakeholders / Beneficiaries	Choose from the drop down list the type of stakeholder that is most supported by the good practice	Drop Down List
If Other	Complete if other is chosen in Stakeholder / Beneficiaries column	Short text
Level of Uptake	Number of stakeholders availing or subscribing to the good practices	Drop Down List
Is the practice currently in operation?	Is the practice currently in operation within the region?	Short text (1 - 5 words)
Number of years that the measure has been operational in the region	How long since it's introduction has the practice been in operation within the region?	A Number
Environmental Impact	Environmental impact or benefits resulting from implementation of good practice, if relevant	Short text (20 - 40 words)
Social Impact	Social impact or benefits resulting from implementation of good practice, if relevant	Short text (20 - 40 words)
Economic Impact	Economic impact or benefits resulting from implementation of good practice, if relevant	Short text (20 - 40 words)
Organisation name	Name of the responsible organisation or authority that has implemented or oversees the good practice	Short text
Typology of circular bioeconomy governance model	Which type of circular bioeconomy governance model does this fall in, according to the typologies defined in T1.2	Short text (5-10 words) Filled by MTU and AuTh
Contact Person	Contact person for the organisation	Short text
Link (mandatory)	Link to the detailed info of about the good practice	A web link